

**AUTHORIAL FRAMEWORK AND THE
PROBLEM OF STYLE THROUGH A
COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS OF
NEO-LATIN DRAMA**

UTRECHT UNIVERSITY

**AUTHORIAL FRAMEWORK AND THE PROBLEM
OF STYLE THROUGH A COMPUTATIONAL
ANALYSIS OF NEO-LATIN DRAMA**

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I, Andrea Peverelli, hereby declare that the thesis titled "*Authorial Framework and the Problem of Style through a Computational Analysis of Neo-Latin Drama*" and its content are the result of my own work.

I confirm that:

- This work was primarily conducted during my pursuit of a research degree at this university.
- If any portion of this thesis has been previously submitted for an academic degree or any other qualification at these universities or any other educational institution, I have explicitly disclosed this information.
- I have consistently acknowledged the sources of published works by other authors that I consulted.
- In cases where I have included excerpts from the work of others, I have consistently provided proper source attributions. Aside from these quotations, the entirety of this thesis represents my independent effort.
- I have acknowledged all significant sources of assistance.
- In cases where this thesis draws upon collaborative efforts with others, I have provided a clear distinction between the contributions made by collaborators and my own individual contributions.

[22/11/2024]

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INTRODUCTION

Humanism and the Renaissance were crucial phenomena of early modern Europe, beginning around 1300 in Italy and around 1450 in northern Europe. One of their key aspects was the relative laicisation of culture. Whereas in the Middle Ages learning and teaching had been the prerogative of the Church, in the fifteenth century schools that were separate from the Church began to appear throughout Europe. These institutions of 'new learning', entirely in Latin, were run by humanists who embodied one of the tenets of the humanist tradition: to go *ad fontes*, that is to study the classics not primarily as a means of developing the Christian faith, but as they were in themselves, a heritage of the golden age of classical antiquity, with philological respect. As part of this development, ancient drama was rediscovered as a literary genre worth reading in its own right. Authors such as Plautus and Seneca, and to some extent Greek playwrights, who had almost been forgotten, were brought to new light and read at the schools as means to learn Latin conversation. However, in the transition from an 'ecclesiastical' to a 'secular' culture, it must be emphasised that the humanists, although they had a different focus, were still Christians and had Christian morals and values, which they were able to combine with values and morals of classical antiquity. Through their common language, Latin, the humanists in early modern Europe formed an international *respublica literaria*, a "republic of letters": an overarching community of intellectuals from all countries who communicated, exchanged knowledge, grew together and often struggled over ideas. In the case of drama, this republic of letters had its main centres in the Latin schools and universities, where many of their teachers and headmasters wrote new Latin dramas, inspired by the classics, and used them in their teaching programmes. Thousands and thousands of such texts were written and performed throughout Europe, and while many plays remained local or regional, some circulated across political, geographical and temporal boundaries. Teachers and students wrote, taught, read, copied, rehearsed and performed plays which, as they circulated, often transcended religious and political affiliations: a Catholic comedy from the Low Countries could be received and imitated in a comedy by a Protestant author in Bohemia, a tragicomedy from Norway could appear in Rome. The circulation of Neo-Latin drama, of similar dignity and value to that produced in a vernacular language (a gap in some cases bridged by translations, both from Latin into a vernacular language and vice versa), had a truly transnational and pan-European character. Not only did plays circulate, but some authors also travelled throughout Europe, coming into contact with other centres of writing and teaching, mixing their own backgrounds, enriching their own styles, and using Latin as a common international language of communication. In the words of [Bloemendal and Norland \(2013\)](#) (5):

"In this changing world, Latin drama was written and read, rehearsed and performed, all over Europe. It was a 'coat of many colours', comprising tragedy, comedy, farce and tragicomedy, varying in length, outspokenly confessional, Protestant or Catholic, or demolishing the walls between the religions, taking its subjects from the Bible, the saints' lives, fairy tales, history, daily life and school life, and finally offering moral, religious or intellectual lessons of various kinds, or just entertainment, or a defence of the humanist cause."

Because of the transnational aspect of Neo-Latin drama, in its ability to transcend boundaries, another crucial aspect to consider is precisely that of religion and faith. For some time, early modern drama was torn between two extremes. On the one hand, classical theatre was considered by many to be a legacy of paganism (following the hostile statements of Saint Augustine and other Church Fathers; see [Dox \(2004\)](#)), and was therefore viewed negatively, also because humanists considered that it often conveyed an idea of moral licentiousness. On the other hand, in the early decades of the sixteenth century, some writers and theologians of Protestant confession such as Martin Luther spoke favourably of theatre as a means of teaching and moral education, and in a few years they raised its importance to a true "sermon, catechesis and an act of worship or a service" ([Washof \(2007\)](#), 55). The Catholic counterpart was quick to recognise the great didactic value of drama. Half a century later, the Jesuit Order, which had always a particular focus on teaching and mission and made themselves the champions of the Counter-Reformation, used dramas in their education to teach Latin and theological ideas and morals, and to prepare students for missionary activities. Thus, as we have seen, numerous dramas were written by school teachers, who replaced the 'pagan' plays of Plautus and Terence and the tragedies of Seneca by their own plays. Playwrights chose all sorts of subjects, but often dramatised biblical stories and passages, to the point of generating a whole sub-genre, that of "sacred drama", writing *comoediae sacrae* or the *tragoediae sacrae* in which the tenets of the authors' respective faiths were often upheld. The authors were either Roman Catholic or Protestant – in one of the many varieties of Protestantism – and could in fact sometimes express their own beliefs in their plays. All these aspects together contributed to a renaissance of the theatre in the early modern period, with the same aspects of internationality and cross-linguistic communication of values that humanism in general espoused. Thousands of plays are known to have been written between the second half of the fifteenth century and the second half of the eighteenth, and although many have survived either in manuscript or in print, a large number of them are now lost.

This vast corpus, or what is digitally accessible and usable, provides the framework within which I develop my dissertation, situated in the context of the TransLatin project¹. The project investigates the transnational circulation and impact of early modern Neo-Latin drama, an almost entirely neglected chapter of European literary history. It aims to map its interactions with other vernacular productions of the same period by analysing the extent of the transnational *respublica literaria*, with a particular focus on the Netherlands. Using the collection of texts gathered in the TransLatin project, my research combines traditional close reading literary analyses with digital and computational methods to explore this corpus in new ways. As Miguel Escobar Varela points out in Theater as Data, computational

¹<https://translatin.nl/>

theatre research offers a dual advantage: it enables "reasoning under constraints" to reveal hidden patterns in large textual corpora while also "problematizing assumptions" to open new interpretive horizons (Varela (2021), p. 9). These methodologies resonate with this thesis's goal of integrating data-driven analyses to uncover stylistic and thematic trends within Neo-Latin drama, while simultaneously interrogating how these plays circulated across political, linguistic, and confessional boundaries.

The focus on Neo-Latin drama is not simply a convenient choice for testing computational methods; it is fundamental to a deeper understanding of European literary and cultural history. Often overlooked in favor of immensely popular vernacular literature like that of Shakespeare or Marlowe, Neo-Latin drama played a central role in the intellectual and public discourse of the early modern period. Its dialogical nature made it an ideal medium for exploring and debating themes from biblical and classical literature, thus engaging with political, religious, and moral issues of the time. As several scholars have noted (IJsewijn (1970), Celenza (2004)), the Latin tradition has been vastly underestimated in discussions of Renaissance and early modern literature, despite its significant influence on shaping European thought and culture. The transnational reach and public accessibility of Neo-Latin drama allowed it to transcend linguistic and national boundaries, fostering an international dialogue.

By focusing on these texts, my research addresses the current myopia in literary studies that tends to neglect the substantial impact of Latin plays that circulated widely across Europe. In this light, the integration of Digital Humanities methods into my analysis is not only innovative, but necessary. These methods enable large-scale, data-driven investigations that can reveal patterns and connections previously hidden within this vast, multilingual corpus. This approach enriches our understanding of Neo-Latin drama's contribution to European culture and challenges the traditional narratives that have long dominated literary historiography, ultimately demonstrating the genre's crucial role in the broader history of European literature.

0.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

My research is centered around building and analysing a network of interconnected works and geo-chronologically distributed similar texts: a story network. "Story networks consist of stories and links between stories that represent pre-textual relationships. Stories that are more similar to each other are more likely to stand in a pre-textual relationship than stories that are more distant" (Karsdorp and van den Bosch (2016), 5). Pre-texts are particularly influential "models" that authors adopt and adapt. These "relationships" between texts are embodied by their level of stylistic similarity. Since early modern drama authors were inserted in the aforementioned transnational *respublica literaria*, and often read and took inspiration (both in style and content) from either the classics or other contemporary authors, the first research question is:

1. *How can the extensive network of stylistic textual similarities within early modern drama be mapped and quantified through computational means?*

Searching for an answer to this question prompted me to generate a composite pipeline for the computational analysis of literature by focusing on the similarities between texts and the way of writing of their authors, that is, their *style*. Early modern drama offers

a case study to test historical assumptions. With a combination of methods I tackle the question of to what extent the style of one play resembles that of another. With this method, I can draw connections between authors. The method can be applied to other genres as well, dealing with general aspects of literary imitation such as detecting the emergence of "hubs of reuse" (clusters of influential models and towards which other groups of authors show strong stylistic connections), the imitation of classics, and the influence on style of elements such as personal and social background. Style is of course a contentious term that has centuries of attempts at a definition, resulting in what Ray (2015) describes as "a cacophony of definitions". Contemporary studies (Herrmann et al. (2015), 4 and 14; Ray (2015); Anbeek and Verhagen (2001), 6-11; Andereg (2008), 1017-1091; Simpson (2004), 22-30; Wales (2001); Stamatas (2009), 1-24) though agree that there is a convergence among the different traditions on some common, recurring elements in the components of style, such as: the result of choices of expression among alternatives, an expression of individuality and subjectivity of an author, the deviation from a type of norm, and "any property of a text that can be measured computationally" (Herrmann et al. (2015), 4). I here refer to the latter, a more operational and pragmatic conceptualisation of style, that of computational nature, which "allows statements about style in some unit of analysis (e.g., text part, author, genre) in comparison with a wide range of reference data (other text parts, other authors, other genres)" (Herrmann et al. (2015), 16). Computational methodologies aim at identifying a large quantity of style markers (also called stylomes or authorial signal in the Stylometric tradition) in terms of frequencies and co-occurrences: "a certain style can be described using methods based on computing frequencies, relations, and distributions of features and relevant statistics" between textual segments within a single text between multiple texts, so that "frequencies of selected elements can be quantitatively related across a collection of individual texts [...] using a larger reference corpus as a backdrop", as "stylistic computations hence allow statements about style in some unit of analysis (e. g., text part, author, genre) in comparison with a wide range of reference data (other text parts, other authors, other genres)" (Herrmann et al. (2015), 15). It is thus that, starting from a specific corpus as a standard, I develop, tweak according to the nature of our corpus, and test several methodologies from the field of Computational Linguistics and Natural Language Processing to trace stylistic similarities between texts and authors in a twofold perspective:

- Style as an internal structure: defined as the sum of the similarities and overlaps between textual segments, both inter- (between different texts) and intra- (within the same text) text overlaps.
- Style as influenced by external elements, defined not only as the "choices writers make", but also its "expression of social identity" (Ray (2015), 16), and thus as the constellation of a) contextual features, such as background, social network, ideals, education, faith and confession, and b) paratextual and pretextual elements, such as genre, place of publication, diffusion, time and age: "style can be associated with categories such as genre, epoch, author, and many more. [...] Genre can cause style (e.g. by means of conventions: form and themes), authors can cause style (e.g. by means of idiosyncrasies), theme and topic can cause style. [...] Any stylistic phenomenon can ultimately be considered the trace of or the index towards such categories" (Herrmann et al. (2015), 16).

These individual elements together define our operational definition of style: the sum of a text's internal and external features that can be analysed computationally. The second group of elements, that of external factors, leads to a second central question:

2 To what degree do internal and external factors of style interact, and how much do external elements influence style?

This is a central aspect to be considered, since style is also defined as the expression of societal identity aspects like the ones we mentioned above. As such, it is of paramount importance to also analyse the influence of religion and genre in our corpus. The early modern period was rife with conflicts between Catholic and Protestant parties, and at the same time the models of classical Latin authors loomed large when it came to structure, style and content. The impact of external elements like religious background and the role of models on the writing of early modern dramatists comes with a set of further considerations from a literary and cultural history point of view. Always keeping in mind that a drama is not a theological treatise, a high degree of religious affiliation towards the two opposing confessions can be gleaned from dramas. But how strong this actually is? How well defined between the two sides? Are there grey areas, meeting points, overlaps? How much can we discover from the often obscure and fluid interaction between the two confessions? We know from previous literary and cultural assumptions that, for example, Catholics (Jesuits especially) had a much more defined, dense and unified approach to writing, coming from a solid tradition that could not be questioned; Protestants, on the other hand, still in the process of forming a coherent thought system and ever fractured between many sub-confessions, showed a more open and less definable approach, both in the choice of models for their inspiration and in their writing style. With my experiments, I give empirical arguments to further this discussion. To give an example, I deal with the supposed presence of Terence's *auctoritas* in Shakespeare: while his influence is clear in the choice of themes and characters, to the point that Shakespeare was saluted as "our English Terence" by his contemporaries (John Davies, *The Shakespeare Allusion Book*, 1219), I demonstrate his style could not be farther away, showing absolute extraneousness to Terence in an experiment with early modern corpora in 4 languages. Again on the same matter of *auctoritates*, Plautus is known to be one of the major sources for early modern drama writers, being cited countless times in their letters and comments. This is not shown in their actual writing: our experiment demonstrates that early modern playwrights betray no traces of Plautine style whatsoever, in any of their texts, instead favouring either Terence or Seneca. This shows a severance between theory and practice from early modern writers that was not evident before. This is all captured by my experiments, where I give substantiation to each of these claims through data-driven analyses. My thesis thus takes an approach that is not only methodological, in a Digital Humanities environment, but also tackles issues of literary and cultural history in a novel way, with the ultimate goal of furthering these fields by, on the one hand, confirming or refuting claims, and, on the other, making substantiation to assumptions measurable and replicable.

0.2 CORPUS BUILDING AND PRE-PROCESSING

To answer my research questions, I built a pipeline for the stylistic inquiry of historical literary texts with a main focus on early modern Neo-Latin drama, eventually moving to a

multi-language environment. I started with gathering a corpus of dramas written in Latin and then expanded it with texts in other languages (Italian, French, English, German, Dutch), from the ones available in the TransLatin Project repository. These texts range from the end of the 1400s to the mid 1700s, with some outliers of earlier and later texts. Varying compositions of this corpus are used throughout the experiments, corresponding to the different stages of gathering and processing of the many texts at our disposal, with the last experiment using the largest number and variety of languages. Before proceeding with the actual analyses though, I needed to pre-process the dramas to yield a corpus that can be used in multiple types of computational analyses. The texts I use in my experiments come from a process of OCR-digitisation, which is replete with computationally-unnecessary textual artefacts (annotations, scribbles, unrecognised characters, and even errors). Besides, the text often presents different orthographic and phonetic solutions, as Neo-Latin, while highly normalised and unified, was still prone to typographical differences. I therefore turned these texts into a machine-operable form that has a unified and plain layout. This eases the processing by an algorithm or a program to reach a quick and automatic extraction of information. It often involves a process of automatic cleaning and manual check, which can be painstaking. Drama texts in particular involve extra steps that are not usually involved in other types of texts: depending on the kind of analysis one is performing, the "dramatic" textual layer (verse number and type, character notations, act-scene boundaries, prologues and choruses markings...) is one that can be expunged as part of pre-processing. I applied this last layer, since the present research did not involve any analysis that could have leveraged this layer. To achieve a faster and more precise pre-processing of the Latin texts in my corpus, I wrote a custom program, called CURRENS². This program answers the need for a free, user-friendly, customly-modifiable and complete pre-processing pipeline for Latin. It automatically handles several Latin-specific issues with great speed and accuracy, and it is built modularly, with a core general-purpose module and three optional (which deal with different aspects of Latin pre-processing: enclitics, archaisms and stopwords) that can be activated depending on one's needs.

Although these steps are done automatically, manual checking for errors and consistency was still performed, and the "dramatic layer" was still cleaned manually, because it was too text-specific to be generalised as patterns recognisable by a program such as CURRENS. As for the other languages, the NLTK (Natural Language Processing Toolkit)³ was used for pre-processing.

0.3 METHODOLOGY

The present thesis builds on three main sets of methodologies, that deal with three layers of a literary text:

1. Content. Semantic-related methods: weight and distance measures (TF-IDF, Cosine), Topic Modelling, Word Embeddings.
2. Language features. Stylometry and Network Analysis;
3. Metadata. Machine Learning for Feature Prediction and Text Classification.

²<https://github.com/AndrewPeverells/CURRENS>

³<https://www.nltk.org/>

The first group of methods - including TF-IDF, Cosine Similarity, and also Topic Modelling approaches such as LDA - share a reliance on the Bag-of-Words (BoW) assumption: that is, they do not take into consideration a) the order of words in a text, and b) the size of a text, while still keeping statistical multiplicity (frequency). TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) and Cosine Similarity are well known scoring statistics, used in a wide variety of Information Retrieval and Natural Language Processing tasks, often in conjunction with more complex analyses. They both rely on transforming tokens (words) in a string (sentence) into mathematical representations (vectors) in an n-dimensional space, where each dimension corresponds to a single word-vector. TF-IDF represents the weight, and thus the importance, of a word in a collection of documents (texts), with words appearing fewer times across all documents being assigned more weight.

Cosine similarity is a measure often used in conjunction with TF-IDF, as it is a complementary and further statistic that calculates how similar two vector-words (previously transformed as such by TF-IDF) are. The two vector-words are drawn in a space (their dimension) and the distance between them (the cosine of their angle) shows how similar those two words are. The score is calculated in a range between 0 (orthogonality, no overlap) and 1 (perfect overlap). Combined, these two measures can yield a degree of similarity between texts, regardless of their size and internal syntax (order of words).

They both are widely used measures with a plethora of possible applications, especially in the field of Information Retrieval ([Manning et al. \(2008\)](#); [Connor \(2016\)](#)), but they have been used with particular success in different forms of text analysis ([Manjavacas et al. \(2019\)](#); [Sturgeon \(2018\)](#)), where sets of words within the same text or among different texts are compared to unveil similarities. This is what I employ these measures for in Chapter 1: starting from TF-IDF's assumption that words that appear fewer times across all texts have a higher weight, and thus they are going to be particularly important content words⁴, I implement Cosine similarity as a means to compare these low-frequency, high-importance content words between texts.

Both topic modelling and word embeddings have a long history of development and usage, and they rely on the often cited motto by J. R. Firth "you shall know a word by the company it keeps" ([Firth \(1957\)](#)): that is, the basic distributional semantics assumption of "co-occurrence" ([Lenci \(2018\)](#) 152-153). Topic modelling is an Information Retrieval and Text Mining semantic-based methodology that clusters words together, based on their patterns of co-occurrence within a corpus. These co-occurrence patterns help infer latent topics, which are conceptualised as a "probability distribution over a fixed vocabulary" ([Blei et al. \(2003\)](#), 994). When discussing certain themes, some words are more likely to appear together in the same context, like, for example, "pitch", "player" and "goal" when talking of football. This collection is a distribution of probabilities, meaning that words in the topic have different likelihoods of showing up. On a whole text level, a document is considered a mixture of topics, with some dominating over others, and thus revealing the general theme. While in the end topic modelling implementations contemplate a process of manual review, where annotators identify distributions of words as coherent topics and assign them labels, several algorithms have been developed through the years. LDA, or Latent Dirichlet Allocation, ([Blei et al. \(2003\)](#)) was the first and most successful of these, being at the base of a plethora

⁴Words that bear semantic meaning, as opposed to function words or stop-words, syntactic connectors like conjunctions, subordinations and interjections.

of subsequent algorithms, like the ones I employ in Chapter 4 (MALLET and scikit-LDA) to identify thematic patterns in common across generations of early modern drama writers. Like other BoW-based approaches, LDA follows the same working principles of the BoW approach explained earlier. It models texts as mixtures of topics, leveraging distributions of probabilities of words appearing in a topic to cluster each document around the most probable topics, allowing the user to uncover underlying themes without any prior knowledge of what they might be in an unknown text.

Word embeddings is another semantic, BoW-based model that calculates the similarity of words like in other measures (Cosine Similarity), but, instead of treating each word as independent, words are put in a mathematical vector space where similar ones are close together. For example, "ball" and "player" would be closer in this space, while "ball" and "car" would be kept further apart. In this process, the role of context is central, as words that appear together in similar situations over a text end up closer in the resulting model. To achieve this, embedding models rely on the process of dimensionality reduction, where the relations between words are simplified over a smaller number of dimensions, usually between 100 and 300, to allow a precise and dense representation of similar words in a context. Word embedding models are powerful tools that can capture nuanced semantic similarity in a wide variety different tasks (language translation, meaning variation, similarity and analogy, named entity recognition, text classification, etc.), and have also been successfully employed in the conjunction between historical languages such as Latin and the analysis of language features (Sprugnoli et al. (2020), Sprugnoli et al. (2021)) and even literary phenomena such as intertextuality (Burns et al. (2021)). Following these examples, in Chapter 3, alongside topic modelling, I make use of word embeddings to develop a model that can highlight subtle semantic differences between the two opposing confessions in our early modern drama corpus (Catholic and Protestant), by extensively comparing the two main embeddings architectures: Continuous Bag of Words (CBOW), which predicts the target word from its context words, and Skip-gram, which does the opposite, predicting surrounding words from a given word.

The second category of methodologies, Stylometry (and its related Network analysis), has a radically different assumption at its base, dealing more with the structural phenomena of a text and its linguistic features rather than its contents: it can be described as a set of techniques that rely on analysing and comparing frequencies of "most frequent words" (MFWs), which, as per Zipf's Law, are going to be, for the vast majority, either function words (opposed to content words) or very frequent content words, depending on the nature and thematic of the analysed text (Eder (2016)). The assumption that function words (defined by Fries, 1952, as words that bear little or no meaning and "signal the structural relationship between content words") account for a large portion of a text and will thus be the most frequent, goes together with another principle of Stylometry: the distribution of MFWs (the relationship between their frequency and their positioning along a text) is identified as a set of *stylomes*, stylistic idiosyncrasies peculiar of an author or a single text that, as a whole, yield generalised patterns of *usus scribendi* and similarities between authors. A writer could be more keen on using the definite article "the" rather than the indefinite "a", or may show a higher count than average of adverbs, or could sport a preference towards feminine-marked words rather than masculine, or vice-versa, an element

that could be crucial in identifying the hidden identity of a writer behind a pseudonym (as in the famous case of Elena Ferrante's international bestseller *L'amica geniale*, identified in Eder (2018) as the male writer Domenico Starnone). Because of this, while originally, and primarily, developed for tasks such as authorship attribution and plagiarism detection, Stylometry further developed as a valuable aid to literary studies that deal with stylistic matters. Stylometry was defined as a set of techniques because it encompasses several Machine Learning approaches (Clustering, Component analysis, Support Vector Machines, etc.) to achieve the result of a coherent stylistic analysis. It is this variation of the stylometric approach that I employ across multiple chapters and experiments, always with the aim of identifying stylistic connections between drama writers, whether between our early modern corpus and a classical *auctoritas* (Chapter 2), or within the same corpus of writers (Chapter 1, 5).

A common outcome of a stylometric analysis, among others, is a network, the visualisation of the clustering of authors based on their similarities as a graph of nodes (single instances of authors/texts) and edges (their relations, expressed as mathematical values). I perform this process of visualisation and further analysis on graphs resulting from a stylometric analysis across all chapters that involve Stylometry, ending up with several types of networks and graphs throughout the experiments.

Finally, the last category of methodologies comprises the Machine Learning tasks of Prediction and Classification. Machine Learning is a vast set of techniques and algorithms that can be applied to an immensely broad selection of tasks. It can involve supervised approaches, where the involvement of the user in shaping the approach and tweaking the parameters is substantial, or unsupervised approaches, where it is instead minimal. Prediction and Classification form a sub-category of mixed supervised-unsupervised applications that deal with the challenge of assigning items (words, documents) to the correct group or label. For example, a typical task would be sorting emails as either "spam" or "not spam" (a binary problem), or classifying book genres as "fiction," "non-fiction," "biography," etc. (a multi-class problem). The final goal of the algorithm is to correctly identify or predict the label of new, unseen items after it has learned from a set of labeled examples. The process typically involves three steps: training the algorithm with examples of already labelled data (the "training set"); learning from data, where the algorithm studies the input data and learns its patterns, looking for features that help making the final decision of assigning elements to the correct label; testing and prediction, where the algorithm is tested on new, unseen data ("test set") to assess its precision. As a result, the role of metadata (enriching data with labels that describe it) is crucial, because it provides the algorithm with the necessary information it needs to learn and perform its task, and thus the quality of the input data and its labels largely decides the output performance. I tackle these specific issues in Chapter 4, where I develop a classification and prediction algorithm for the automatic identification of linguistic features that define and distinguish the two religious backgrounds of our corpus, Catholic and Protestant. This experiment demonstrates how to achieve very precise and meaningful results in describing what determines the two backgrounds and analysing their overlaps.

0.4 THESIS STRUCTURE AND SUMMARY OF CHAPTERS

This thesis contains 5 chapters, made up of mostly published papers in Digital Humanities and Computational Linguistics conferences and journals. The papers presented here answer the different questions in several ways and stages.

Chapters 1 and 2 tackle research question 1, with two perspectives:

- Paper 1, *Tracking Textual Similarities in Neo-Latin Drama Networks*;
- Paper 2, *The process of imitatio through stylometric analysis: the case of Terence's Eunuchus*.

The first experiment is an overall general birds-eye view on Neo-Latin drama with a combination of a set of weight and distance measures (TF-IDF, Cosine similarity) and Stylometry, that map the authors' stylistic relations between themselves and the creation of hubs of re-use. The main result is that I found Early Modern drama networks follow real-world evolutionary networks with a pattern of evolution defined by a S-TA/MA model (spatial-temporal attractiveness and modal attractiveness: authors tend to prefer models closer to them in time and space): this model shows that it exhibits clear patterns of connection based on similarity. With this paper I tackle the issues and nuances of pre-processing historical drama texts, and I give more evidence to the extensive process of imitation and reuse between early modern era authors, which built strong relations and communities based on similar stylomes. The second experiment gradually delves deeper into the texts and deals with another form of imitation, the one towards classics (*auctoritates*), using a specific play as a test case. This completes the initial inquiry, starting from a network analysis of Neo-Latin dramas and eventually ending up within the analysis of the structure of a single drama as a case study and its relations with other close texts in a multi-language environment (involving 4 different language corpora). In this experiment, I devise a stylometric methodology for the inquiry of literary imitation (at least limited to early modern literature). With this approach, I track the stylistic shifts and the reuse of stylomes tied to specific passages of an original drama, and I also propose a possible solution for dealing with multi-language corpora.

Chapters 3 and 4 deal with research question 2:

- Paper 3, *Tracing Themes and Topics in Neo-Latin Drama through Topic Modelling and Word Embeddings*;
- Paper 4, *When a Catholic Comedy looks like a Protestant Tragedy: Predicting Religious and Genre Features in Neo-Latin Drama*.

These two complementary papers deal with bridging between style as an internal factor, described in Chapters 1 and 2, and style as a constellation of external elements. In particular, I inquire the two primary defining contextual aspects of early modern drama writing: literary genre and religion. By first using Neo-Latin, I create an operational basis for future models that involve other languages, and a replicable pipeline that can be applied to other languages, corpora, genres and periods, for the inquiry of the influence of external elements on style. The first paper deals with setting up a semantic analysis through the complementary usage

of topic modelling and word embeddings. With these, I measure the impact of overarching literary genre and religious background on the stylistic patterns of our corpus. The second deals with training Machine Learning algorithms to automatically predict these external features. Through a Text Classification and Feature Prediction task, I can differentiate between them and highlight the importance of each of our two chosen feature on the overall textual structure. With these papers I define how external, contextual elements shape the language of early modern writers in clear and predictable patterns, demonstrating that the inquiry of contextuality is productive and informative about an author's style by means of unveiling specific age- and literary history-related phenomena and general underlying trends.

Chapter 5 presents our last paper and it serves as a wrap-up to the project, presenting overall results that follow both lines of inquiry (question 1 and 2):

- Publication 5, *A Stylometric and Network Analysis of a Multi-lingual Early Modern Drama Corpus*

In this chapter, I complete the analysis of the authorial framework by, on the one hand, inquiring internal similarities within the same text and clusters of authors. On the other hand, I evaluate and external, contextual elements through labelled metadata. The final aim is to create a complete overview of the process of imitation and reception within a large corpus of early modern drama writers: to achieve this, I produce multiple visualisation graphs through stylometric and network analysis, that show the layered amount of interconnected data and metadata (stylistic similarities, publication date, religious background, genre, thematic).

Finally, Chapter 6 concludes the dissertation by revisiting the Research Questions and exploring the implications of my findings in a broader point of view.

1

TRACKING TEXTUAL SIMILARITIES

This paper describes the first experiments towards tracking the complex and international network of text reuse within the Early Modern (XV-XVII centuries) community of Neo-Latin humanists. Our research, conducted within the framework of the TransLatin project, aims at gaining more evidence on the topic of textual similarities and semi-conscious reuse of literary models. It consists of two experiments conveyed through two main research fields (Information Retrieval and Stylometry), as a means to a better understanding of the complex and subtle literary mechanisms underlying the drama production of Modern Age authors and their transnational network of relations. The experiments led to the construction of networks of works and authors that fashion different patterns of similarity and models of evolution and interaction between texts.

The content of this chapter was previously published as: Andrea Peverelli, Marieke van Erp, and Jan Bloemendal. Tracking Textual Similarities in Neo-Latin Drama Networks. In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference*, pages 5295–5303, Marseille, France. European Language Resources Association, 2022.

The division of work in this chapter is as follows: main experiment design and execution by Andrea Peverelli, contributions to the original idea and its development and proof-reading by Marieke van Erp and Jan Bloemendal.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

One of the defining characteristics of the early Modern Era, burgeoning from the Italian Renaissance period, is the wide international network of exchanges between writers of different nationalities that bears the Latin name of *respublica literaria* (Republic of Letters)¹ Authors feel part of a wider, universal, intellectual community, and their authorial signal can and must be read especially in light of its complex network of interdependent exchanges with other peers.

Tracking instances of textual reuse and similarities between works thus comes as the prime reflection of the complexities of the *respublica literaria*. Relations between authors are primarily expressed through writing and an intense, foregoing discussion upon the reuse of models (that is, the hot topic of *imitatio*).

Besides the vast literary production in the various natural languages of Europe, the early Modern Age is characterised by a wide, if barely known, production in Latin from the first sparks of Humanism in the Italian Peninsula during the XIV century. The production of poetry and prose in Latin increased dramatically, and drama began to be involved in this process in great quantities (at least 10,000 works are known from this period; see [Bloemendal et al. \(2022\)](#)). The Low Countries were at the forefront of this revitalisation, thanks especially to the outstanding work of Erasmus.

Early Modern Latin (or “Neo-Latin”) was very different from the one written and spoken in the former medieval centuries. According to [Bloemendal and Norland \(2013\)](#), Neo-Latin was characterised by: “a shift [from the Middle Ages] in the use from a pragmatic one (if necessary, new words could be coined, even ‘unclassical’ ones, and syntactic means could be used as seemed fit), to a principled one, which should aim at writing ‘classical’ Latin morphologically and syntactically”. This, paired with the general methodology typical of Humanism of “going ad fontes” (i.e. to strictly adhere to the original classical texts), makes for a close resemblance of early Modern Latin to the classical standards. It thus comes naturally that comparison with classical authors is, in the topic of textual similarity, particularly meaningful as a means of clustering authors within common ancestries.

Whether conscious text reuse or coincidental resemblance, textual similarity can be viewed in a twofold manner, based on its presence or absence: when present, it is a measure of the closeness between two texts, so that one of them can be read as a means of relations to the other one; when instead absent, it represents their degree of distance (or “dissimilarity”), and it is as important as its counterpart. Moreover, dissimilarity can be a criterion for further inquiries: as a standard measure between two texts, to state their closeness under different literary aspects (style, content, space and time, etc.); or as a marker for a more subtle closeness to be found in a common ancestry back in time or in another unrelated place, in the form of a predecessor, or “pre-text” shared by both texts. The concept of pre-text within evolutionary networks is well explained in *The structure and evolution of story networks* [Karsdorp and van den Bosch \(2016\)](#), by which our research was inspired. According to them: “Story networks consist of stories and links between stories that represent pre-textual relationships. We make the simplifying assumption that stories that are more similar to each other are more likely to stand in a pre-textual relationship than stories that are more distant”. While the focus of their paper is on “storied retellings” (well-defined story frames

¹The concept appears for the first time in an epistolary exchange between the humanists Francesco Barbaro and Poggio Bracciolini at the start of the XV century. See [van Miert \(2022\)](#) for a recent reading on the topic.

towards which heavy text reuse is ascertained as a starting point), our own verges on a more explorative approach: trying to discover the very existence of a complex network of textual reuses and its internal strategies.

Our research question is formulated within the framework of the [TransLatin Project](#), which tries to inquire this very notion and blends perfectly with the aim of our paper: what is the extent of the process of imitation and reception within Neo-Latin drama? Are any authors connected at all? Which ones serve as the strongest pre-texts (in literary terms: “models”) for the others? To answer these questions we made our first steps towards a thorough investigation of similarities networks, while being aware of the wide arrange of tools for text reuse detection, through two different methodologies: Cosine Similarity and Bootstrap Consensus Trees.

The contributions of this paper are as follows:

- CURRENS: a new tool for the pre-processing of Latin texts:
- insights into reuse of Neo-Latin Drama;
- new applications of known methodologies, drawn from Information Retrieval and Stylometry, towards the topic of textual similarities.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In section 1.3 we explain the criteria that we followed for preparing our corpus. In section 1.4 we get into details about the experimental setup. In section 1.5 we discuss the results. Finally, in section 1.6 we consider future steps and draw conclusions about our whole experiment.

1.2 RELATED WORK

In the last decade, several tools have been made available for tracking proper text reuse through text alignment or feature extraction for historical languages. The most well-known of these tools (TRACER,² Tesseract,³ and Passim⁴) have also been tested for Latin: one of the last experiments is that of [Franzini et al. \(2018\)](#), in which a thorough exploration of HTRD (*Historical Text Reuse Detection*) tools can be found. These tools can be quite powerful in detecting precise reuse, both intentional and unintentional, in the forms of quoting and allusion. While more traditional HTRD methods will be employed in the future, we wanted to explore the possibilities of the application of older approaches (Cosine Similarity and Stylometry) to a novel case study, shifting towards a more general textual similarity framework that will serve as a solid base for future inquiries. As for Cosine Similarity, [Manjavacas et al. \(2019\)](#) approached allusive textual reuse detection on a Latin Biblical corpus from an Information Retrieval standpoint: through an extensive usage of Cosine Similarity scores and Word Embeddings [Manjavacas et al. \(2019\)](#), they found that custom query algorithms for automatic allusion detection were consistently outperformed by simpler TF-IDF models and that Cosine Similarity can prove a sound basis for inquiring textual reuse. Other studies, such as [Bär et al. \(2012\)](#) and [Sturgeon \(2018\)](#), employed Cosine Similarity and TF-IDF scores, in text reuse and similarity detection with good results,

²<https://www.etrapp.eu/research/tracer/> Last visited: 16/1/2021

³tesseract.caset.buffalo.edu Last visited: 16/1/2021

⁴<https://github.com/dasmiq/Passim> Last visited: 16/1/2021

both for contemporary language corpora (the former, which was tested on the METER corpus and the Webis Crowd Paraphrase corpus) and historical language corpora (the latter, which worked on an Early Chinese corpus). As for stylometric approaches, the use of Stylometry for textual similarity and reuse detection is ample. Some experiments have also been conducted upon historical languages, especially Latin (cf. [Eder \(2017a\)](#)) and Ancient Greek [Gorman and Gorman \(2016\)](#).

1.3 CORPUS PREPARATION

Our corpus was assembled considering three parallel tracks, designed to cover the main aspects of a literary corpus:

- Topical aspect: works pertaining the same subject;
- Authorial aspect: works from the same author;
- Diatopical and diachronical aspects: works from different times and places.

Our aim for this initial set of experiments is to set a stable pipeline and a golden standard to expand upon in the future.

Our corpus is thus built containing 47 works in total, sub-divided as follows.

15 works from early Modern Neo-Latin drama, of which 8 pertain to the topic of “Joseph play” (to satisfy the first aspect), 3 same-author clusters (to satisfy the second aspect), and a range of 4 different nationalities and places of publication (to satisfy the third aspect): 3 authors from Germany, 1 from Poland, 1 from England and 7 from the Netherlands, thus keeping our particular focus on Dutch writing. The diachronic aspect is satisfied by the range of these works: the works were published between 1510 and 1639.

To track the first models of our Modern-era drama corpus and to serve as an additional counter-check proof for the clustering in Subsection 1.4.2, we added the 6 works from the Latin playwright Terentius, the 20 from Plautus (the known 21st is heavily fragmented and could not serve our purpose) and 6 certain dramas from Seneca, whose corpus authenticity is still highly debated⁵.

As our Neo-Latin drama texts come through a process of OCR from centuries old prints, they come with errors and imprecisions that can severely impact the processing of a text [van Strien et al. \(2020\)](#). Furthermore, we needed our texts to be devoid of any unnecessary information (e.g. verse number and character abbreviations), just presenting the bare tokenised script. We thus cleaned the texts in our corpus following a common pipeline of text manipulation for Latin texts:

- Cleaning OCR errors;
- Replacing punctuation;
- Changing everything to lower case;
- Normalizing Latin-related issues with spelling (such as V into U and J into I);

⁵We followed the selection in Wilson, 2010. For an overview on Seneca’s corpus authenticity, see Conte, 1994. These texts are gathered from the LASLA corpus <http://web.philo.ulg.ac.be/lasla/>

- Replacing para-textual annotation (e.g. characters speaking, line number, verse type).

A final layer of cleaning involved the process of manipulating the actual content of the texts:

- Stop words filtering, based on the Perseus Project list⁶ and then heavily modified and expanded;
- Non-semantic words filtering (conjunctions, subordinations, pronouns, auxiliaries, some very common adverbs);
- Lemmatisation. These two final steps were implemented in the Cosine Similarity part of our analysis (Subsection 1.4.2).

This whole process was done automatically using our custom-built program *CURRENS* that builds upon the tokeniser and enclitics exception list from the CLTK pipeline⁷, and the LemLat lemmatiser amended with in-house developed modules and expanded stopwords from the Perseus project⁸. *CURRENS* is available on Github.⁹

1.4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we present our experiment setup and analysis. The experimental setup sketches our general approach to analysing Neo-Latin texts. We then explain how we use Cosine Similarity 1.4.2 and Stylometry 1.4.3, by constructing a Bootstrap Consensus Tree, to compare different texts and what these different analysis methods bring.

1.4.1 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Our first analysis is inspired by [Karsdorp and van den Bosch \(2016\)](#), where we calculate the cosine similarity for every text in our corpus and produce a sparse correlation matrix, in order to express the closeness between texts and authors in terms of vector representation in an n-dimensional space model. This served as a basis to build a network representation that revealed a pattern of evolution shaped by the “PA-TA”(preference-based and temporal-based) attractiveness, basically a heavy-tailed, mostly chronological distribution of similarities that resemble real life evolutionary growth networks (and thus confirming the findings of [Karsdorp and van den Bosch \(2016\)](#)).

Our second analysis involves a stylometric approach [Eder \(2017b\)](#). We computed a Delta-distance Bootstrap Consensus Tree and produced the Principal Components Analysis (PCA) for our corpus of 47 works. Combining the results from these analyses, we drew another network that revealed a new and unexpected clustering, unveiling similarities unknown before. The computer was also able to correctly identify classical models and age- or generation-defined clusters, as found in previous literary inquiries, thus confirming the general structure and the evolution of Early-Modern Neo-Latin drama.

⁶<http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/stopwords>

⁷<http://cltk.org/>

⁸<http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/>

⁹<https://github.com/AndrewPeverells/CURRENS>

1.4.2 COSINE SIMILARITY

As a first step in our twofold experiment, we calculated the cosine similarity scores for each pair of texts in our corpus, which needed a final layer of manipulation: we thus lemmatised the texts, since calculating the cosine similarity between tokenised corpora, for a highly inflected language such as Latin, would bear too many false negatives (for example, the tokens “Deus” and “Deorum” would be held separated and would not contribute towards the final cosine similarity score, when they are clearly the concept pointing to the same word - “lemma” level - realised in two different ways - “token” level -); on the other hand, to prevent the inflation of the final score due to false positives, we eliminated most of the lemmas that do not possess a high semantically-informative content and that usually occur in the form of textual invariants (stopwords and function words, together with some very frequent Latin words, such as a few adverbs - *ut, iam, saepe...* - nouns - *res* - and verbs - mostly auxiliaries and derivatives: *habeo, sum, fio, possum...* -).¹⁰ As interjections are an important part of theatrical writing, these were kept.

Firstly, we transformed the lemmatised corpus into a Word Vector Space model (an n-dimensional space for representing documents and/or words as vectors, needed in order to compute the TF-IDF - *term frequency/inverse document frequency* - scores as the logarithmically scaled product of vectors); secondly, we turned it into a matrix of TF-IDF features; finally we computed the actual cosine similarity scores for our texts. We then generated the co-occurrence tables for every text, for a better in-depth explanation of the word likeness between works, divided into spreadsheets with a precise ratio: one for the general co-occurrences between the two sub-corpora (Neo-Latin Modern plays and Classical plays), and the other group for the highest cosine similarity scoring texts. Every spreadsheet is accompanied by a second sub-sheet bearing some general statistics for the particular pair analysed: type-token ratio (TTR), medium word length and lemma dispersion.

1.4.3 STYLOMETRY

For the second part of the experiment, we opted for a stylometric analysis through the R package *stylo* Eder et al. (2016). We went back a step in the corpus preparation procedure to maintain the stopwords/function words in the texts, as they are the vital part of every stylometric analysis, and we kept our corpus tokenised. We then produced a Bootstrap Consensus Tree, spanning through different parameter tests.

- As for the computed Distance, we decided to choose *Eder’s Delta* Evert et al. (2017), which is particularly suited for highly-inflected languages and not too long word vectors (the texts in our corpus very rarely exceed 15,000 tokens);
- As for the most frequent word (MFWs) analysed, we run through several trials, and found that the clustering begun to fall off at around 500 MFWs, gradually reuniting every work together in a single branch. We thus chose a comfortable plateau of 200 MFWs, that could properly show a meaningful branching of the clusters;
- As for other important parameters, we kept the Consensus of our tree at 0.5, left the pronouns out, and employed no culling of the MFWs.

¹⁰The importance of lemmatisation in cosine similarity score measuring for textual similarity is also confirmed by Manjavacas et al. (2019), as “lemmatization boosts the performance of nearly all models”

Figure 1.1: Cosine Similarity scores heat map.

1.5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Karsdorp and van den Bosch (2016) propose that the evolution of textual networks is to be based on two dimensions: *temporal attractiveness* (TA), the principle for which authors tend to prefer more recent models, and *model-based attractiveness* (MA), that involves elements from the context (such topic or the importance of an author). Our networks follow these two principles.

From our cosine similarity experiment (see 1.1), we can see that texts tend to follow a TA evolutionary fashion, exhibiting works that are closer in time as their highest-scoring models. Moreover, another key element incurs in the earlier stages of the network: a first cluster is clearly visible, composed of authors (Macropedius-Crocus-Gnapheus) of Dutch origin and active in the Netherlands. This shows the relative importance of the spatial aspect, which is closely related to the temporal one, thus transforming the TA into a T-SA (*temporal-spatial attractiveness*). However, this model of T-SA is especially true for the initial elements of the corpus, while the probability of works straying off their closest ones as models gets increasingly higher with the evolution of the network. This is due to the growing importance

Figure 1.2: Out-Degree Network of the Neo-Latin works.

of context (MA): as time passes, authors are given more choice for their inspiration.

Another crucial aspect is that of hubs, or, in our case, key turning points. We drew a graph from our cosine data (see 1.2), introducing a minimum threshold of 0.3 to filter out the weakest scores. The resulting (*out-degree*) network, displaying the outgoing edges, clearly shows that some texts serve as central hubs of reuse, or “models”: works from a first, earlier period (1510-1556) appear to be strong models for later authors, and a clear-cut clustering also stands out, with one very tight group (Crocus-Macropedius-Diether) and another cluster (Macropedius-Gnapheus-Foxe) that looks loosely connected to the first one. Moreover, each cluster has its key central hub that serves as a cornerstone: in the first one, Diether is well connected to both works from an earlier period and to later texts, while in the other one Foxe serves this purpose. In general, Crocus, Macropedius, Diether and Foxe were the highest scoring authors, both in cosine similarity and out-degree values, so we can (relatively safely) assume their importance and renown in the greater *respublica literaria*.

From the data gathered in our second part of the experiment, we can draw some new and complementary considerations. We drew a Bootstrap Consensus Tree with our full corpus (also comprising Plautus, Terence and Seneca) through a built-in algorithm from the R package *stylo* (1.3). Three main aspects stand out. Firstly, the authorial signature is very strong: all three groups of same-author works were correctly clustered together. This came in spite of the first aspect that we wanted to inquire: topic seems to be completely irrelevant to this kind of analysis, as Joseph plays are mixed with non-Joseph plays without any discerning ratio. Moreover, it is particularly interesting since this preeminence of the authorial aspect over topic was not really clear in the first part of the experiment: from cosine similarity scores, sometimes same-topic texts over-scored same-author clusters (as in the case of the Joseph by Schonaeus, which scored really low when compared to the Cunaee, another of his works), while sometimes works from the same author had a higher score than same-topic works from other authors (as in the case of the Joseph and the Hecastus, both from Macropedius). Secondly, the T-SA dimension is maintained, but with new and interesting additions: the algorithm automatically drew two very distinct clusters, separating the XVI century works from the XVII century ones (although Bidermann seems to be an exception). This goes in pair with a third consideration, regarding classical authors: Plautus was put aside from everything else, while Terence seem to have a higher influence on the

Figure 1.3: Bootstrap Consensus Tree of 49 Latin and Neo-Latin Dramas using 2-202 Most Frequent Words, Eder's Delta distance, Consensus 0.5.

XVI century cluster and Seneca on the XVII century one. This clear-cut subdivision is confirmed by literary studies on the matter. [Bloemendal and Norland \(2013\)](#) identifies a three-staged evolution of Dutch Neo-Latin drama: a first one (roughly 1500-1550) that serves as a proving ground for new authors that revealed to be very influential in later periods; a second one (1550-1600), characterised by the use of Terence as the primary model; and, finally, a third one, more akin to Baroque literature, that shifted heavily towards a more Senecan style.

There are still two notable exceptions to our Consensus Tree: Bidermann (1615) seems to fit better in the XVI century cluster, and the *Adelphoe* resulted as the most separated terentian work in all of our tests, more akin to authors in the XVII century cluster. The first anomaly is maybe due to Bidermann's Jesuit background: within the XVII century cluster, one (Libenus) out of three authors pertain to the Jesuit Order, which is much more concentrated in the XVI century cluster. The second anomaly, the *Adelphoe* by Terence, still needs more investigation.

1.6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper describes an exploration towards building a functioning pipeline for assessing textual similarities in Neo-Latin texts. Through this experiment we wanted to test textual similarity and reuse through the three main aspects of literary works: the authorial aspect (works from the same authors, thus tracking internal reuse); the topical aspect (works

pertaining the same topic, thus tracking similarities throughout a same-topic sub-corpus); and the diatopic-diachronic aspect (thus tracking the reuse of other authors' texts through time and space and the individuation of "models"). We hence built our test corpus in such a way that it covered every one of the three aspects we wanted to inquire, also inserting the works of classical drama authors (Plautus, Terence and Seneca) as a counter-check for the second part of our experiment.

Although our focus is on drama pieces and on Neo-Latin, this pipeline can be applied to any kind of Latin text, as its parameters are the same. This is thanks, especially, to our tool, CURRENS, which can be used to pre-process a Latin work in a customised fashion, depending on which module is needed in one's analysis. We employed it in its entirety to generate clean, tokenised texts to work upon, and tweaked its modules in order to get a two-fold type of data from our initial corpus: one raw, tokenised, as presented in the original texts (the full 49, comprising classical authors); and one lemmatised and deprived of stop words and function words (just the 15 Neo-Latin texts of the XVI-XVII centuries period that we gathered as an initial exploration). The latter was used in the first part of our experiment, involving cosine similarity, for which we employed a TF-IDF vector space model to calculate its score for every text in our corpus. From these results, we built a network showing the out-degree values for the processed texts, and a heat map showing the correlation distribution between the 15 samples. From this, two noteworthy results stand out:

- The evolution of similarity patterns in our corpus tends to follow a S-TA/MA model (spatial-temporal attractiveness / modal attractiveness): in the early (chronological) stages of the network, authors tend to prefer texts closer in time and space as their models of reuse (S-TA); conversely, as time passes by, the dispersion of this preferential attachment increases dramatically, with authors preferring other texts based on more aleatory reasons such as topic, style or vicinity (MA).
- The emergence of text clusters is modeled around central hubs (our "models"), represented by particularly fortunate authors: our corpus, in particular, split into two clear-cut clusters, with Andreas Diether in one and John Foxe in the other serving as central hubs of reuse, well connected with both authors from the early age and authors from later stages, around which the other texts seem to gravitate. This shows the relative importance of these authors and the end of the early period of our network (1544-1556) as a testing ground for later literary imitation.

The other type of processed data (raw, tokenised text) that resulted through the use of CURRENS was instead used for the second part of our experiment. We generated a BCT (Bootstrap Consensus Tree) of the whole 49 works that make up our corpus, combining together the Neo-Latin works and the texts from classical authors as a counter-check for the clustering method that we employed (Eder's Delta, 0.5 consensus strength, 200 MFWs). From this, we could draw further considerations:

- The authorial signal is stronger than the topical aspect. Internal style within same-author clusters takes over features of same-topic style. The cosine similarity experiment gave mixed results in this regard.
- S-TA is maintained, but with new clusters that define an age-dependent evolution of style: the algorithm automatically recognised two very distinct groups, one in the

XVI century and one in the XVII century, with classical authors arranged as clear models (Terence for the first group and Seneca for the second; Plautus was set apart as too distant). This is confirmed by literary critique studies, that report a similar generation-like evolution of Neo-Latin drama and model selection.

- Two main exceptions stand out: the alien presence of the *Adelphoe* by Terence in the XVII century group and that of Bidermann (1615) in the XVI century cluster. These need more evidence.

We thus answered to the original questions: we demonstrated that the process of imitation and reception within Neo-Latin drama is extensive, and it happened on many layers (spatiality, temporality, modality); we tracked connections between authors and checked the reuse of models, both contemporary and ancient: finally, we demonstrated the existence of hubs of reuse, thus gaining more insight on the importance of some authors in the Early Modern Era and the reflection of classical drama writers on this very age.

As a further step to improve our model of textual similarity for Neo-Latin texts, we plan to improve on the basis we have set, as well as employ new methodologies for our next experiment. First of all, an expansion of our corpus, with new Neo-Latin texts from the XVI-XVII centuries, will be a constant background operation, as the TransLatin Project moves forward and enables more texts to be digitised and analysed. Secondly, a word embeddings analysis for our corpus will be conducted, to improve upon the foundations of the cosine similarity experiment that we already conducted. Finally, for a more different approach, we would like to implement a topic modelling analysis to better inquire the topical aspect of our pipeline and have a deeper understanding of how textual reuse works in conjunction with topic variation.

2

THE PROCESS OF *imitatio* THROUGH STYLOMETRIC ANALYSIS

The Early Modern Era is at the forefront of a widespread enthusiasm for Latin works: texts from classical antiquity are given new life, widely re-printed, studied and even repeatedly staged, in the case of dramas, throughout Europe. Also, new Latin comedies are again written in quantities never seen before (at least 10,000 works published 1500 to 1800 are known). The authors themselves, within the game of literary imitation (the process of imitatio), start to mimic the style of ancient authors, and Terence's dramas in particular were considered the prime sources of reuse for many decades. Via a case study "the reception of Terence's Eunuchus in Early Modern literature", we take a deep dive into the mechanisms of literary imitation. Our analysis is based on four comedy corpora in Latin, Italian, French and English, spanning roughly 3 centuries (1400-1700). To assess the problem of language shift and multi-language inter-corpora analysis, we base our experiments on translations of the Eunuchus, one for each sub-corpus. Through the use of tools drawn from the field of Stylometry, we address the topic of text reuse and textual similarities between Terence's text and Early-Modern corpora to get a better grasp on the internal fluctuations of the imitation game between Early Modern and Classical authors.

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The division of work in this chapter is as follows: main experiment design and execution by Andrea Peverelli, contributions to the original idea and its development and proof-reading by Marieke van Erp, Jan Bloemendal and Dirk van Miert.

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades, Stylometry has been used to track authorial signals and stylistic similarities between authors with great effectiveness (Eder (2017a) and Eder and Rybicki (2012)). Stylometric tools can be a useful means to help clarify issues of style, relationship and network construction, and it has become a paramount methodology in the field of Computational Literary Studies and Stylistics. While eminently a distant reading environment, it can account for general and specific features of correlation and possible connection between sets of corpora, often with high precision results (cf. Lagutina et al. (2019); Zangerle et al. (2021)). Literary scholars can therefore be presented with new perspectives and definitive evidence; as stated by O'Sullivan et al. (2018) on the usefulness of Stylometry in literary studies: "literary interpretations can be focused, with computational precision, on the relevant passages. In using such methods, [...] [Stylometry] uses computer-assisted criticism to shed new light on a pre-existing concern". Our paper gives an account of the precise spots where the two drama corpora (Terence and Early Modern comedies) overlap and where Terence's features are most prominent in relation to each textual turning point. The primary scope of our paper is thus to demonstrate the interference of Terence's most renowned piece, the *Eunuchus*, in Early Modern drama writing, by analysing the fluctuations in preference and similarity that different authors might display. Our aim is to account for this deep and complex imitation game between Early Modern and classical authors from a distant reading point of view. Through the use of stylometric methodologies applied to a case study, we set the base ground for a wider inquiry into the intricate phenomena behind the choice of classical models and how these operate in the background of modern writing. Our main contribution is a methodology: gathering of a suitable corpus, analysing the texts and building a stable network of interconnected plays. This new set of correlated analyses on similarity and dissimilarity between corpora can in turn be then replicated on wider cases.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2.2 gives a brief overview of the related research. Section 2.3 presents the data and the process of structuring our corpus. Section 2.4 sketches our experimental setup. Section 2.5 gives a detailed analysis of the results and a discussion on a literary history level. Section 2.6 concludes the paper with an overview on future work.

2.2 RELATED WORK

Our processing line builds on very stable and already frequented ground. Stylometric tools of different origin and applications have been gaining popularity since the work of Burrows, Holmes, and Craig in the early '90s Burrows (1987); Craig (1999); Holmes (1998). For a comprehensive overview of the set of tools offered by Stylometry, the main references are Lagutina et al. (2019) and Eder et al. (2016) (which offer a complete rundown of the usage of the main R library for stylometry, *stylo*). A number of stylometric studies has been devoted to tasks such as authorship attribution and detection (cf. Burrows (2010); Hoover (2001, 2012); Jockers et al. (2008); Rybicki et al. (2014); van Dalen-Oskam and van Zundert (2007)); which is different from our goal, but can serve as a layout for a more general analysis on style and similarities between authors, and, when needed, we point out the differences in approach and scope throughout our paper. More akin to our topic is that of style variation analysis and stylistic similarities (cf. Zangerle et al. (2021) for an overview): Choiński et al.

(2019); O’Sullivan et al. (2018); Schöberlein (2016) apply stylometric analysis tools to the study of contemporary (19th-20th century) authors’ style, while Eder (2017a); Gorman and Gorman (2016) and Chapter 1 of this dissertation take different perspective on text reuse for ancient historical languages, also implementing network analysis through Stylometry. The core statistics and algorithms we use in this paper are Burrows’ Delta and Sequential Stylometric Analysis (SSA), being already known for their efficiency in the field of stylistic analysis. For an in-depth overview of Burrows’ Delta and, in general, Delta analysis for textual similarity tasks, see Argamon (2007); Burrows (2002); Hoover (2004), while for a more hands-on application of Burrows’ Delta in a literary case study we suggest Lauer and Jannidis (2014). As for Sequential Stylometric Analysis (SSA), Eder (2016) is paramount, while for a more in-depth explanation of the usage of the NSC (Nearest Shrunken Centroids) algorithm in SSA, see Jockers et al. (2008); Roper et al. (2012); Schaalje et al. (2011); Schöberlein (2016).

2.3 DATA AND CORPUS CONSTRUCTION

We collected a corpus of 85 comedy pieces from the DraCor Project¹ database (English, French, and Italian) and the Translatin repository (Latin).² The original classical Latin text of the *Eunuchus* is taken from the LASLA corpus.³

The corpus statistics are shown in Table 2.1

Language	# of Texts	# Tokens	Time span
Latin	15	160,741	1510-1639
French	34	456,493	1634-1668
Italian	21	409,000	1496-1761
English	15	250,646	1592-1611
Total	85	1,276,879	1496-1761

Table 2.1: Corpus statistics for the different language corpora in terms of number of texts, period covered and number of tokens.

As is visible from the time spans, the covered period varies, but it fits the general boundaries of the Modern Era (roughly: early 15th - late 18th centuries). A practical reason for this diversified selection is due to the selection offered by DraCor and in literary history: the two most famous Italian comedy writers of the Modern Era, Ariosto and Goldoni, are set apart by 2 centuries, while the vast majority of the most important drama writers of France’s Modern Era (Molière, Racine, Corneille) are found in the middle of the 17th century. For English, DraCor only possessed the complete Shakespeare corpus, from which we selected 15 comedies. Finally, we added a random selection of Neo-Latin works from a wide variety of authors, nationalities and years of production, drawn from our project

¹<https://dracor.org/> Last visited: 29 August 2022

²<https://www.translatin.nl>

³https://www.lasla.uliege.be/cms/c_8508894/fr/lasla Last visited: 29 August 2022

repository, automatically cleaned and manually checked from a previous OCR process.⁴

For this whole experiment, we wanted the translations to be in the background and cause as little noise as possible to keep the focus on the original work by Terence. The translations were thus gathered according to the following criteria:

1. As close as possible (time-wise) to the period span of its related sub-corpus;
2. Freely available and downloadable;
3. A philological translation, as close as possible (style-wise) to the original from Terence.

The first and third criteria helped make up for the linguistic and stylistic divide. If contemporary translations had been taken into consideration, the experiment would have been invalidated from the start, the language of those translations being too distant from their relative Modern Era counterparts. The third point poses another subtle but important aspect: the translation must be "philological", thus as close as possible to the unadulterated original. This rules out, for example, an "artistic" translation of Terence's works by Nicolò Machiavelli, supposedly of very little rigorousness as far as adherence to the original was concerned.⁵ Spelling variants were unified with a layer of pre-processing from the CLTK/NLTK pipeline.⁶

The translations meeting all criteria at the time of our experiment are:

- FRENCH - H. Clouard, 1937
- ITALIAN - L. Perelli, 1869
- ENGLISH - G. Colman, 1768

The Italian and French translations, while rather late, are still sufficiently suitable, as French altered very little from the end of the 17th century, while Perelli's translation of 1869 still falls roughly under the same pre-unified contemporary Italian.

2.4 EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we give an overview of our experiments. We start with a preliminary exploration of our dataset using a clustering algorithm to identify general groupings within our corpus. Then we analyse our texts in their sequential development, with the aim of identifying overlaps and distances between our modern drama sub-corpus and their relative translations of the *Eunuchus*, to accurately identify modern authorial fingerprints and takeovers against Terence's piece, throughout the succession of acts and scenes of the original.

⁴The whole corpus, together with the parameter specifications for the Stylo code, can be found in our GitHub repository: <https://github.com/AndrewPeverells/The-Imitation-Game>

⁵Cf. the article on Terence from the Italian *Enciclopedia Machiavelliana*

⁶NLTK, and CLTK Last visited: 22 August 2022

Figure 2.1: Cluster analysis of the English sub-corpus, Classic Delta distance, 300 Most Frequent Words. Plays are clustered together in branches based on their similarity, with ancestors reuniting them at the root. The score on the x-axis at the bottom indicates the level of Delta (distance) between branches, the lower this score (and the shorter the distance between the texts) the more similar the plays are between themselves.

2.4.1 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

As a pre-processing step, we divided our corpus into two distinct sets: the primary set (test set), composed of the 81 modern texts, subdivided into four language corpora; and the secondary set (training or reference set), composed of the four versions of the *Eunuchus*, again subdivided per language. The training or reference set is the relevant *Eunuchus* translation, or the "known" text, against which our test is to be conducted to identify authorial signals and similarities. For the first experiment, the clustering analysis, this subdivision is irrelevant, since we need to distribute all the texts together into different clusters, and we need the *Eunuchus* to be evident in our clusters. The general parameters that were kept for both sets of experiments are the following, based on our previous experiment [Peverelli et al. \(2022b\)](#):

- To overcome issues related with an arbitrary selection of MFWs (Most Frequent Words), we ran several trials on every setting from 100 to 1500 MFWs.⁷ We found 300 MFWs to be the most suitable for our experiment, as the texts are not too long (they rarely exceed 15,000 words) and we noticed that, over this number, the clustering began to gradually merge every branch together. This was already observed in our recent experiment [Peverelli et al. \(2022b\)](#) and is confirmed by [Hoover \(2004\)](#). This somewhat low parameter of 300 MFWs makes the set of words on which our analysis is conducted almost entirely comprised of function words and a handful of high-frequency semantically meaningful words, mainly related to the dramatic language

⁷A practice already well-established in the field of Stylometry: [Eder and Rybicki \(2012\)](#)

Figure 2.2: Cluster analysis of the Latin sub-corpus, Classic Delta distance, 300 Most Frequent Words. Plays are clustered together in branches based on their similarity, with ancestors reuniting them at the root. The score on the x-axis at the bottom indicates the level of Delta (distance) between branches, the lower this score (and the shorter the distance between the texts) the more similar the plays are between themselves.

(e.g. for English "lord, father, lady, pray, brother, true", or for Latin "quaeso, mehercle, dico, amor, senex");

- Contractions were not removed;
- No filtering of the function words was introduced, thus keeping the texts as they appear originally. Interjections and personal pronouns especially were not removed on purpose, as they are a vital part of the dramatic language;
- Maximum culling was set to 20%, meaning that a word needs to appear in at least 20% of the text, to eliminate some background noise.

2.4.2 CLUSTERING

The first experiment set is a cluster analysis produced via a Delta algorithm. The selected delta measure is Burrows' [Burrows \(2002\)](#), which is widely used for stylistic analysis as a reliable similarity measure between two candidates (cf. [Porgeirsson \(2018\)](#)). Burrows' Delta is also confirmed to be better suited for shorter-vector corpora ([Jannidis et al. \(2015\)](#) and Chapter 1 of this dissertation). Although Cosine measures are confirmed to outscore others, it is repeatedly stated that it depends on many factors, such as corpus selection, choice of MFWs, type of language and length of vectors [Evert et al. \(2015\)](#); [Hettinger et al. \(2015\)](#). As we are looking for evidence that Cosine measures outscore other traditional measures even in shorter-vector literary texts (10,000-15,000 words) with a lower selection of MFWs for tasks other than authorship attribution, we decided to use Burrows' Classic Delta. Burrows' Delta

Figure 2.3: Cluster analysis of the French sub-corpus, Classic Delta distance, 300 Most Frequent Words. Plays are clustered together in branches based on their similarity, with ancestors reuniting them at the root. The score on the x-axis at the bottom indicates the level of Delta (distance) between branches, the lower this score (and the shorter the distance between the texts) the more similar the plays are between themselves.

is calculated as the geometric distance between "two standard-deviation-normalised mean word frequencies" Argamon (2007). In summary, "Delta may be viewed as an axis-weighted form of ‘nearest neighbor’ classification, where a test document is classified the same as the known document at the smallest ‘distance’" Argamon (2007).

A simplified formula of Burrows’s Delta, which enriches Burrows’s original by taking into account standard deviations between word frequencies, is given in Equation 2.1:

$$\Delta_B^{(n)}(D, D') = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i} |f_i(D) - f_i(D')| \tag{2.1}$$

Where n is the set of MFWs, the subscript B indicates the relation to Burrows’s original Delta, $|f_i(D) - f_i(D')|$ the computed normalised difference between the frequency of a word f_i in a text D , and σ_i its standard deviation.

Using the 300 MFWs max-culling 20% parameters we introduced in Subsection 2.4.1, we calculated and produced clusters for each sub-corpus as shown in Figures 2.1-2.4.

We then produced a slightly modified version of this delta analysis by implementing the Rolling Delta procedure initially proposed by van Dalen-Oskam and van Zundert (2007) and implemented in the R Stylo package.⁸ This methodology, instead of inspecting the whole corpus as one batch and calculating the Delta distance from the sum frequency of two texts, subdivides every text into equal-sized windows, following the evolution (in words) of the

⁸<https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/stylo/versions/0.7.4/topics/rolling.delta>

Figure 2.4: Cluster analysis of the Italian sub-corpus, Classic Delta distance, 300 Most Frequent Words. Plays are clustered together in branches based on their similarity, with ancestors reuniting them at the root. The score on the x-axis at the bottom indicates the level of Delta (distance) between branches, the lower this score (and the shorter the distance between the texts) the more similar the plays are between themselves.

reference set text, and then compares each of these windows for every text in the corpus. This is particularly useful to track stylistic shifts along the evolution of a text's length.

First, each text is divided into samples, or "windows". Then the centroid (C) is computed for the mean relative frequency of the n most frequent words of each window. The centroid C then consists of a one-dimensional vector composed of 3 elements: the mean frequencies (μ_i) computed against the relative frequencies (w_i) of the window samples, and enriched with the standard deviation for each of the n 's (most frequent words) relative frequencies for each window sample. Finally, the standard Delta is computed for each window (W) and its relative reference C (centroid), calculated as above as shown by Equation 2.2.

$$\Delta(C, W) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i(C)} |\mu_i(C) - f_i(W)| \quad (2.2)$$

After having "rolled" through each window, the result is the plotted Delta in an x,y axes space, where the x-axis corresponds to the evolution (in words) of the texts, and their relative window samples, against the reference set (the *Eunuchus*) and the y-axis to the Delta distance. Thus, the closer to the x-axis, the higher the similarity; the further away from the x-axis (= higher Delta), the lower the similarity. This methodology was originally developed for authorship attribution and detection Burrows (2010); Hoover (2012, 2013); van Dalen-Oskam and van Zundert (2007), but the underlying tenets can be assimilated in our case. Normally, "if the curve for a text shows a sudden drop, this may indicate a stylistic change in the test text, caused, for instance, by one author taking over from another" Rybicki et al. (2014): in our case, it indicates takeovers in an author's style, therefore *loci* where an

author is closer to Terence and actually re-using parts of his style (or the contrary, in case of high spikes on the y-axis).

Figure 2.5: Rolling Delta Analysis of the Latin sub-corpus. Different visualisation of Figure 2: the Delta here is plotted in an x,y axes space where the x-axis corresponds to the evolution (in words) of the texts, and their relative window samples, against the reference set, and the y-axis to the Delta distance.

2.4.3 SSA - SEQUENTIAL STYLOMETRIC ANALYSIS

The second experiment focuses on the use of Sequential Stylometric Analysis [Eder \(2016\)](#), which takes the previous method of calculating distances between texts in regards to their evolution in words (hence "sequential"), and combines it with the application of a machine-learning algorithm, such as *k*-Nearest Neighbor, Support Vector Machine, Naive Bayes, and Nearest Shrunken Centroid (NSC).

We chose the NSC algorithm as it is already widely and successfully used in the field of Stylometry [Jockers et al. \(2008\)](#); [Roper et al. \(2012\)](#); [Schaalje et al. \(2011\)](#); [Schöberlein \(2016\)](#). As this classification methodology is also primarily used for authorship attribution and detection tasks, we here start from Burrows' assumption of a 'closed game' [Burrows \(2002\)](#), i.e. the situation in which we know for certain that the author (or one of the authors) in the test set is the certain and true one amongst the candidates to be evaluated in an authorship detection task: our environment then shifts from an identification environment of one sample among others, to the next level of analysing an author's stylistic imprint on the other candidates.

The NSC algorithm is a form of feature selection and evaluation: it performs the evaluation of a sample, extracting classes of features and shifting them towards the more central ones (centroids, interpreted as the geometric centre of a data distribution set and calculated as the mean average value of each feature) and removing the more distant ones as noise (shrinking) until only a few classes of features have an actual impact on the classification. The algorithm calculates the centroid for each class group in the dataset,

thus assigning a model label to each class group based on its relative centroid; after the shrinkage, the remaining centroids are the ones composing the general model on which the Delta distance is calculated. For an in-depth mathematical analysis of the NSC classifier applied to stylometry, see [Schaalje et al. \(2011\)](#).

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The NSC algorithm, built in the R package *Stylo* [Eder et al. \(2016\)](#) for the "Rolling" function, produced 4 different visualisations of our analysis, in which the bottom (bold) horizontal line indicates the first set of most probable candidates (i.e. the highest scoring "closest" authors to the *Eunuchus*), while the second (lighter) one corresponds to the second set of most probable overlapping authors, based on the different class calculations from the algorithm. The thickness of the line also contributes visually to the analysis: a thicker line indicates more overlapping sets of features (thus closer stylistic similarity), and a thinner line marks a decreasing degree of similarity.

Figure 2.6: Sequential Stylometric Analysis ("Rolling Stylometry" methodology) of the English sub-corpus. Here each text from the test set is chunked into windows and analysed sequentially against the reference set (the *Eunuchus*). The x-axis corresponds to the evolution of the latter, the y-axis accounts for the usual Delta distance (expressed in the thickness of the horizontal line), while the different colours correspond to the different texts that are given as the most probable candidates for similarities.

Figure 2.7: Sequential Stylometric Analysis of the French sub-corpus. Here each text from the test set is chunked into windows and analysed sequentially against the reference set (the *Eunuchus*). The x-axis corresponds to the evolution of the latter, the y-axis accounts for the usual Delta distance (expressed in the thickness of the horizontal line), while the different colours correspond to the different texts that are given as the most probable candidates for similarities.

Figure 2.8: Sequential Stylometric Analysis of the Italian sub-corpus. Here each text from the test set is chunked into windows and analysed sequentially against the reference set (the *Eunuchus*). The x-axis corresponds to the evolution of the latter, the y-axis accounts for the usual Delta distance (expressed in the thickness of the horizontal line), while the different colours correspond to the different texts that are given as the most probable candidates for similarities.

Figure 2.9: Sequential Stylometric Analysis of the Latin sub-corpus. Here each text from the test set is chunked into windows and analysed sequentially against the reference set (the *Eunuchus*). The x-axis corresponds to the evolution of the latter, the y-axis accounts for the usual Delta distance (expressed in the thickness of the horizontal line), while the different colours correspond to the different texts that are given as the most probable candidates for similarities.

2.5 IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS

In this section, we present and discuss the results from our experiments and combine them together to have a general framework of the authors' preferences towards a model, thus gaining more insights on the general process of *imitatio*. First we discuss each sub-language corpus separately, followed by a summary of the general tendencies that stand out from our analysis.

2.5.1 ITALIAN

From the clustering part of the experiment (2.4) we note a clear closeness between earlier works (16th century) and the *Eunuchus*, despite its translation being closer to Goldoni. This similarity is especially evident for the works of Machiavelli (*Mandragola* and *Clizia*) and Ariosto: they were both notorious connoisseurs of Terence, the former even producing one of the first Italian translations of some of its works, while the latter was responsible for numerous re-enactments of Terence's comedies (especially the *Eunuchus*), both in Latin and Italian, when he was in Ferrara at the Este court.⁹ We can therefore assume that Terence's style was deeply rooted in their own, while the *Eunuchus* had little to no influence in the later stages of Italian comedy production. The clear-cut distance between two texts closely related to Terence and the Este court, that was at the forefront of the revitalisation of Latin drama (especially Terence) at the end of the 15th century.¹⁰ Both *Comedia di Timon Greco* by Galeotto del Carretto (who dedicated his work to Beatrice d'Este) and the *Comedia di Danae* by Baldassarre Taccone (who was patronised by the Este in Mantova), while very close, are kept strictly separated from Terence. Therefore, the style of the *Eunuchus* does not seem to have had a particular influence on their works, where one would expect so.

From the SSA experiment (Figure 2.8), the closest relative to the *Eunuchus* appears to be *I Suppositi*, in the largest part, being closest to Terence's play at the start and at the end. Both works are a switching doubles comedy, and in both many of the characters go undercover. We interpret this in the lights of the fact that the start and ending of a switching doubles comedy are especially important in the setting-up of the disguise and the final resolution of the misunderstanding at the very heart of the comedy, while the actual central plot of scheming and deception is left to the invention of the author (being the central part, up until the very end of the piece, the most interpolated section). The turning point between the end of act IV and the start of act V, right before the final resolution, is instead taken by Ariosto's *Cassaria*, a plautine-inspired comedy.

2.5.2 LATIN

The clustering algorithm automatically drew two very distinct clusters (see Figure 2.2), separating the 16th century works from the 17th century ones, and the *Eunuchus* is the clear dominant model in the first 16th century cluster. This is confirmed by literary scholars in for example Peverelli et al. (2022b) and Bloemendal and Norland (2013).

One exception is in the 1615 text by Jacob Bidermann. A possible explanation is that Bidermann is the only Jesuit in our 17th century cluster: our previous paper (Peverelli et al. (2022b)) confirmed the general tendency of 16th century catholic authors, such as

⁹For an overview on Ariosto's life and production and the literary role of the Este court in Italian late Renaissance, see Hainsworth and Robey (2002)

¹⁰For a more in-depth analysis on the matter Torello-Hill (2015)

Macropedius, Crocus, Diether, Simonides and Schonaeus, to heavily favour Terence as a literary model (before switching to Seneca).

From the sequential analysis (Figure 2.9), the closest overlapping relatives to the *Eunuchus* are Crocus and Macropedius, which take more than half of the work's body. This is an already well-established parallel, in line with the start of the 16th century's widespread passion for Terentian drama. As a general note, the Latin sub-corpus appears to be the one with the heaviest and most varied influences from the *Eunuchus*, with the least branching in the clustering and the most numerous switches in author similarity in the SSA analysis. This confirms the heavy usage of textual instances from Neo-Latin authors towards their models, rather than an underlying echo of influence: Neo-Latin authors read, copied, transcribed, imitated, staged, and taught ancient authors on a daily basis [Bloemendal and Norland \(2013\)](#).

2.5.3 FRENCH

From the cluster analysis (Figure 2.3) we can observe the almost complete preponderance of Molière, the very minor presence of Corneille and complete absence of Racine, Fontaine and other minor authors. Furthermore, the complete distance of Fontaine's *Eunuque* from the original model on which it is based stands out. Even though Fontaine's work is based upon Terence's, his style is apparently very different (a consideration perfectly in line with the chosen methodology, stylometry, which is in most cases considered independent of content and semantics).

From the sequential analysis (Figure 2.7), the absolute winners of this *imitation game* with Terence are *Les Fourberies de Scapin* by Molière and *Les Fausses Vérités* by Antoine d'Ouville. Both are comedies of love intrigue and infatuation of a man for a young girl that are stylistically influenced by the prior Italian comedy, which is in turn heavily Terentian. As for Ariosto, one particular work (*Les Fausses Vérités*) takes the parts of *I Suppositi*, gathering heavy influences from the very start and end of the *Eunuchus*; for the remaining part of the play, *Les Fausses Vérités* and *Les Fourberies de Scapin* battle themselves for predominance, continuously switching primacy for the influence within the *Eunuchus*. Again, the most interpolated part seems to be the second half of Terence's work, with act IV displaying the heaviest influences.

2.5.4 ENGLISH

The English sub-corpus presents a different situation, because all the results are negative. From the clustering experiment (Figure 2.1) we note a clear-cut distance between the *Eunuchus* and the Shakespearean comedy corpus. This poses the following questions: could this distance be due to the translation not being contemporary to Shakespeare? although it is the oldest and the closest to the test corpus out of all the languages inquired? This also poses a question about style and language that deserves further investigation: is it the diachronical variation of language or is it Shakespeare's style that sets them apart? Is this issue due to the language of Colman's translation or is it entirely to be attributed to Shakespeare's notoriously idiosyncratic and peculiar style, so that even a contemporary translation would not be sufficient to track similarities between his corpus and Terence's works? This renders necessary a digitisation of Webbe's translation (1638), which is, to our knowledge, the

closest to Shakespeare's times done by a "professional"¹¹ and, at the time of our experiment, not freely available.

Finally, From the sequential analysis (Figure 2.6), the closest candidate is *The Comedy of Errors*, but it is a result that cannot be trusted: the overlapping line is almost negligibly thin, thus the score of Delta distance is comparably quite high.

2.5.5 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

From our experiments, and by looking at the results shown by the Rolling Delta visualisation on the primary sub-case study of Neo-Latin (Figure 2.5), we can draw some conclusions about the influence of Terence's *Eunuchus* on the Modern Era drama production, that give us some insights on the underlying process of imitation towards ancient authors.

- Act IV seems to be the most interpolated and reused, as shown from the high coincidence of overlaps in the SSA. This indicates a preference, by modern authors, for taking inspiration from a specific *topos* in classical theatre writing, as the fourth act always corresponds to an escalation in the web of intrigues and a turning point in the general plot before the final settlement: we can then assume that a particularly animated style of narration is at work and modern authors tend to be close to it;
- Act I and V, the opening and closing of the comedy, are always taken by a specific work, from the modern perspective. Act I and V are inextricably tied to the specific play's plot and are usually made up almost exclusively of fast-paced spoken dialogues (monologues and reported speech, typically from serfs, taking up the middle of the play): the new characters are presented (Act I) and their misadventures are resolved in a turning of events (Act V), so it makes sense that only works with a similar story could tie to their specific style, mimicking in particular the new characters' exchange of gags and blows.

From the Rolling Delta analysis, applied to the sub-case study of Neo-Latin against the original *Eunuchus*, we can note some clear patterns:

- The imitation game follows a rough ups-and-downs style, with two clear areas of low and high delta, respectively: the end of act II, act III scene 5, the end of act IV, and the ending of the play;
- The first low delta (= high similarity and overlap with the original) corresponds to the end of the initial story set-up and character presentation, where usually the characters starts to get into the thick of the machinations, confirming again that the usefulness of the original play stops when the plot overcomes the possible usage of styloms (that is, when modern plays' stories become too distant from the *Eunuchus* to justify the re-use of style);

¹¹In our experiment, at first, we used William Heming's 1602 translation, but the results were even worse: the delta distance between Heming and Shakespeare's comedies more than tripled relative to our current test Colman. This is probably due to Heming's very loose translation: he was a playwright and a poet, not a translation expert, grammarian and language teacher as Webbe was.

- The first high delta (= low similarity) perfectly overlaps with the most famous of Terence's scenes: the rape scene of act III scene 5. Although in reported speech, this scene goes into details of the rape, and it is surprising that the Neo-Latin authors do not make use of the seduction and emotional violence styloms of Terence's scene;
- The second low delta corresponds to the end of act IV, and it ties in to the aforementioned turning point in the comedy's structure;
- The second, and last, high variation section coincides with the near-end of the play, but it shows a very interesting pattern: on the one hand, plays that originally turned out to be very close to the *Eunuchus* from the other parts of our experiment, at that point plunge even further down, reaching a new low delta and confirming their similarity in the important ending section of the play; on the other hand, works that originally turned out to be distant, sport an opposite fashion, going ever upward in their delta distance and reaching the second highest point of dissimilarity.

2.6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we described a case study for the application of computational methods on the issue of assessing the process of *imitatio* between authors from the Early Modern Period and classical models. We started by gathering a corpus, consisting of one of Terence's works as a case study, the *Eunuchus*, its translations in another three languages (English, Italian and French), and four sub-corpora of drama from the Early Modern Period, in the four respective languages, that served as the proper test set. We then explained the methodology we employed for our experiment and the two different and complementary analysis it enabled us to perform: Cluster Analysis through Delta measures, and Sequential Stylometric Analysis. We then proceeded to the in-depth analysis of the results for each of the 4 languages, evaluating the peculiarities of each sub-corpus and the broader patterns that stood out. Finally, we drew some general conclusions on the process of modern authors' imitation of classics within theatrical writing.

By this, we achieved our initial, more general, aim of describing the methodology for multi-language literary studies that can be used for other case studies beyond Terence (for example: 20th century authors reusing Renaissance authors). Furthermore, provided the correct parameters (such as the act-scene subdivision for drama or the verse-stanza structure for poetry), our methodology can be used not only for inquiring drama, but any other genre. The combinations coming out of the possibilities given by such methodology are copious, as many other studies showed in the past (Section 2.2).

However, the chosen methodology has limitations. Stylometry only tackles issues of style in a purely "formal" way, that is by only taking most frequent words,¹² it is by no means a methodology for semantic analysis, and it only provides tools for a distant reading environment. Furthermore, it showed its internal limitations in the analysis of the English sub-corpus (Subsection 2.5.4), when it yielded poor results both in the Cluster Analysis and the SSA. Conversely, Stylometry can often catch hidden patterns especially thanks to its core features (distant reading environment and function words analysis): Stylometry has proven

¹²MFWs are often going to be function words in a traditional literary work, but for other cases this depends on the type of input text. There is also no consensus on the exact definition of function words.

successful and useful when analysing literary corpora with the aim of building networks of common and dissimilar features, often handling quite large sets of these features at the same time. To us therefore, Stylometry is not to be taken on its own, but to be combined with other methodologies that can complement its structural flaws, and in turn be enriched by Stylometry's unique take.

It is with these caveats in mind that we plan to expand our methodology with implementations from other methods, primarily semantic analysis. Internally, one critical step to cement our findings would be to access to proper contemporary (to the Modern Era) translations of the *Eunuchus*, to get rid of every possible imprecision due to the distance between the author's language and the translation's very own, while one entire sub-project could devoted to comparing different translations and how they perform. Furthermore, we deem a mandatory step to expand our reference corpus of classical drama writers to the point of including every Latin play and replicating our methodology on each one of them. Finally, enriching our corpus with new data from the copious drama production of the Modern Era would be a natural next step. This would bring our the ultimate goal of accounting for the complex issue of *imitatio* within Modern Era drama writing closer.

3

TRACING THEMES AND TOPICS THROUGH TOPIC MODELLING AND WORD EMBEDDINGS

This paper studies key aspects of contextuality in literature through computational methods. We investigate genre and religious background for an early modern Neo-Latin drama corpus. To capture nuanced semantic relationships and structural phenomena specific to each of these two contexts, we use topic modelling and word embeddings. We fine-tune earlier research and develop new models targeted for our case study. We achieve high scoring and coherent results, both from a computational and a human interpretational point of view. The findings affirm the efficacy of our approach, demonstrating that these computational methods can indeed detect the impact of contextual aspects in shaping literary texts.

The content of this chapter is currently under review at DHQ, Digital Humanities Quarterly Journal, as follows: Andrea Peverelli, Marieke van Erp, Jan Bloemendal, 2025. Tracing Themes and Topics in Neo-Latin Drama through Topic Modelling and Word Embeddings.

The division of work in this chapter is as follows: main experiment design and execution by Andrea Peverelli, contributions to the original idea and its development and proof-reading by Marieke van Erp, Jan Bloemendal and Dirk van Miert.

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The exploration of external impacts on a text, such as its socio-cultural and the author's biographical context, is often regarded as one of the major contributing factors in shaping literary history. Partly drawing on the theory of intertextuality of Kristeva (1980), we inform our definition of contextuality as a particular form of intertextuality, between an author's text and its own surrounding constellation of 'external elements'. Our experiments investigate the impact of external elements on literary writing as major contributing factors to the shaping of a text. These elements, such as genre, the author's religious or philosophical background, cultural milieu, socio-political circumstances of the time, are seen as forces that significantly co-shape the stylistic features of a text, influencing not just what is written but how it is written.

In this paper, we investigate two of these contextual elements, genre and religious background, using topic modelling and word embeddings in an early modern Neo-Latin drama case study. The choice of these elements was dictated, on the one hand by the fact that religion was one of the most important elements in the early modernity. This was often regarded as the age of the 'Wars of Religion' between Catholics and Protestants, the age of the Reformation and Counter-Reformation (MacCulloch (2003), pp. 7-15). Thus, it is likely that religious background thus was of particular importance for an author's writing. On the other hand, our corpus contains drama texts with different sub-genres, therefore genre was another obvious choice. These two elements seem to be unrelated and bear no apparent interactions: our exploration is thus focused around two parallel features that independently impact and add to shaping an author's style. To investigate this impact, we use the methods of topic modelling and word embeddings.

Topic modelling identifies prevalent themes or 'topics' across a collection of documents, providing a macroscopic view of the main subjects discussed in the text, but is not able to capture the subtle nuances of language change. Word embeddings offer a complementary insight and have been proven in multiple instances to be effective at capturing semantic differences in literary texts.

Our paper presents two contributions to the current state-of-the-art. The main contribution is demonstrating that contextuality can be inquired through computational methods: we present a reproducible and expandable methodological pipeline to uncover specific and meaningful patterns of word distribution that shape the language of authors in recognisable ways according to their religious confession and the dramatic sub-genre. Furthermore, our research contributes to the field of Neo-Latin studies, showing that computational methods can reveal new perspectives on how external factors may have helped to shape early modern drama.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Related work is presented in section 3.2. Section 3.3 presents the data and corpus construction. Section 3.4 describes the experimental setup, with a further subdivision into section 3.4.1 and section 3.4.2. Section 3.5 presents the results. Section 3.6 concludes the paper with an overview on future work.

# of Texts	# Tokens	Time span	Genre distr.	Religious distr.
38	243,490	1529-1657	24 tragedies / 15 comedies	27 cath. / 12 prot.

Table 3.1: Corpus statistics in terms of number of texts, period covered, number of tokens, genre statistics and religious background distribution.

3.2 RELATED WORK

Both topic modelling and word embeddings have a long history of development and usage, and both rely on the often cited motto by J. R. Firth “you shall know a word by the company it keeps” (Firth, 1961): i.e., the basic distributional semantics assumption of “co-occurrence” (Lenci (2018)).

Blei first described topics as “a distribution over a fixed vocabulary”, and developed the most used methodology, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), that is also used in our experiment (Blei et al. (2003); Blei (2012)). Regarding word embeddings approaches, we are mostly interested in synchronic and distributional semantics, rather than diachronic evolution and meaning change. Li and Jurafsky (2015) deal with a wide range of NLP tasks such as relation identification and semantic relatedness, while Leavy et al. (2018) tackles with the issue of fine-tuning model parameters for historical texts. Closer to our case study, Sprugnoli et al. (2020), Sprugnoli et al. (2021) and Burns et al. (2021) provide a state-of-the-art word embeddings model for Latin.

In Computational Literary Studies that deal with elements of context, Manjavacas et al. (2020) describe how external elements and dominant themes are more likely to trigger intertextual references in a corpus of religious writings. In Bloem et al. (2020), the authors develop a word embeddings model to evaluate the philosophical-mathematical ideas in a late Neo-Latin corpus. Navarro-Colorado (2018) investigates single topics and themes in Spanish early modern poetry through topic modelling: the paper proposes a thorough investigation, through topic modelling, of this kind of poetry and whose distinction between single topics (found by the LDA algorithm as distributions of co-occurring words) and themes (clusters of topics that concur to define broader semantic categories) poses a novel foundation for the theoretical aspects of topic analysis. Jockers and Mimno (2013) applied topic modelling to nineteenth-century novels, revealing gender-based preferences in writing about certain topics. Thematically closer to our work is Schöch (2017), which presents a topic modelling experiment on early modern French drama demonstrating the impact and the shaping of traditional genre distinctions on drama writing.

3.3 DATA AND CORPUS CONSTRUCTION

We collected 38 texts from Catholic and Protestant authors comprising a total of 223,490 tokens and 4 different dramatic sub-genres, as defined by the authors themselves in their titles and prefaces or by contemporary literary critics, such as Julius Caesar Scaliger (Scaliger (1994-95)) and Gerardus Johannes Vossius (Vossius (2010)). These sub-genres pose the distinction between “sacred” and “secular” variants, being divided into tragedy, sacred tragedy, comedy and sacred comedy. The sacred variants are of course expected to have more focus on religious aspects.

The texts were pre-processed using a custom program, automatically cleaning errors,

modernising archaisms, unifying spelling variants and eliminating stop words, and then manually checked for errors and consistency by a Latin language expert.

Exclamations, interjections and general swear or dialogue-related words (oh, ah, vah, pol, mehercle, heu...) were kept as a vital part of the dramatic language. We eliminated stop and function words as their high frequency crowded out content words and generated noise in the experiments. Eliminating stop words has been demonstrated to improve the performance of topic models (Uglanova and Gius (2020)). For the word embeddings experiment, an additional layer of lemmatisation was applied using LatinCy (Burns (2023)). An overview of the corpus distributions can be seen in 3.1.

3.4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We performed two sets of experiments: 1) topic modelling experiments to trace the prevalent topics in our corpus, and 2) embeddings experiments as a complement to the first experiment, to pin-point more exactly the use of language that sets our sub-groups apart. The combination of these two helps us to gain insights into the religious background of the authors in our corpus, where topic modelling alone is not able to capture the nuances of confessions. The topic modelling experiment was performed through an evaluation of three different algorithms, producing several models that were then evaluated using topic coherence, as well as manually by an independent panel of 3 domain experts. The embedding experiments were evaluated using word similarity and analogy statistics as well as a Word Categorisation task.

3.4.1 TOPIC MODELLING

We used three different algorithms: Top2Vec, Scikit-LDA and MALLET. Top2Vec is a heuristic, unsupervised machine learning model that automatically identifies topics from a collection of documents by leveraging document embeddings. Both Scikit-LDA and MALLET instead utilise the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) algorithm for topic modelling, a statistical analysis of word frequencies and document-word distributions that uncovers latent topics within documents by assuming each document is a mixture of topics.

As a first step, our texts were chunked into separate documents of 100 tokens each, for a total of 2,290 snippets. Topic modelling algorithms have been proven to have better performances with a high number of low-token count documents, rather than small collections of large texts (Sbalchiero and Eder (2020)).

We then proceeded with a comparison between the three algorithms, with several trials combining different parameter combinations.

- Top2Vec - We tested combinations of different embedding models and parameter settings for UMAP, which is responsible for dimensionality reduction, and HDBSCAN, which performs clustering. Two embedding models were employed: ‘universal-sentence-encoder’ and ‘base-multilingual’. For UMAP, we varied parameters corresponding to the number of neighbours, the number of components, and the metric used (cosine or euclidean). For HDBSCAN, we altered the minimum cluster size, the metric (again cosine or euclidean), and the cluster selection epsilon, with two distinct settings for each. The final total number of model-parameter combinations were 8.

- **MALLET** - We used MALLET's implementation of LDA, systematically varying three key parameter combinations: the number of topics, the optimisation interval and the number of iterations. The number of topics was varied across four distinct values: 5, 10, 20, and 30, for different granularity exploration. The optimisation interval parameter, which controls the frequency of hyperparameter optimisation for topic-word distributions, was tested across six settings: 50, 100, 300, 500, 1000, and a special case of None (handled as 0 to indicate no optimisation). Finally, the iterations parameter, dictating the total number of sampling iterations over the corpus, was varied among six values: 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, and 1000. A total of 144 different models was thus produced.
- **Scikit-LDA** - Using Scikit-Learn's implemented LDA, we varied three main dimensions: the number of topics, the learning decay rate, and the choice between using TF-IDF weighting or raw term frequencies. The number of topics was explored over a range of 5, 10, 15, 30, 40, 50 and 100, again to assess different levels of granularity in our analysis. Learning decay rates of 0.5, 0.7, and 0.9 were tested to evaluate their influence on the learning process and ultimately on the quality of the topics extracted. Finally, the effect of pre-processing the input documents with TF-IDF transformation as opposed to using raw term frequencies was assessed, offering insights into how term weighting impacts topic coherence. A total of 42 different model-parameter combinations was thus produced.

We evaluated the performance of each model across the three algorithms through coherence score. Many variations of coherence have been proposed (Röder et al. (2015)): UMASS (which uses log probabilities of word co-occurrence within documents based on document co-occurrence counts, Mimno et al. (2011)), UCI (which utilises pointwise mutual information and document frequency to assess word associations, Newman et al. (2010)), nPMI (which employs normalised pointwise mutual information, providing a normalised measure of word co-occurrence strength, Bouma (2009); Aletras and Stevenson (2013)) and Röder's c_v (Röder et al. (2015)) (which does not use co-occurrence frequencies, but context vectors, counting the amount of words that appear within the range of a target word). We chose the most recent Syed and Spruit's c_v version (Syed and Spruit (2017)), being a widely used measure that encompasses a reliable multi-layer evaluation, and is also implemented in Gensim's package, thus making it easily applicable to any algorithm. Furthermore, the measure, contrary to simpler coherence measures that rely on direct word co-occurrence statistics, integrates both the co-occurrence and the conditional probability of word pairs within a sliding window across the text corpus. The measure is based on the idea that words contributing to a coherent topic are not only likely to co-occur but also share similar distributional contexts. has a procedural nature, and it involves several steps: segmentation (for a given topic's top N words, create pairs of words w_i, w_j), co-occurrence calculation (utilises a sliding window approach to estimate the probabilities of word occurrences and co-occurrences within the corpus), confirmation measure (for each pair of words, it calculates a confirmation measure that quantifies the degree of semantic similarity or support between them, leveraging normalised pointwise mutual information), and aggregation (aggregates the confirmation measures across all word pairs to yield the overall topic coherence score). Conceptually, it can be represented as follows:

Figure 3.1: Results of the topic modelling evaluation in terms of coherence scores. Since the training round produced widely different numbers of models across the three algorithms (MALLET, Top2Vec and Scikit-LDA), we plot them on a normalised scale, where the x-axis shows the number of model-parameter combinations and also show the number of topic batches for MALLET and Scikit-LDA. Scikit-LDA massively outperforms the other two algorithms, though showing an inverse tendency with a gradually decreasing line.

$$c_v = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i!} \sum_{j!} \text{score}(w_i, w_j) \quad (3.1)$$

Where N is the number of top words considered for each topic, typically the top 10 or 20 words; w_i and w_j are individual words from the set of top N words in a topic, with $i \neq j$ to ensure each pair is considered only once; $\text{score}(w_i, w_j)$ represents the confirmation measure between the word pairs.

As can be seen in Figure 1, with a scale of 0 to 1, Top2Vec's coherence showed scores between 0.14 and 0.24, Mallet showed values between 0.34 and 0.45, while Scikit-LDA's models scored between 0.69 and 0.82, massively outperforming the first two algorithms. Scikit-LDA was thus the algorithm of choice for the remainder of the experiment. As for the specific model that was chosen, it would be straightforward to just choose the best performing model as per coherence score. However, a few aspects must be taken into consideration when choosing the optimal number of topics:

- While, as foreseeable, as the number of topics increases, coherence scores tend to decrease, there isn't a clear trend regarding the decay rate's effect on coherence scores, while the usage of TF-IDF in some cases positively impacts the performance. Within the same number of topic batches (5, 10, 15, 30, 40, 50, 100) the variation in coherence is minimal, and thus is the choice of one model within the same batch as well (also confirmed by manual inspection of the topic distributions).
- Following these premises, the optimal configuration would be in the 5-topic batch. However, we note that at around 30 topics there is a stabilisation plateau of the

models (Figure 1): this indicates a balance between granularity and coherence, as 5 topics would be far too general and not able to properly distinguish any meaningful distribution, while, conversely, 100 would show a far too sparse granularity. In our specific dataset's case, with our parameter settings and chosen algorithm, for the remainder of the experiment we chose the 30 topics batch. Beyond this point there is a diminishing return effect: increasing the number of topics does not significantly enhance the coherence of the model, instead introducing more noise or redundancies. This choice is also corroborated by the “Sbalchiero-Eder rule” (Sbalchiero and Eder (2020)), which shows that the optimal number of topics is inversely proportional to the length of text chunks and the medium length of the dataset in terms of word count, setting it to 20-40 for our word count range (5.881 tokens average).

As a final step in our evaluation process, we submitted the chosen model's topic-word distributions to three independent domain-expert annotators. The evaluation was unanimous in recognising the high-quality level of our topics. The process of manual, blind evaluation, without pre-determined choices given to the annotators, can indeed yield widely varying results, derived from the annotator's personal background and biased reading: in our case, two annotators gave almost the exact same labels, differing very little between themselves (e.g. “Christian religion” vs “Christianity”), while the third annotator chose to give more ample and precise descriptions of the topics (following the previous example: “life and death of Christ on the cross and ascension to Heaven”). This poses the crucial aspect of granularity when assessing a topic model: the level of perceived disagreement depends entirely on the authors' will of smoothing the natural degree of semantic dispersion in the process of assigning objects to categories. For our experiment, we deemed a medium level of granularity optimal, thus maintaining the “christian religion” label. In the end, “life and death of Christ on the cross and ascension to Heaven” seemed to us, while too fine-grained, still encompassed in “Christian religion”, and so was for all the other cases.

We found the following clusters of topics: 6 super-specific, tied to very narrow topics depending on the plot; 6 general thematic categories: Religion (2 Christian, 1 Pagan), Kingship-Lordship (1 Kingship proper, 1 Kingship-military, 3 Kingship-religion), Emotions (2 Grief, 2 Love-Joy), 2 Crime, 3 Family, 3 Feast (excerpts of the topic-word distributions can be seen in Table 2, and 4 noise topics.

3.4.2 WORD EMBEDDINGS

As acknowledged in 3.4.1, the topic modelling experiment was able to capture general tendencies and phenomena related to genre as a hyper-generalistic feature of early modern literature, while giving no meaningful insights on the religious background feature. To capture the nuanced differences in style and writing between early modern era confessions, we needed to go deeper into the texts' fabric and ascertain if the heated theological debates of that age, particularly between Roman Catholics (mostly Jesuits) and the adherents to the newly instated Reformed (Protestant) faiths, could also be evident from a special case of literary production. On the contrary, word embeddings have been proven to be able to precisely capture semantic shift in literary history, whether diachronic or synchronic, with state-of-the-art examples for the Latin language Sprugnoli et al. (2020), Sprugnoli et al. (2021) and Burns et al. (2021); Bloem et al. (2020).

topic	Keywords
Religion	deus "god", christus "christ", nomine "in the name of", dominus "lord", uerbum "word", ueritas "truth"...
Kingship-Lordship	caesar "cesar", regna "reigns", caput "head", potens "powerful", sceptrum "sceptres", rex "king"...
Grief	poenitus poenitus "penitent", dolor "grief", lachrymas "tears", labor "toil", heu "alas", cura "anxiety", crudelis "cruel"...
Feast	dapes "meal", mensa "dining table", bacchus "(methonymic) wine", uenter "belly", fames "hunger", unum "wine", hospes "host"...
Love-Joy	amor "love", mulier "woman", hera "mistress", laeta "joyous", pectus "(methonymic) heart", foelix "happy", uoluptas "desire"...
Family	pater "father", filius "son", iuuenis "youngster", gnatus "child", frater "brother", torum "matrimonial bed", puer "kid"...
Crime	sscelus "crime", crimen "guilt", plangi "cry/repent", poena "punishment", nefas "violation", furor "madness", minas "sin/menace"...

Table 3.2: Excerpts from the keyword-topic distributions of the Scikit-LDA model with the main thematic categories.

- For the training round, our corpus of Early-Modern drama and a selection of sample Classical Latin texts were set as the training corpus . We collected a sample of the LASLA Latin corpus, keeping only dramas, philosophical and religious treaties, poetry, and some philosophical letters (such as those of Seneca), for a total of, combined with our corpus, 900.000 tokens;
- The corpus was lemmatised, using LatinCy, as earlier described in Section 3.
- For the test round, only our own drama corpus was considered: since we were exploring Catholic and Protestant religious backgrounds, our corpus was further filtered by only keeping texts after the year 1520, the year of Martin Luther's excommunication by pope Leo X, roughly indicative of the start of Protestantism.
- A custom metadata annotation was prepared by a domain expert, and our dataset corpus was accordingly sub-divided into two sets, catholic and protestant.

We leveraged several word embedding algorithms, using CBOW and Skipgram architectures from the Word2Vec and FastText algorithms (two fundamental and widely adopted approaches, repeatedly demonstrated to be effective at tasks like ours; [Sprugnoli et al. \(2021\)](#)), systematically testing different parameter combinations: dimensionality (100 and 300), window size (5, 10) and iterations (5, 10, 20). A total of 96 models was then produced, distributed over the 4 algorithms and the 2 features (catholic and protestant) we wanted to explore.

We set up various evaluation tasks on our corpus. As an external task, we used the benchmark set by [Sprugnoli et al. \(2021\)](#), which produced several word embedding models

for Classical Latin. By leveraging 8 of their models (which comprise the combinations of CBOW and Skipgram architectures from the Word2Vec and FastText algorithms with both dimensionalities, 100 and 300), we set up a simple similarity task: through a set of target words defined by a domain expert as the most representative in our early modern Neo-Latin drama corpus (and also confirmed as such by our first experiment on topic modelling word distributions), and by ensuring they are present also in the pre-trained models' vocabulary by applying a filter, we calculate the cosine similarity between the embedding of said target words and the embeddings in the models pre-trained by Sprugnoli. Cosine similarity values range from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates identical vectors, 0 indicates orthogonality (no similarity), and -1 indicates opposite vectors. Results showed a general tendency towards orthogonality with a very slight similarity, with values between -0.1 and +0.16. This indicates that our models are highly specialised towards the training corpus and not well-suited for a generalised task. We also noted that the catholic_fasttext_skipgram model consistently outperformed the others in this task: albeit by a margin and still within very low values, this confirms later findings, where the same model was found to be among the top scoring. An example can be seen in Table 3.

Target word	Models							
	Catholic FT CBOW	Catholic FT Skip-Gram	Catholic WV CBOW	Catholic WV Skip-Gram	Protestant FT CBOW	Protestant FT Skip-Gram	Protestant WV CBOW	Protestant WV Skip-Gram
gratia	0.106	0.1632	0.0196	-0.0305	0.069	0.0902	0.0639	0.0775
fides	0.0893	0.123	-0.0431	-0.1172	0.0908	0.0562	0.0674	0.0286
caesar	-0.0289	-0.0088	-0.0457	-0.1303	-0.0283	-0.0712	0.1403	0.1491
rex	0.0524	0.0864	-0.0138	-0.1475	0.0335	-0.0228	0.119	0.179

Table 3.3: Sample results of 4 target words for the similarity task between our word embedding model categories and the benchmark set by Sprugnoli et al. (2021). Median cosine similarity values are shown, with a range of -1 to 1, where 1 indicates identical vectors, 0 indicates orthogonality (no similarity), and -1 indicates opposite vectors.

Since the comparison with the mainstay Latin model did not yield meaningful results, we then reverted to an internal benchmark, namely an internal Word Analogy analysis. This was performed on our models following the approach of Sprugnoli et al. (2020). The fashion behind this analysis is 'x is to y as z is to ?', where the model predicts a word that best fits this relationship based on the vectors' geometry in the embedding space. We set up several question tasks following this structure, using the same most representative keywords defined in the earlier external comparison. The results vary widely across the different tasks and models, as expected, with scores reaching a 0.2 lowest. The results (a snippet of which can be seen in Table 3.4) also reach values very close to 1, indicating very similar or almost identical semantic meanings: these high scores indicate that the models very strongly associate the compared words due to similar contexts in the training data.

Finally, we devised a Word Categorisation task. First, we defined a set of categories and related keywords, covering the main aspects of our corpus (family, religious, royalty, war, emotions, historical, biblical), and their related top 10 most representative words as in the previous tasks. For each category, we computed the centroid (the mean vector of the group) of the vectors of the words in that category. For a given word, we

Model	caesar : christus, sanctus : ?	gratia : fides, pater : ?
catholic_fasttext_cbow	coelum	altus
catholic_fasttext_skipgram	christianus	consto
catholic_word2vec_cbow	coelum	caesar
protestant_fasttext_cbow	caelestis	rex
protestant_fasttext_skipgram	inuideo	fortis
protestant_word2vec_cbow	fides	uolo

Table 3.4: Word Analogy Task Results: samples of the top scoring models for two example question tasks, where "?" is the target word to be found by the model in order to solve the analogy.

predicted its category by assigning it to the category whose centroid is closest to the word's vector (in terms of cosine similarity). Finally, we compared the predicted categories with the true categories to calculate precision, recall and F1-score, calculated on a per-category basis and then averaged (through macro-averaging) to get an overall performance measure. The task results, which can be seen in Table 3.5, were solved in a median of F1 between 0.61 and 0.67 for the Word2Vec models and 0.48 and 0.61 for FastText, which performed worse overall. The best performing models in terms of F1-score were, more specifically, catholic_word2vec_cbow_dim300_window5_iter5 and protestant_word2vec_skipgram_dim300_window5_iter5, reaching very high scores between 0.83 and 0.93 and confirming the better performance of the 300 dimension setting and lower parameter settings for the window size and number of iterations in the context of our dataset.

Model		F1 Score
Catholic dim100	word2vec skipgram, windows:10, iterations:20	0.898
	fasttext cbow, windows:5, iterations:10	0.347
Catholic dim300	word2vec skipgram, windows:5, iterations:20	0.937
	fasttext cbow, windows:5, iterations:10	0.289
Protestant dim100	word2vec cbow, windows:10, iterations:5	0.844
	fasttext cbow, windows:10, iterations:20	0.185
Protestant dim300	word2vec cbow, windows:10, iterations:5	0.865
	fasttext cbow, windows:10, iterations:20	0.142

Table 3.5: Word embeddings model evaluation scores, with a snippet of the highest and lowest F1 model scores and the parameter combinations (dimension, windows, iterations and the type of algorithm) for each of the two religious backgrounds.

3.5 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The topic modelling experiment was only able to capture general tendencies and phenomena related to genre as a general feature of early modern literature. On the other hand, our results were quite precise in defining the relations between tragedy and comedy (and of the

Figure 3.2: Graph visualisation of the Religion and Kingship-Lordship topics. In the four sub-plots we show the genres (in this order: comedy, sacred comedy, tragedy, sacred tragedy), on the x-axis the number of text chunks in our corpus (in chronological order), and on the y-axis the strength of the topics, which are also colour-coded: Religion in blue, Kingship-Lordship in red. Religious topics dominate in the ‘sacred’ variants, while kingship topics, related to lordly and statecraft words, are prevalent in the ‘secular’ variants.

Figure 3.3: Graph visualisation of the Crime+Family/Feast topics chronological distribution. The 1620s phenomenon is shown here with a vertical black line.

sub-genres of sacred tragedy and comedy). Analysing the results of our experiments, we found that our topic modelling experiment could capture genre-related tendencies in early modern literature.

As was to be expected, we noted clear preferences towards religious topics in sacred comedy and sacred tragedy sub-genres, while Kingship-Lordship topics can almost exclusively be found in the tragedy and sacred tragedy sections. Family and feast topics were predominantly found in comedy (Figure 3.2), while crime topics were prevalent in the tragedy sector. For the emotions theme cluster (Joy-Love and Grief), there is almost no presence of grief topics in comedy, while they dominate in tragedy (Figure 3.2). Consequently, the

results largely confirmed the genre characteristics as traditionally described in Literary History. Generally, it was easier to define Catholic plays than Protestant ones, probably because Protestant theology on the one hand arose from its Catholic counterpart, and on the other hand was developing and had many strands.

From a chronological point of view, an atypical phenomenon can be noted in many thematic sectors (Figure 3.3). Towards the later stages of the corpus, around the 1620s, there's a steep rise in the Religion theme and an almost complete stop of Family-Feast topics, that instead give way to Crime topics (at least in our corpus). This could be a direct result of the worsening of the wars between Catholics and Protestants in those decades, but such statement needs to be proven with further evidence.

Regarding the second part of the experiment, again the results were highly coherent and distinctive. We here illustrate the most representative example, by listing the top scoring most similar embeddings in our model related to target words. As the most representative test, we explored the relation between *Gratia* and *Fides*, by showing the closest words in our model. This test explores the relationship between two of the most contentious concepts between the two confessions: Grace and Faith (being two of the "solae", the fundamental tenets of Lutheranism, "sola fide" and "sola gratia": by faith alone and by God's grace alone is man saved, with no external human intervention). In the Protestant cluster, there is a high presence of:

- words pertaining to hierarchy and mixing: *primus* (first), *pariter* (equally), *nexus* (bond), *misceo* (mix), *coniungo* (connect);
- negative aspects: *malignus* (evil), *tumultus* (turmoil), *horridus* (frightful), *uiolentus* (violent), *inuidus* (hateful), *languidus* (weak);
- faithfulness and the primary role of faith and reasoning: *fidus* (faithful), *consilium* (intention), *mens* (mind), *anima* (soul);
- words pertaining surpassing and betterment: *supero* (surpass), *superior* (superior), *augeo* (improve);
- negative words pertaining to inadequacy and partiality: *portio* (portion), *pars* (part), *nihil* (nothing), *desipio* (irrational), *inuitus* (unwilling);
- words pertaining doubt, fault and violation: *infernus* (hell), *periculum* (danger), *dubius* (doubt), *metus* (fear), *nefas* (sin), *timeo* (dread), *crimen* (crime).

These words suggest that, within the Protestant religious background, there is a focus on concepts such as faithfulness, and betterment, while implying an emphasis on themes related to the faith of individuals, seeking guidance, and the hierarchical structure within their works, and highlighting the fact that the concepts of grace and faith are linked to notions of improvement and inadequacy, besides doubt and internal struggle. This implies that Protestant writers explore themes such as the role of grace and faith in surpassing one's limitations, seeking a community, and understanding the inadequacy of human efforts. These patterns, perfectly aligning with early Protestant debates on theology, also indicate that Protestant writers in early modern Neo-Latin drama explore the challenges, conflicts and uncertainties related to the interaction between faith and grace, while still holding

these concepts as the centrepiece of their confession. In the Catholic cluster there is a high presence of:

- words pertaining to steadfastness, faithfulness, constancy and accomplishment: *constante* (firmly), *fidenter* (faithful), *fideliter* (faithful), *fidelis* (faithful), *confidentia* (confidence), *conficio* (accomplish);
- words pertaining to interpretation and authority: *interpretes* (interpret), *consultum* (deliberation), *principium* (principle), *consilium* (decision), *imperium* (authority);
- positive words traditionally related to Christianity: *gloria* (glory), *numen* (deity), *bonum* (good), *primus* (first), *confidentia* (credence), *feliciter* (happily);
- words related to sacrifice and hardship: *misereor* (be miserable), *excrucior* (be tortured), *interficio* (to die), *seruo* (be a slave), *contrarius* (adversary);
- words on factionalism and militancy: *factio* (faction), *militia* (militia), *satelles* (body-guard), *perduelles* (national enemy), *prodeo* (betray);
- words pertaining to “being lost” and penitent: *despero* (be desperate), *inficio* (deny), *poeniteo* (repent), *paenitentia* (repentance).

These words suggest that within the Catholic religious background, the concepts of grace and faith are associated with notions of repentance, perishing, compassion, interpretation, factionalism, and being lost and saved. These findings may imply that Catholic writers explore themes such as the need for repentance, the transformative power of grace, the presence of factions within the faith (possibly in open contrast with the Protestant churches), the struggles in everyday lives, and the quest for spiritual salvation, while also expressing a stable connection between the concepts of faith and grace, with a focus on themes related to unwavering faith, confidence in religious matters, interpretation of doctrine by higher authorities (the Church), and spiritual achievements, and in general a stronger emphasis on the harmonious or positive relationship between faith and grace. Again, this aligns with considerations on early modern, Tridentine, Roman Catholic theology (MacCulloch (2003), pp. 413-420)¹.

3.6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Our paper presents two main contributions: 1) for the field of Computational Literary Studies, it sets a base approach to the study of contextuality, by applying topic modelling and word embeddings to the case studies of genre and religious background. We demonstrate that the inquiry of these often vague aspects is indeed possible through computational methods. 2) for the field of Neo-Latin studies, it deepens the understanding of external, concurring factors in drama production.

¹While this study assumes Catholic and Protestant confessional labels as meaningful contextual categories, it does not claim they were rigid or uniform. As MacCulloch repeatedly emphasises, confessional identities in the Reformation era were fluid, internally diverse, and often shaped as much by politics and locality as by theology. The classifications used here reflect broad tendencies that emerge from our corpus, but they are not intended to suggest absolute divisions or essentialised religious ideologies

In this study, we primarily aimed to detect the impact of contextual elements on the case study of early modern drama authors, not to establish superior models for the Latin language processing. We adapted existing word embeddings models, not optimised for general-purpose tasks, confirmed by the fact that our model did not outperform pre-existing models when compared, but for the nuanced task of capturing semantic relationships associated with our focused context. These models excelled in identifying these relationships unique to our corpora, as reflected by their high internal word similarity scores. Our analysis further allowed us to pinpoint structural phenomena tied to genre, demonstrating that the authors' religious backgrounds significantly impacted the semantic relationships in the Neo-Latin texts. Thus, while our models may not be suited towards general-purpose tasks, they effectively served our targeted aim and established a methodological pipeline that could be replicated in similar research contexts. Our work is a showcase to predict features specific to different drama genres and the opposition between Catholic and Protestant backgrounds of the authors. We tuned our parameter combinations to our use case, which for other use cases such as other literary genres or languages would have to be tuned differently. However, our basic framework and methodology for investigating contextuality and its elements can be reused.

One natural future step would be to expand our corpus and experiment. Many drama texts are easily accessible, thanks to projects such as DraCor. This would require fine-tuning of our methodological approach, expanding to a multilingual setting, and a different set of hyper-parameters for topic modelling algorithms to better handle corpora of varying size and nature.

Another follow-up experiment, which the authors are already working on, is to reproduce the results of the experiments presented in this paper in a rule-based approach. Such an approach is purely heuristic and would constitute an additional proof, as well as giving new insights into a text or an author and its genre category and/or religious background. A text categorisation task would then be devised to accomplish this.

Our experiments present but two of the perspectives on tracing themes and topics in drama texts. Employing more tools from the NLP field will further our understanding of these and other corpora, helping to shed some more light on specific periods of literary history.

4

4

PREDICTING RELIGIOUS AND GENRE FEATURES

This paper studies key aspects of contextuality in literature through computational methods. Our case study revolves around two contextual aspects (genre and religious background) for an Early Modern Neo-Latin drama corpus. To investigate contextuality and capture nuanced semantic relationships and structural phenomena specific to each context, we perform a Text Classification task and exploit machine learning algorithms to produce a set of feature coefficients analysed through a custom metric, namely the Distinctiveness Coefficient. We achieve high scores and coherent results, both from a computational and a human-interpretable point of view. Furthermore, our model is able to pin-point both general tendencies of genre mixing and the differences between confessions in shaping the semantic background of Early Modern drama.

The division of work in this chapter is as follows: main experiment design and execution by Andrea Peverelli, contributions to the original idea and its development and proof-reading by Marieke van Erp, Jan Bloemendal and Dirk van Miert.

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The exploration of external influences on a text, such as its socio-cultural and author's context, is often not captured by traditional linguistic and literary analysis methods. The power of predictive algorithms can be harnessed to operationalise this aspect and bridge a knowledge gap too frequently overlooked by computational studies. Our experiment delves into the impact of external, contextual elements on literary writing. In this experiment, we use contextuality to refer to the relationship between a text and the broader constellation of historical, social, religious, and literary discourses within which it was produced and received. While this resonates with Kristeva's idea of intertextuality - that every text is an absorption and transformation of other texts (Kristeva, 1980, pp 68) - our usage of contextuality extends the concept beyond textual reference to include metadata, paratexts, and the external markers of genre, confession, and authorial influence. In this sense, contextuality becomes a bridge between style and culture, allowing for computationally measurable links between internal textual patterns and external cultural forces. Contextuality is thus defined as a particular form of internal intertextuality between an author's text and its own surrounding constellation of 'external elements' (Kristeva, 1980, pp 64-65). These elements, including but not limited to the author's religious or philosophical background, their cultural milieu, and the socio-political circumstances of the time are seen as forces that significantly shape the shape of a text, influencing not just what is written but how it is written. In this study, we apply a range of machine learning techniques such as Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Support Vector Machines, Gradient Boosting Machines and k -Nearest Neighbours, to analyse and categorise textual data, focusing on religious background and genre as primary features. We devise a classification task with an unsupervised heuristic approach, to, as described in Du et al. (2022), "identify characteristic or distinctive features of each group of texts in order to gain an evidence-based understanding of the specific contents, style and/or structure of these groups of texts".

Our main contributions is twofold. First, we present a reproducible approach by developing a pipeline that results in a task-specific model, eventually expandable to account for a wider generalisability, while also proposing a new score to evaluate features of a Logistic Regression prediction algorithm. Second, we demonstrate that contextuality can be accurately analysed through classification algorithms by focusing on what insights can be provided by their results and also errors - which partially steered our inquiry of genre features - when analysing literary texts. This enables us to draw both general observations on tendencies and patterns of writing and pin-point specific semantic characteristics that define the texts' fabric on a word level. Furthermore, our research contributes to the field of Neo-Latin studies by applying computational approaches to Neo-Latin drama: with this, we uncover new perspectives on how external influences may have shaped Early Modern drama, offering insights into a rich yet often overlooked body of literature and, for the first time, offering an automated drama classification for this corpus. This paper not only presents our findings but also discusses the challenges we faced in terms of model generalisability. These challenges point to important areas for future research, as we continue to refine our pipeline and expand its applications.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 4.2 gives a brief overview of the related research. Section 4.3 presents the data and its pre-processing. Section 4.4

describes the experimental setup, further sub-dividing into a model training and its evaluation. Section 4.5 offers a detailed analysis of the results, with three sub-sections dedicated to: analysing the errors and misclassifications, the distinctiveness score and the analysis of the coefficients for the religious background feature. Section 4.6 concludes the paper with an overview on future work.

4.2 RELATED WORK

Our experiment builds on the long-existing ground of Text Categorization (or Classification), with the main contributions in the field being found in the 90s, such as in [Lewis and Ringuette \(1994\)](#), [Reynar and Ratnaparkhi \(1998\)](#) and [Reynar \(2002\)](#).

More recent studies have proposed advanced Machine Learning solutions to text classification tasks. [Xu et al. \(2012\)](#) employs a Support Vector Machines (SVMs) classifier and provides an exhaustive study on how to deal with imbalanced data sets; [Yadav and et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Clark and Stuart \(2007\)](#) leverage Logistic Regression algorithms for text classification with high results, while [Liu et al. \(2009\)](#) and [Shah et al. \(2020\)](#) evaluate the performance of other algorithms (Random Forests and k -Nearest Neighbors), with [Shah et al. \(2020\)](#) in particular employing the same evaluation metrics as in our experiment (accuracy, precision, F_1 and confusion matrix). On the same issue of evaluation, [Du et al. \(2022\)](#) remains the most in-depth contribution to the extensive testing of distinctiveness metrics for the interpretation and the evaluation of feature results, in their three base types of frequency-based, distribution-based and dispersion-based metrics.

One of the two contextual macro-features we investigate in our research together with religious background is genre, which is a frequent application in the field of text classification. [Finn and Kushmerick \(2006\)](#) gives an exhaustive overview on the theoretical foundations of genre classification and how to operationalise the “domain transfer” between what we know to be a genre in general terms and what is actually portrayed by a data-driven approach (that is, the discrepancy shown between what is traditionally ascribed as genre and what instead results from data-driven analysis). As for practical applications, the approaches explored in the last years have been multiple, based on different features: from quite old contributions on web-based genre recognition [Roussinov et al. \(2001\)](#); [zu Eissen and Stein \(2004\)](#), to recent library inquiries [Ozsarfati et al. \(2019\)](#) in which the dominant features become non-content based information such as the age of the book or its title (and thus investigating paratextuality, an aspect akin to our contextuality), and the field of literary analysis. The latter is quite dense and the contributions are copious. Serving as examples, some recent studies are those of [Hettinger et al. \(2015\)](#), [Worsham and Kalita \(2018\)](#): the former focuses on large data, inquiring a corpus of 1700 German novels on both stylometric features and newly proposed ones like topic-based and character social network graphs; the latter creates the Gutenberg Dataset for Genre Identification and leverages deep learning algorithms to build an ensemble method based on decision trees, in which each chapter of a book votes towards the total genre of its whole, demonstrating the high performance of ensemble methods when dealing with large data.

The wider field of study on computational approaches to drama is extensive, and the approaches that have been proposed are multiple (mainly thanks to the DraCor Project, [Fischer and et al. \(2019\)](#), whose considerable database of dramas in several languages helped the development of the Computational Drama Studies field). [Schöch \(2017\)](#) for example

applies a Topic Modelling inquiry on thematic trends in classical French drama, while the very recent Szemes and Vida (2023) proposes an extensive analysis on clustering of German and Shakespearean dramas based on character networks and speech distribution. More in line with our proposed approach, Lehmann and Padó (2022) applies document embedding techniques and, like in our experiment, an analysis through log-likelihood scorings to categorise an unknown set of dramas as either comedies or tragedies, against a golden standard of pre-labeled comedies: the experiment shows a high precision in its approach, also showing a higher accuracy in tragedies. This higher accuracy ascribed to tragedies, that show a higher internal stylistic and lexical coherency, is also confirmed in our experiment.

To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first on possible overlap between the study of religious background and its influences on literary analysis and genre classification, and its influence on drama.

4

4.3 CORPUS CONSTRUCTION AND PRE-PROCESSING

In the composition of our corpus we identify 2 different classes in the religious background feature group (catholic and protestant), and 4 in the genre feature group (comedy - tragedy and sacred comedy - sacred tragedy). In early modern drama, three main genres have been identified by contemporary literary critics such as Julius Caesar Scaliger (Scaliger (1994-95)) and Gerardus Johannes Vossius (Vossius (2010)): tragedy, comedy and tragicomedy. The differences lie in the social status of the main characters (high in tragedy, low and middle in comedy, and mixed in tragicomedy), style (high, middle, and mixed), and plot and ending (sad ending, happy ending, and a sad play ending well or vice versa). These are formal characteristics that define genres, types or classes of literature (Abrams, 2005, pp.115-117)). In addition, Early Modern Neo-Latin playwrights called some of their plays 'comedia sacra' and 'tragoedia sacra' (sacred, i.e. biblical) comedy or tragedy. This designation is a distinction in terms of subject matter (biblical or other religious - Christian - stories), content and (educational) purpose, and thus these authors contrasted their plays, so to speak, with more 'worldly' or 'secular' subjects or 'history plays'. It is in line with these contemporary distinctions that we seek here to trace dramatic 'genres' in the traditional sense of tragedy, comedy and tragicomedy, and between 'sacred' and 'worldly/secular' ('non-sacred') drama. Sacred drama was written by playwrights on both the Protestant and Catholic sides of the denominational divide. One of our aims is thus to trace the choices of genre, style and language made by playwrights on both sides in contrast to 'secular' drama.

We started by collecting the Neo-Latin corpus from the TransLatin project repository,¹ for a total of 39 dramas and 243,490 tokens (post-cleaning). The texts were pre-processed using the CURRENS program², automatically eliminating non-alphanumeric characters, unifying spelling variants and eliminating stop words, and then manually checked for mistakes³. Exclamations, interjections and general swear or dialogue-related words were kept as a vital part of the dramatic language. Finally, the texts were lemmatised using LatinCy⁴ and manually checked for consistency in the lemmatisation. Our corpus was further sub-divided into its genre and religious background components, thus generating two sets

¹<https://www.transLatin.nl> Last visited: 30 November 2023

²<https://github.com/AndrewPeverells/CURRENS>

³Typically: OCR imprecisions (since the original texts come from a process of digitisation of ancient prints)

⁴Burns (2023)

of metadata labels: comedy, sacred comedy, tragedy and sacred tragedy for genre, catholic and protestant for religious background. The corpus was then converted into numerical representations through TF-IDF and finally sub-divided into smaller textual chunks of 100 tokens each and split into training and test set in a 80%-20% ratio, following a stratified approach to partially account for the data imbalance: to make sure at least one sample from each metadata label would be represented in both the training and test set, the data was divided in such way that each sub-group ("stratum") was present in both sets.

# of Texts	# Tokens	Time span	Genre distr.	Religious distr.
39	243,490	1529-1657	24 trag. / 15 comedies	27 catholic / 12 prot.

Table 4.1: Corpus statistics in terms of number of texts, period covered, number of tokens, genre statistics and religious background distribution.

4.4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, we present our experiment. Starting from an evaluation of the performance of 5 classifiers, we proceed with tuning and electing the best performing, that is then further evaluated and used to produce the coefficient distribution results.

4.4.1 MODEL SET-UP AND TRAINING

There exists a broad collection of classification algorithms. In our experiment, we evaluated five: Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forests (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) and k -Nearest Neighbour (k -NN). Recognising the unique characteristics of our dataset, comprising both genre and author's religious background, we intentionally developed a unified model to investigate how these elements independently contribute to the language and style of Early Modern drama authors. This approach allows us to dissect the distinct influence of each feature without conflating their potential interactions, which, while acknowledged as a separate and potentially worthwhile inquiry, lies beyond this study's scope.

We performed the first round of training with default parameter combinations, which yielded overall accuracy scores between 0.63 and 0.73. We then proceeded with tweaking our approach by:

- Re-training the models using 100 different iterations and expand the parameter grids for each algorithm to include at least 10 different parameter combinations. we selected parameter grids for each algorithm to encompass a diverse range of configurations. For instance, different choices of C values for Logistic Regression and SVM and a variation of `n_estimators` and `max_depth` in Random Forest and GBM models, aimed at balancing model accuracy with computational efficiency, as these parameters significantly influence the learning capacity and speed of ensemble methods.
- Applying Oversampling [van den Goorbergh et al. \(2021\)](#), [Megahed et al. \(2021\)](#) on the training data to account for the imbalance in our corpus, thus assigning higher weights to underrepresented classes;

- Applying Hyperparameter Optimisation through RandomizedSearch, to find the best combination of hyperparameters in our learning models.

While re-training a model with different and increased parameters addresses the problem of overfitting, and Oversampling tackles the issue of an imbalanced dataset, Hyperparameter Optimisation optimises the model's internal performance. At the end of this round, we notice a substantial improvement, with the best hyperparameter combination sets for each model yielding accuracy values between 0.73 and 0.89. The best scoring algorithm proved to be LR in both rounds (maybe due to the inherent simpler, binary, nature of our experiment, together with the limited amount of data at our disposal), and was therefore the model used in the final experiment.

4

4.4.2 MODEL PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To properly assess the validity of our model, stratified cross-validation was applied, yielding an average of 0.91 across accuracy, precision, recall and F_1 , over a 10-fold cross-evaluation. While this already gave us a better sense of the model's high stability and performance, statistical significance was tested using a t-test with $\alpha = 0.05$, to compare the results of the LR model pre- and post-tuning. Our results (T-statistic = -59.2, P-value = 4.87×10^{-7}) show that the difference in performance between the training rounds, pre- and post-tuning, yielded positive and substantial improvements to our model; they are thus statistically significant, having indeed an impact on its ability to accurately classify or predict outcomes. As a final step in the evaluation of our model, we calculated the feature performance, in terms of precision, recall and F_1 scores, for each of our six studied features (the aforementioned metadata labels), to check where our model was performing best and worst. The results are shown in Table 4.3. Finally, we produced a Confusion Matrix to have a visual representation of the types and the magnitude of misclassifications our model produced. These will be further analysed in the next section.

Models	Base Models accuracy score	Improved Models accuracy score
LR	0.73	0.89
RF	0.63	0.73
SVM	0.69	0.77
GBM	0.71	0.78
kNN	0.70	0.76

Table 4.2: Classification performance with five classifiers in terms of accuracy, before and after tuning.

Figure 4.1: Confusion Matrix on our model’s types and magnitude of misclassifications for the Religious Background features, with raw numbers. A darker colour indicates a higher level of misclassifications between the predicted label (x-axis) and the true label (y-axis) of our features. Note that the diagonal values are 0 because we are specifically inspecting errors.

Features	Precision	Recall	F ₁
protestant	0.89	0.97	0.93
comedy	0.95	0.90	0.92
sacred comedy	0.91	0.70	0.79
tragedy	0.93	0.84	0.89
catholic	0.92	0.73	0.81
sacred tragedy	0.82	0.96	0.89

Table 4.3: Classification Report for Logistic Regression model’s features in terms of precision, recall and F₁ scores.

Figure 4.2: Confusion Matrix on our model's types and magnitude of misclassifications for the Genre features, with raw numbers. A darker colour indicates a higher level of misclassifications between the predicted label (x-axis) and the true label (y-axis) of our features. Note that the diagonal values are 0 because we are specifically inspecting errors.

4.5 RESULTS

In this section, we present an in-depth analysis of the feature coefficients produced by our best performing model, by first analysing the errors and misclassifications and then proposing a novel analysis on the coefficients' distribution and values. Finally, we re-test our model on unseen data (Classical Latin) to evaluate its robustness in the specific task of identifying genre and religious features.

4.5.1 FEATURE AND MISCLASSIFICATION ANALYSIS

Our results yield a 10.9% misclassification rate, with some classes proving more unstable than others. By analysing these more in-depth, we can discern some patterns:

1. Religious background:

- “protestant” has a high incidence of misclassifications into catholic, while the other way round (catholic mistaken as protestant) is comparably really low. This is confirmed by the feature performance report (table), where protestant scored the second lowest precision out of every feature;
- Some authors (Grotius, Heinsius and Zevcotius) have an especially high misclassification rate from protestant into catholic, posing a doubt on their clear-cut religious background and putting them as a sort of “middle-ground” authors between the two confessions;
- As a general trend, authors falling in the Protestant background class show a weaker imprint compared to their Catholic counterpart. This makes Protestant authors somewhat less immediately “recognisable” by their textual features. Historically, Protestant authors, especially in earlier stages (16th century and early 17th) tended to be more experimental in their writing. Many did not want to appear openly protestant for political reasons, and in general the Reformed faiths were still building their own theology and narrative, while Catholicism had centuries of well-grounded tradition to rely upon.

2. Genre:

- In the “base” genre classes (comedy and tragedy), tragedy is the most consistently clear-cut, while comedy is often mistaken as a tragedy. This can mean that tragedy has stronger defined features than comedy, an element already noted in [Lehmann and Padó \(2022\)](#);
- In the “sacred” genre variants, while sacred comedy is sometimes only mistaken with its base form (comedy), sacred tragedy appears to be the most unstable of classes, quite often mistaken with its base form (tragedy). Neither sacred variant class is ever mistaken as its opposite (sacred tragedy into sacred comedy and vice versa). This is again confirmed by the feature performance report 4.3, where sacred tragedy scored the lowest precision (0.82) out of all classes;
- This pattern can be roughly drawn as in 4.3, where the closer (horizontally and vertically) two classes are the more “hybridable” they appear to be. Comedy has a high hybridisation with tragedy, sacred tragedy has a high hybridisation with

tragedy, while sacred comedy seems to be the most separated of genres, having very low hybridisation with both sacred tragedy and comedy. Tragedy seems to be a focal point, as all of its nearest co-genres tend to it, and not the other way round. This analysis, which relies on the general trends of our limited corpus, will have to be supported by more insights and critical studies of genre evolution in Early Modern Literature.

Figure 4.3: Schema of the 'hybridisation rate' between drama sub-genres based on error analysis. The closer (horizontally and vertically) two classes are the more "hybridable" they are.

4.5.2 DISTINCTIVENESS SCORE

To better analyse the distribution and nature of the religious background features, we propose a Logistic Regression Distinctiveness Score (LRDS). While still conceptually aligning with the overarching theme of assessing the importance of features in a general classification task, our metric is specific to the Logistic Regression algorithm here employed. Furthermore, it is akin to distribution-based scores such as Welch's t-test [Du et al. \(2022\)](#), in that it focuses on how distinctively a word contributes to classifying texts into different categories. Instead of being a statistical test, our LRDS is calculated as the sum between the absolute values of coefficients in a boolean fashion, proceeding with two opposing classes at a time, as follows:

$$LRDS \ |coeff_{i_1}| \ |coeff_{i_2}| \quad (4.1)$$

The result of this calculation is a binary table (as in [Table 4.6](#)), showing raw values and a positive/negative distinction, based on how distinctive or non-distinctive a specific feature was found by the model, and a final column with the overall distinctiveness value to attest how generally distinctive a specific word is in the considered corpus (and thus its overall thematic importance). When calculating the Mean Distinctiveness across all features (0.28) and the 90_{th} percentile (0.8), the resulting plot ([4.4](#)) shows a distribution that

follows a power-law, with an elbow curve. The 90_{th} percentile, thus the top 10% features with a coefficient of >0.8 (marking the elbow in the distribution), is a reasonable choice for a threshold to consider when discriminating what is distinctive for either class. As a comparison, we calculated the log-likelihood values to assess the significance of individual features in our model. Our results revealed varying degrees of significance among the features, with lower log-likelihood scores indicating stronger discriminatory power. The chi-squared test yielded a log-likelihood G₂ score of 29.1 with a corresponding p-value of 6.8, indicating a highly significant association between the features and the class labels. The top features found by the log-likelihood analysis can be viewed in table 4.6 alongside the ones produced by the Distinctiveness analysis: as can be seen, there is a clear overlap between the two sets of features, although with different rankings.

In our specific case, as an example of qualitative analysis, when considering the top 100 distinctive features for both classes in the religious background features (Catholic and Protestant), we confirm that our model was able to capture the subtle nuances between the two confessions in terms of words distributions while also giving us insights on the key underlying thematics of Early Modern Neo-Latin drama production:

1. Catholic: presence of words pertaining to temporal power and kingship (Caesar, rex, regius, dominus, patria, regnum, princeps, nutus, procer - Caesar, king, regal, lord, state, kingdom, prince, command, noble), militancy and opposition (periculum, hostis, miles, odium, iniuria, carcer, uulnus - danger, enemy, soldier, hate, offense, jail, wound), servitude (seruo, seruus - to serve, to be a serf), a sense of brotherhood (frater, soror - brother, sister), strong passions (lacryma, turbo, furia, amo, inuidia, iniquus, ferus, laboro, amor - tear, to shake, fury, to love, envy, wicked, savage, to toil, love), sacred spaces and the tradition of the Church (templum, sermo, sacer - temple/church, speech/sermon, holy), sacrifice and hardships (misereo, excrucio, interficio, contrarius - be miserable, to suffer, to fail, to be opposed), death, the afterlife and Christ (Christus, coelum, coeli, cedo - Christ, sky, heavens, death);
2. Protestant: presence of words pertaining to doubt and uncertainty (dubius, flebilis, excutio - doubtful, weak, examine), crime and wrongdoings, and in general negative words that indicate the emphasis on human depravity and the fear of God's judgment (crimen, malum, moneo, scelus - crime, wrongdoing, admonish, sin), inadequacy and partiality (portio, pars, nihil, desipio, inuitus - to be partial, part, nothing, act unreasonably, unwilling), moral values related to justice and a correct life (recte, sane, exemplum, rectus, certe - correctly, reasonably, example, honest, reliably), "philosophical" concepts and learning (disco, anima, forma, frons, mens, spes - to learn, soul, form, knowledge, mind, hope), and words pertaining to quietness and moderateness (quies, resto, medium - quiet, stand firm, moderate), while shunning everything related to kingship and the role of authority, strong passions and militancy.

These words suggest that, within the Catholic religious background, the most distinctive word-features are associated with notions of perishing, repentance, compassion, factionalism, faith through hardships, the primary role of rulers and their divine mandate, and being lost and finally saved. On the opposite side, Protestants put more focus on faithfulness, betterment, the faith of individuals, notions of improvement and inadequacy before God,

doubt and internal struggle, moral values tied to moderation, restraint, justice and rectitude. These considerations align perfectly with considerations on Early Modern, both Tridentine Roman Catholic and Reformed Protestant theologies.

feature	coeff_protestant	coeff_catholic	distinctiveness score
caesar	-4.903694882	6.003554131	10.90724901
coelum	-3.349492849	6.443470674	9.792963524
frater	-2.160909004	6.588889494	8.749798498
crimen	5.736912339	-2.982059086	8.718971425
christus	-2.601463388	6.049339061	8.650802449
coeli	-2.273204956	4.917769456	7.190974412
rex	-1.2380146	5.698262069	6.936276669
disco	4.196774056	-2.527466773	6.724240829
regius	-2.29900129	4.326191744	6.625193033
dubius	3.95774998	-2.591834787	6.549584766
hostis	-1.939525563	4.489386285	6.428911848
seruus	-2.292542271	4.110176242	6.402718513
anima	5.462119737	-0.904835675	6.366955412
cedo	4.140706706	-2.019452271	6.160158977
sacer	-1.245508517	4.579210377	5.824718895
recte	2.923740919	-2.879014925	5.802755844
impius	-2.100476913	3.669966603	5.770443516
quies	3.649554719	-2.098001337	5.747556056
miles	-2.522929517	3.130317821	5.653247338
dominus	-1.581446971	4.065808403	5.647255374
laboro	-2.309145927	3.291911845	5.601057772
forma	3.37510853	-2.156424959	5.531533489
procer	-2.292571179	3.158401165	5.450972344
resto	4.124362642	-1.292288738	5.41665138
lacryma	-1.917231733	3.374230213	5.291461946
lex	4.515394706	-0.752622495	5.268017201
odium	-2.340004002	2.900922898	5.2409269
...			

Table 4.4: Distinctiveness Score

protestant feature	catholic feature
coelum	frater
crimen	christus
recte	caesar
dubius	rex
disco	malus
conuiuus	magnus
fides	animus
sane	coelum
frater	mens
queus	sacer
deus	hostis
pater	regius
forma	seruus
quies	uerus
minax	dominus
mens	puer
actus	amo
animus	loquor
infelix	impius
affectus	mорий
uita	amor
uetus	sanguis
malus	dux
rectus	lacryma
certe	carcer
excutio	laboro
exemplum	seruo
...	

Table 4.5: Log-likelihood

Table 4.6: Sample of the top 100 features for the religious background classes for the Distinctiveness Score analysis (top) and the log-likelihood analysis (bottom)

Figure 4.4: Power-law distribution of distinctiveness scores across features. The x-axis shows the features in order of ranking based on their Distinctiveness score, while the y-axis shows the actual magnitude of their Distinctiveness.

4.6 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented two contributions: 1) For the field of Computational Literary Studies, it sets a base approach to the study of contextuality, by applying classifiers to the case studies of genre and religious background, ultimately demonstrating that the inquiry of these often vague aspects is indeed possible through computational methods, and 2) For the field of literary and Neo-Latin studies we find a way to trace external, concurring factors in Early Modern drama production, and deepen their understanding.

In this paper, we primarily aimed to detect the influence of contextual elements on the case study of Early Modern drama authors, not to establish superior models for Neo-Latin language processing. We developed a specific model, optimised for the nuanced task of capturing semantic relationships associated with our focused context. This model excels in identifying these relationships unique to our corpora, as reflected by its high performance and highly coherent coefficients. Our analysis further allowed us to pinpoint structural phenomena tied to genre, and to demonstrate that the authors' religious backgrounds significantly influenced the semantic opposition between faiths in the Neo-Latin dramas. Thus, our models effectively served our targeted aim and established a methodological pipeline that could be replicated in similar research contexts, while they may not be suited towards general-purpose tasks. Furthermore, this study's methodological approach, deliberately selecting a unified model to examine the distinct influences of genre and religious background, aligns with our goal of uncovering how these elements independently shape Early Modern drama. By doing so, we performed a nuanced exploration of each contextual factor's standalone contribution, setting a precedent for further inquiry that might explore their interactions, or those of other

features, within the literary domain.

One take-away from our experiment is the often overlooked consequence that errors (misclassifications) can have on literary analysis while developing models for the analysis of literary phenomena. Through a discrepancy with pre-existing knowledge (in our case pre-set labels), these can tell us something different from what we presume to know and unveil hidden characteristics. For example, some authors that were traditionally ascribed to the Protestant faith (e.g. Grotius' *Sophompaneas*, a tragedy about the patriarch Joseph) showed an imprint that is much more akin to their Catholic counterpart than their brethren, posing doubts on their earlier clear-cut place.

A natural future step would be to expand our corpora and case study. The availability of data for drama texts is high and of quite easy access, thanks to projects such as DraCor⁵ and TransLatin⁶. This would also naturally imply a fine-tuning of our methodological approach, by re-testing classifiers with and a different set of hyper-parameters to better handle corpora of widely varying size and nature.

Another follow-up experiment, which the authors are already working on, is to replicate what has been presented here using a rule-based approach: while this experiment is purely heuristic, and found meaningful results through an unsupervised approach by building models tailored to the inquired corpus, it would constitute an additional counter-proof, while also possibly giving new insights, to build new models, or leveraging entirely different methodologies like Topic Modelling and Word Embeddings, based on the findings of our experiment.

⁵<https://dracor.org/>

⁶<https://translatin.nl/>

5

A STYLOMETRIC AND NETWORK ANALYSIS OF A MULTI-LINGUAL EARLY MODERN DRAMA CORPUS

The content of this chapter is currently under review at: Andrea Peverelli, 2025. A Stylo-metric and Network Analysis of a Multi-lingual Early Modern Drama Corpus. To be published in: D. Wouters and J. Bloemendal (eds.), *The Transnational Impact of Latin Theatre: Qualitative and Computational Analyses*. Leiden: Brill (in preparation)

The division of work in this chapter is as follows: main experiment design and execution by Andrea Peverelli, proof-reading by Jan Bloemendal, Dinah Wouters and Marieke van Erp.

5

5.1 INTRODUCTION

When we read experiment reports on stylistic analyses for modern and contemporary literature (whether through Stylometry, Network analysis, common distance measures and Machine Learning algorithms for text classification and categorisation), there is a common feature that can be gleaned in most cases: texts of the same author tend to be inextricably tied together, with minimal scatter (fig. 5.1). Of course, there will always be connections between different authors, giving researchers a basis for claiming stylistic similarities between different writers, but the strongest connections are regularly found within clusters of the same authors. This phenomenon is what the field of Stylometry calls a stronger ‘authorial signal’, which is described as the sum of features found to be defining of an author’s style¹: in the case of modern and contemporary writers, the tendency seems to be that the set of stylistic features shared by same-author instances is stronger than that shared by different authors. However, we have already discovered previously in other papers that in the case of drama², early modern authors do not follow the same distribution, but show a higher degree

¹These would typically be lists of most frequent words, for Stylometry, but they could be a myriad others. [Stamatatos \(2009\)](#), pp. 538-56, estimates nearly 1,000 different features). In general, these features, or markers, are ‘any linguistic feature that can be formally defined and measured computationally’, and include: ‘frequencies and frequency distributions of characters, words, lemmata, word classes or syntactical structures, taken by themselves or in sequences (n-grams); and the length, and distribution of lengths, of words, sentences, paragraphs or other units’ ([Herrmann et al. \(2015\)](#), pp. 25–52).

²[Peverelli et al. \(2022b\)](#), pp. 5295–303. Regarding other genres, it is still to be definitively proven with evidence, but there are already hints towards this same conclusion (see for example [Navarro-Colorado \(2018\)](#))

Figure 5.1: Dendrogram stylistic (Delta) visualisations of a modern era English novels corpus (right, 1811–1915) and of Harper Lee's (left, 1926–2016) inspirations and models. Same-author instances are shown in the same colour, displaying the phenomenon of a stronger authorial signal in modern and contemporary literature. See Eder (2017a), pp. 50–64; Choinski et al. (2019), pp. 355–374.

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of scatter (i.e. same-author instances that do not cluster together, but end up in different groupings) and, consequently, show a weaker authorial signal (fig. 5.2)

This brings us to a first consideration: Could this phenomenon be due to the fact that modern and contemporary authors have a stronger sense of authorship than early modern playwrights? The concept of the literary author as the expression of a strong individuality through writing emerged much later than in the early modern era, especially with European Romanticism. For a long time, authors were the auctor(s), the classics were used as models whose auctoritas was unquestioned. In other words, all authors were following in the footsteps of the ancients and their style was largely shaped by the literary style of the same ancient dramatists. Moreover, much of the early modern drama was not intended as an expression of the author's individuality, but primarily as a means of teaching. Jesuit playwrights were even obliged by their Order to remain anonymous:

“They [Jesuit dramas] are not primarily conceived as literature in the present sense for a reading circle of recipients, but rather are the result of a subsequent action of archiving. [...] In this respect, the term author can be questioned. For the Jesuits deemed it important that the performance of a play was not valued as an individual achievement, but as proof of the collective pedagogical potency of the college in question or of the entire Order. For that reason, the manuscript texts were transmitted in a fundamentally anonymous manner. Their allocation to individual authors is almost always secondary.”³

Therefore, anyone attempting a stylistic analysis of similarities between early modern dramatists must be aware of several factors. An analysis of style as a raw comparison between texts and their quantifiable elements, while still valuable, is not the only one to take into account, and may not even be meaningful in itself. The role of external elements operating in the background, such as religious affiliation, theme of the work, place and

³Fidel Rädle, ‘Jesuit Theatre in Germany, Austria and Switzerland’, in Bloemendal and Norland (2013), p. 185.

Figure 5.2: Early cluster visualisation (Classic Delta, 100–1,000 MFWS) of raw stylistic similarities in our early modern drama corpus. Same-author instances have the same colour, showing the higher degree of scattering of the authorial signal.

year of publication, institutional context, purpose and function of the text, classical stylistic model and audience, all contribute in shaping the authorial signal. The fact that one author is linked to another by stylistic similarity does not tell us much; but if we take into account additional contextual information, if we superimpose the knowledge that both authors are Protestants, from different countries and different periods, but both dealing with Biblical drama, this gives us a much different and more informed interpretation of that link. And if we do the same for every author and text in our corpus, the resulting overall picture will change dramatically, revealing recurring phenomena and tendencies that raw, quantifiable stylistic similarities could not reveal on their own. This reveals one of the issues of Transnational Literary Studies: the circulation and reception of texts can take place in both geographically and chronologically distant countries, but the context is very important for establishing actual relationships. For these reasons the aim of this article is to provide a multi-layered analysis of an early modern drama corpus, taking into account both raw similarities and the crucial external elements mentioned above.

5

5.2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this experiment is that of Stylometry combined with network visualisation and analysis. Stylometry is a computational approach to the study of texts, involving a variety of different methods such as distance measures and Machine Learning algorithms. Its aim is to compare the frequencies and distributions of Most Frequent Words (MFWs), the most frequently occurring words in a text, with the underlying assumption that their number and distribution across multiple texts by the same author constitute stylomes, peculiar idiosyncrasies of an author's *usus scribendi*. As such, it is a crucial set of methods for the study of literary style, and it differs from semantic-based approaches that analyse the content of a text, mostly dealing with aspects of sentence structure and linguistic features. Stylometry has a long history of development and use, having been established between the 1980s and the 1990s⁴. Our experiment therefore builds on well-trodden and stable ground, and in particular it replicates the first of two sets of experiments carried out by the present author⁵. The paper proposes a stylometric investigation to assess stylistic similarities within an early modern drama corpus, similar to our case; secondly, it compares the resulting clustered network with a classical Latin auctoritas, that of the *Eunuchus* by Terence. Our analysis makes use of the first part of their experiment, since it shares many similarities and even some texts themselves. Instead of sub-dividing our corpus into 4 different languages, we end up building a much larger final monolingual corpus⁶, starting from multiple languages and ending up, with automatic translation, to an English version for all the texts. Therefore, while the general approach remains the same, the choice and adjustment of the parameters is adapted to our specific corpus, in terms of language, total size and medium length.

⁴Burrows (1987); Holmes (1998)

⁵See Peverelli et al. (2022a)

⁶Peverelli et al. (2022a) had 4 different sub-corpora for Italian, Latin, English and French, with the largest having 34 total texts and a grand total of 85 between all four languages, while the corpus of this experiment has 74.

5.3 CORPUS CONSTRUCTION AND PRE-PROCESSING

We know that hundreds of dramas were written in the early modern era, a great part of which is still waiting to be digitised. Our own corpus is the result of a long process of digitisation and correction, and, while partial, it is still representative of the whole production. It can accurately capture trends and patterns that, as will be evident in the Results section, largely re-confirm earlier findings of even smaller corpora. In the end, we gathered a total of 74 texts, totalling 667,000 words after cleaning. The texts comprise different databases of early modern drama:

- Thematic: Joseph plays (8), Prodigal Son plays (3), Everyman plays (14), Old Testament dramas (18), generic Historical dramas (14), Morality/Didactic plays (8), other Religious drama (7), and other/unknown (1).
- Didactic plays (8), other Religious drama (7), and other/unknown (1).
- Religious background: Catholic (44), Protestant (21), Humanist/Mixed (4), and Anonymous (5).⁷
- Genre: Comedy (22), Tragedy (39), Unspecified (10), Tragicomedy (3).
- Provenance/Place of publication: Low Countries (41), Germany (18), France (8), Switzerland (4), Italy (1), Poland (1), England (1).
- Year span: the vast majority of the texts are within the 1500s (38) and the 1600s (35), and 3 from the 1400s, with some notable outliers (Ecerinis – Mussato 1315 and Annibal Moriens – Weitenauer 1756).

Each text, coming from an OCR process, was manually checked for consistency and errors in the digitisation process, and then cleaned of its dramatic paratext (notations of characters, choruses and verses, scene and act boundaries, abbreviations, summaries and introductions). The languages involved are: German, Dutch, Latin and English. The challenges are immediately apparent, as multilingual analysis in Computational Studies is never an easy task. There is currently no straightforward way to deal with a multilingual corpus for any kind of similarity task without having an intermediate link, typically in the form of translations or transliterations⁸. The way we overcame this problem was through automatic translation into contemporary English using OpenAI's GPT API (Application Programming Interface). We used the GPT 4.0 model with a custom API key. The process involved a number of crucial steps:

- Since the API can process up to 4,000 words at a time, and there is a trade-off between the accuracy of the task performed and the amount of tokens submitted for the task (i.e. despite the 4,000-word maximum, there are diminishing returns effects if a user submits close to 4,000 words, yielding less answers and requiring more computational effort, rather than submitting fewer words at a time), we split each text

⁷The author is aware of the issue of a more “fluid” religious affiliation in the early modern era: some authors did not identify themselves as clearly Protestant or Catholic, while some others either changed sides or were simply not interested in identifying with a specific affiliation.

⁸See [Peverelli et al. \(2022a\)](#).

Original	GPT Translation	1992 Translation
Nemo omnium mortalium felicior Me vivit usquam gentium, quod nesciam Si quidlibet meam ad beatitudinem Queat addier. Formosa coniunx, filii Acres, venustae filiae, ampla familia est. Varia supellex ornat aedeis splendidas, Thesaurus auro, argento et electro tumet, Arcaeque periticaeque veste plurima Ex purpura vel coccino aut holoserico Conferta sunt;	No one among all mortals lives happier than me anywhere among the nations, that I do not know if anything would increase my happiness. A beautiful wife, hardy sons, fair daughters, a large household, a variety of utensils, decorate splendid rooms. The treasury swells with gold, silver and copper, and chests and perchs are full of many garments, made with purple or scarlet or silk.	There is no man living happier than I am, because I do not know if anything could be added to my happiness. My wife is beautiful; my sons are spirited; my daughters charming; my household is a large one. Furniture of various types adorns my luxurious home. My treasure house is bulging with gold, silver and amber; my chests and my hanging rods are loaded with many garments of purple, of scarlet, all of silk.

in smaller, more manageable chunks of 2,000 words each to ensure a better result. The translated chunks were then reassembled at the end of the process, reconstructing the entire texts prior to analysis;

- The input task (i.e. the command given to the AI) was structured as follows: ‘Translate the following text chunk from early modern [language] to English, maintaining the original poetic structure and verses, punctuation and stop-words as much as possible; no additional annotations, comments, or formatting should be included in the translation output’. The additional parameters given to the AI were inserted to ensure that the structure of the drama was respected, maintaining the boundaries between character utterances and their verse structure. It is important to note that the automatic translation was tested in two approaches: 1) from early modern German to modern German and then to English, and 2) directly from early modern German to English. The result did not show any significant differences in the quality of the translation, but we suspect a greater dispersion of semantics: since a perfect 1:1 translation is impossible, some nuances of meaning are always lost when translating from a source to a target language, and adding another language layer in the middle of the process only increases the risk. In the end we decided to use the direct translation from early modern German to English for the whole experiment.

The result was an acceptable translation that retained as much of the original dramatic tone and verse structure as possible, and was suitable for our experiment. Here is an example of the GPT translation of the *Hecastus* by Macropedius, compared with the translation of C. C. Love, verses 97–106 (see table above)⁹.

As a final step in the preparation of the corpus and in keeping with our aim to also analyse external features, we created a set of metadata with which we annotated each text in our corpus:

- Temporal dimension: year of publication (of the first edition);
- Spatial dimension: place of publication. This was preferred to the place of production, i.e. where the author actually wrote the text (which could be different from where he published it), because, apart from the fact that it is often difficult to trace over the actual registered place of publication, there is one main reason for this. The early modern period is characterised by a *respublica literaria*, a republic of letters in which authors travelled frequently and came into contact with other intellectual centres,

⁹Love (1992), <https://ccltlp.artsci.utoronto.ca/appendix.html>

schools and universities. Very often, for political, religious or simply biographical reasons they ended up as headmasters, teachers and professors in places other than where they were born or studied. It is in these places, where the texts were printed that the plays circulated, were read and performed, making this aspect particularly important for stylistic similarities and overlaps;

- Topical dimension: the main theme of the play;
- Religious dimension: the religious background of the playwright. The early modern period is also characterised by an intense and prolonged series of tensions and violent conflicts between Catholics and Protestants, being the age of the Reformation and Counter-Reformation. It can therefore be valuable to analyse whether there are contacts, overlaps or conflicts between authors, from a religious background point of view, using a network visualisation.

5.4 EXPERIMENT

The kind of analysis we perform is one of stylistic clustering, rather than the more traditional authorship attribution and detection, for which Stylometry originally was developed as a methodology. Our focus is thus shifted to highlighting similarities within a corpus of already attributed works, and, as such, we do not need to divide our corpus into training and test sets and compare a set of features with an unknown target to be identified later¹⁰. We then proceeded to set the parameters for the cluster analysis, the most important of which is the choice of MFWs (most frequent words). The core of stylometric analyses is the comparison between two sets of the co-occurrence of MFWs in texts, whose frequency and distribution along the texts determine the resulting similarities between the two sets. This means that, for example with 100 MFWs, only the 100 most frequent words in a corpus with an average length of between 10,000 and 15,000 words (such as ours) could be considered for the similarity analysis. However, this is too low a setting, which means that each text will be linked to the others as very similar. On the other hand, if the choice of MFWs is too high, the basis for the similarity analysis will be too broad and sparse, and the algorithm will perceive each text as separate. This is true for the set length of 10–15,000 words mentioned above, but as we increase the length of the texts, this trade-off varies: if a text is longer, it will naturally have a greater amount of common frequent words (according to Heap's law¹¹), and thus the MFWs parameter must be adjusted accordingly. Although many studies have tried to extract precise sets of MFWs based on the length of the texts, in the end each corpus is different and must be evaluated separately. Much of stylometric analyses play around this delicate balance. Although this experiment largely replicates an earlier one and shares many similarities with it¹², we still went through a rigorous testing phase, which proved that some parameters should indeed be accurately assessed and evaluated:

- For the selection of the MFWs, we carried out different trials for each setting from 100 to 1,500 MFWs. This is a well-established practice in Stylometry, to avoid the

¹⁰This is the classic case of an 'open game', see [Peverelli et al. \(2022a\)](#)

¹¹Heap's or Herdan-Heap's Law describes the number of distinct words in a text as related to its length. In this empirical law, it hardly matters if a (significant) part of the text or the whole text is examined and if the text is in due order or randomly shuffled.

¹²I.e. [Peverelli et al. \(2022a\)](#)

risk of cherry-picking and overfitting. Up to 500 MFWs the clustering rate increases gradually, moving from a situation where the whole corpus forms a single macro-cluster to the emergence of real families of clusters. After 500 MFWs we observe a diminishing returns effect, where the clustering reaches a stable plateau (marking it as the desirable parameter setting) and then gradually starts to scatter the clusters when very high settings (1100–1200>) are introduced. This optimal configuration lies between what already noted by [Peverelli et al. \(2022a\)](#), and Hoover, with 300 and 700 respectively¹³. While Hoover's setting to 700 MFWs is easier to explain, as it deals with longer nineteenth-century fictional texts, the difference in the MFWs setting with our own experiment somewhat harder to pin down. This can be explained by the fact that: a) a large proportion of the texts present in our current corpus are generally longer than those used in our earlier experiment, and b) the overall size of the corpus is much larger. The main reason, however, is due to the fact that the previous work analysed four different subcorpora, each with its own language, a more limited time span and a smaller number of authors, resulting in a more compact and narrower base of MFWs. Our corpus is a corpus that we made monolingual, but remains very diverse at its base, with more authors, a longer time span and many more total texts: this causes a greater dispersion of the common lexical base among all the samples that make up the corpus (in other words: the base vocabulary within which the MFWs are selected by the algorithm is wider because the total number of texts is higher), and therefore requires a higher MFWs setting;

- The choice of clustering algorithm was Burrows' Classical Delta, calculated as the distance between two standard-deviation-normalised mean word frequencies¹⁴. This choice is in accordance with past scientific literature¹⁵, as was noted with regard to other common choices such as Cosine and Eder's Delta: 'Burrows' Delta is also confirmed to be better suited for shorter-vector corpora. Although Cosine measures are confirmed to outscore others, it is repeatedly stated that it depends on many factors, such as corpus selection, choice of MFWs, type of language and length of vectors. As we are looking for evidence that Cosine measures outscore other traditional measures even in shorter-vector literary texts with a lower selection of MFWs for tasks other than authorship attribution, we decided to use Burrows' Classic Delta.'¹⁶ Similarly, since our corpus consists of averagely short texts ('shorter-vector corpora'), and other measures such as Cosine have not yet been proved to be more effective on shorter texts, Classic Delta was our final choice;
- Contractions were not removed;
- Interjections and personal pronouns were not removed, as they are an important part of dramatic language;
- Maximum culling was set at 20%: a set of words must appear in at least 20% of a text, thus eliminating some background noise.

¹³Ibid., and Hoover (2004), pp. 453–75.

¹⁴See Argamon (2007), pp. 131–147.

¹⁵Borgeirsson (2018), pp. 1–18; Jannidis et al. (2015), pp. 1–10; Evert et al. (2015), pp. 79–88.

¹⁶Peverelli et al. (2022a), pp. 341–42.

The final set of parameters (CA_500_MFWs_Culled_20_Classic Delta) produced a cluster analysis, which was then visualised in Gephi, as a network of nodes (individual texts) and edges (similarity scores). Further network visualisations were created by applying colour-coded layers of metadata (following the different dimensions we mentioned earlier): the base network is the same in each visualisation, produced by our cluster analysis of stylistic similarities, but each new visualisation adds another layer of information on top of it, from which more insights can be gleaned to end up with a more complete outline of our corpus, and of general trends in early modern drama.

5.5 RESULTS

The results of our analysis are rich and varied. Below is a schematic report of the main dimensions, one for each network we created.

1) General Network and Publication Year Metadata Layer (figs. 5.3, 5.4)

Three well-defined distinct macro-clusters:

- The first large one on the left has Cellotius, Caussin and *Catharina* by Holonius as its main centres. It has a sub-cluster at the bottom, where the main connectors are Foxe, Simonides and Palsgrave. This macro-cluster contains only works from the 1600s, connected to its sub-cluster at the bottom, which is made up by mostly works from the 1500s. This re-confirms previous findings¹⁷ and the importance of the second-generation authors (mid-to-late 1500s) as a bridge and main source of inspiration;
- The second large macro-cluster on the right is the most mixed one, and the main connectors are Mussato, confirming his relative importance in the shaping of later early modern drama writing (as the first recorded Latin drama, written at the doors of the Italian Renaissance), and Balde, one of the most important authors of all early modern drama¹⁸. A subcluster at the bottom of this macro-cluster shows the *Hecastus* by Macropedius as an important pre-text and inspiration for many others. In terms of years, there are some more clearly defined sub-clusters, with a late 1500s–1600s cluster at the top and an early 1500s cluster at the bottom (concentrated around the 1530s and the 1540s), a large generation of writers whose main model is Macropedius;
- The last, smaller, macro-cluster is a very defined and separate one, which seems to contain mostly anonymous works and no connections with the other clusters whatsoever. In terms of years, it is mostly concentrated in the early 1500s, in the earliest decades of the whole network (1490s–1530s).

2) Religion Network (fig. 5.5)

The Catholic and Protestant sub-clusters stand out clearly (highlighted in the visualisation), while in the second large macro-cluster on the right they appear to be more mixed. Protestant authors appear to be more tightly clustered, but overall Catholics and Protestants mix well together, with Protestants (a numerical minority) found throughout each major cluster. As further insights are needed to reveal tendencies regarding the intersection between stylistic similarities and religious background, we refer to an additional network

¹⁷Peverelli et al. (2022a).

¹⁸See Bloemendal and Norland (2013), pp. 281–82.

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Figure 5.3: General stylistic similarities network visualisation

Figure 5.4: General stylistic similarities network visualisation with publication year metadata

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Figure 5.5: Network visualisation with religious background metadata. Catholic authors are highlighted in blue, Protestant ones in red and humanist-unaligned in green.

visualisation we produced using the in-degree coefficient. A phenomenon can be seen in the small isolated cluster at the bottom, which shows a more defined distribution: the few known Protestant authors in this isolated, mostly anonymous cluster have very strong connections within themselves, as do the anonymous authors among themselves, but they both show a clear tendency towards the only non-anonymous work, the *Homulus* by von Gennep, which serves as their main, central hub. This means that later works were inspired by it and the *Homulus* itself derived many of its main sources from earlier works, both of which mark it as a successful and highly connected drama.

3) Genre Network (fig. 5.6)

The sub-clusters are very clearly defined. The first large one on the left consists entirely of tragedies, with two outliers in the less easily identifiable unidentified plays of the *Philedonius* by van den Enden and the *De Iuventutis Institutione* by Bloemertius, which seem to share important stylistic features with conventional tragedy. Another sub-cluster of tragedy can be found in the upper right-hand corner, where the two works by Philicinus (*Esther* and *Magdalena*) are the connectors with a large sub-cluster of comedy below. This same sub-cluster, made up mainly of comedies, shows two peculiar phenomena, the first of which will be central to the next analysis:

- The most important model (i.e. the node with the greatest number and highest strength of connections) is the *Mercator* of Naogeorgus, a tragedy. This may be explained by the fact that Naogeorgus is the advocate of a ‘new tragedy’ that ‘breaks with the rules of classical drama’¹⁹;
- Two of the identifiable tragicomedies in our corpus are found in this sub-cluster, revealing a style more akin to a comedy than a tragedy, while Crucius’ *Prodigus* is found in the comedy cluster at the bottom.

The second comedy sub-cluster is found at the bottom left, unrelated to the other comedies and containing one lone comedy, Crocus’ *Ioseph*. Finally, the usual separate sub-cluster at the bottom right is made up of the bulk of unknown and not easily identifiable moral/didactic plays with some comedies, marking their stylistic proximity to comedy much more than to tragedy.

4) Place of Publication Network and Religion Network Overlaps (fig. 5.7)

For this metadata layer, we created a different visualisation, an in-degree network which shows the in-going edges pointing towards the most influential works (again, colour coded). This graph reveals some further insights, when combined with the previous findings:

- The first macro-cluster in the middle corresponds to texts from the 1600s only, with a core of French Catholic works and a constellation of Catholic and Protestant authors from the Low Countries. Again, the absolute centrality of Cellotius and Caussin is evident. This shows the relative importance of French-published drama in the 1600s for the Catholic community in Europe;

¹⁹See Cora Dietl, ‘Neo-Latin Humanist and Protestant Drama in Germany’, in Bloemendal and Norland (2013), p. 150.

Figure 5.6: Network visualisation with genre metadata. Tragedies are highlighted in lilac, comedies in green, tragicomedies in light blue and unidentified plays in orange.

Figure 5.7: In-degree network visualisation with place of publication and religious background metadata. Colour coding: Catholic - Low Countries (lilac), Catholic - Germany (green), Catholic - France (black), Protestant - Low Countries (light blue), Protestant – Germany (orange), Protestant- Switzerland (blue-green), unaligned (bright pink).

- The second cluster on the left shows two phenomena: on the one hand, there is the core of Dutch Protestant authors from the late 1500s to the early 1600s such as Heinsius, Grotius and Zevecotius, connected to the previous cluster through Honerdus, who forms an important hub. The rest of this cluster, on the other hand, is dominated by the Catholic triad of Balde, Roulerius and Philicinus, with Balde again emerging as one of the most important hubs. Stylistically, while Catholic authors again seem to be more compact, imitating and reusing mainly among themselves, Protestant authors seem to be freer to choose more diverse sources as inspiration, often finding it in Catholics: for example, Honerdus appears to be the main stylistic link between Catholic French drama and his Dutch Protestant colleagues, while Grotius shows strong connections with Catholic authors from both the Low Countries and Germany, and Zevecotius has his main links with Catholic French dramatists. As a final aside, the Catholic playwright Philicinus, despite his biography, surprisingly, does not seem to be connected with French authors at all: his stylistic inspiration seems to be found in German dramatists, both Catholic and Protestant;
- The third cluster at the top is more mixed in terms of place of publication, with Catholic and Protestant writers from both Germany and the Low Countries, but it is again dominated by Catholic German authors, the triad of Crucius, Bidermann and Diether, which has already identified as an important hub of reuse (strong in-degree stylistically and connecting clusters together) in our ‘Process of imitation’ experiment. The works in this cluster are all from the mid-1500s, reconfirming their stylistic unity and the extensive dialogue (even crossing religious boundaries) of authors from this ‘second generation’ of early modern drama writers²⁰;
- The fourth cluster at the bottom shows a fairly high degree of homogeneity, consisting for the most part of Dutch Catholic authors from the mid to late 1500s, with Macropedius as an earlier exception. The vast majority of post-1540 works are united by one peculiar aspect: having the *Mercator* by Naogeorgus (a Protestant from Germany, but published in Switzerland) as their main source of inspiration, marking it as one of the most influential dramas of the 16th century. This is explainable by the fact that Naogeorgus himself, although he started as a Protestant, ‘does not identify with any of the Protestant subgroups and their teaching’²¹, and is thus a much more nuanced author than he seemed to be, who suited Catholic playwrights. As a further consideration, it is worth noting that the *Mercator* is part of the same tradition of Everyman plays, which in turn showed a complete extraneity to the rest of the corpus. Not only the *Mercator* is showing completely different behaviours to other Everyman dramas, but, unique in its kind, it even resulted as one of the most influential plays in early modern theatre. Finding possible explanations to this notable exception is a matter that is out of the scope of this article and a challenge for future inquiries.

5) Theme Network (fig. 5.8)

Thematically, the network is divided into several well-defined sub-clusters.

- Biblical drama sub-cluster on the left, which has strong ties with religious and morality dramas;
- Joseph plays and Prodigal Son plays form a sub-cluster at the bottom and mix well with

²⁰See Jan Bloemendal, ‘Neo-Latin Drama in the Low Countries’, in *Bloemendal and Norland (2013)*, pp. 332–42.

²¹Dietl, ‘Neo-Latin Humanist and Protestant Drama in Germany’, p. 150.

Figure 5.8: Network visualisation of main themes metadata. Colour coding: Biblical drama (lilac), Historical drama (green), Religious drama (orange), Morality/didactic (dark blue), Joseph plays (black), Everyman plays (light blue), Prodigal son plays (red).

each other. Joseph plays also form a smaller sub-cluster at the top and seem to have more mixed connections with other historical, Biblical and religious dramas;

- Another smaller Biblical drama sub-cluster on the right, showing strong ties with morality plays and Macropedius' *Hecastus*, again confirming its stylistic importance for later works.
- Historical drama sub-cluster at the top that shows strong links with Biblical drama;
- The Everyman theme, as seen earlier, is the more separate and cohesive, forming a sub-cluster at the bottom right with no ties to others. Three works stand out in this cluster, making them the central hubs for the Everyman theme: *Homulus* by von Gennep and the anonymous duo of the *Homulus Comoedia* and the *De Dïdesche Schlömer*.

6) Investigating the Whole Picture: Year, Religion, Genre, Theme

At this point, multiple layers of metadata have been analysed. By merging them all together we can draw some initial conclusions:

- The first macro-cluster on the left is made up exclusively of Catholic French and Dutch writers from the 1600s, marking them as highly cohesive in terms of style. Theme is not a distinguishing element here, as this cluster is the most diverse, with authors tackling almost every major theme in our spectrum;
- The smaller sub-cluster on the right comprises a tight group of mainly Catholic Dutch playwrights of the 'second generation' (mid to late 1500s), who have a unified and characteristic style. They also deal mainly with Biblical drama and morality plays, and include the only instances of named Everyman plays;
- The other smaller sub-cluster on the top right, connected to the previous one, consists of mixed German and Dutch, Protestant and Catholic writers from the late 1500s to the mid-1600s, dealing with mixed Biblical drama and historical drama;
- As an addendum, the previous sub-cluster (late 1500s to early 1600s) and the first macro-cluster on the left (1600s) are the main ones, showing historical and religious/Biblical drama. This marks the turn of the century, which was marked by a decisive new interest in historical and contemporary political issues, often mixed with religion;²²
- The third smaller sub-cluster on the far left is the most diverse in terms of places and religion, including both Catholics and Protestants from Germany, the Low Countries, Switzerland and even the only instances of England and Poland in our corpus. Instead, they are linked by two other factors: theme (the Prodigal Son and Joseph dramas, which are concentrated here) and year, as they represent the vast majority of the 'second generation' of dramatists (mid to late 1500s). This generation of writers, more than any other in our corpus displays a high degree of stylistic unity that transcends boundaries of nationality and confession;
- Finally, the usually separate sub-corpus on the lower right has the most unified and characteristic set of features: all instances are of mostly unknown Everyman plays from the late 1400s to the early 1500s, from Germany and the Low Countries, with no clear religious affiliation.

7) Hubs of Reuse (fig. 5.9)

²²Andrea Peverelli, Marieke van Erp and Jan Bloemendal, 'Tracing Themes and Topics in Neo-Latin Drama through Topic Modelling and Word Embeddings' (submitted).

Figure 5.9: In-degree network visualisation of stylistic similarities with highlighted influential hubs (higher in-degree values being shown as closer to red, and lower as closer to blue).

Finally, following the same in-degree visualisation of the place-of-publication + religious-background metadata layer, we can analyse a network that more clearly shows which author-texts serve as the main hubs of reuse, marking them as the most important centrepieces of our stylistic imitation network of early modern drama. These are:

1. Cellotius, the author with the absolute highest in-degree edges of the network, marking him as one of the most important authors, especially in the Catholic community of the 1600s;
2. *Iephtias* – Balde, the second most influential work in our network, another important model for mixed Protestant and Catholic authors from different countries, making it an important trans-national, cross-religious hub;
3. *Mercator* – Naogeorgus, a work by a Protestant author which proves to be very influential for a large number of Catholic Dutch authors of the so-called ‘second generation’ of playwrights (mid to late 1500s);
4. *Hecastus* – Macropedius, another highly influential drama in the same cluster as Naogeorgus;
5. *Prodigus* – Crucius / *Joseph* – Diether, a duo of German authors who mark the beginning and end of the ‘second generation’ of playwrights (1540s–early 1600s).

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5.6 CONCLUSION

From our analysis, many aspects stand out. As a general consideration stemming from the discussion of the last results (‘7. Hubs of reuse’), the fact that 4 out of 6 of the most important hubs are from the ‘second generation’ of playwrights and 2 are from the mid-1600s, shows several crucial aspects:

- It reaffirms the relative importance of the ‘second generation’ playwrights, especially Catholic Dutch authors (3 out of 4 hubs), in shaping later drama;
- Secondly, the early authors in the network seem to be less important in later stages, and only show connections within themselves. This reconfirms one of the findings of the ‘The Process of imitatio’ experiment, which, in a much more limited corpus, disclosed a T-SA (Temporal-Spatial Attractiveness) phenomenon: earlier authors in the network are more tightly clustered together, with high imitation between them, but then they lose importance for later authors, giving way to the much more influential ‘second generation’ of dramatists. Thus, writers from the late 1500s onwards tend to prefer authors closer in time as their models, rather than going back to earlier writers (Temporal Attractiveness);
- As for later authors, hubs are less sparse and concentrate around two authors who form the absolute highest in-degree nodes of the entire network. What is even more surprising is that these two, Cellotius and Balde, two real stars of early modern drama, remained nameless and anonymous for a long time, until collections of their works were published and their names were mentioned for the first time. This, again, tells us something about the problematic concept of author and authorship in early modern drama.

Some more important considerations can be summarised:

- In terms of religion, Catholic authors, with the exception of the only outlier of the *Mercator* of Naogeorgus, are a more stylistically compact and solid group, imitating almost exclusively among themselves; Protestant authors show a much greater variety in their

choice of models, often Catholic models. This is confirmed by two of our recent studies²³, where it is shown, by means of Machine Learning text classification for the former and a mixture of topic modelling and word embeddings for the latter, that the language behind Protestant authors shows less defined and strong features than that used by Catholic authors. This is supported by the fact that the vast majority of Catholic authors in our corpus are Jesuits, who ‘were bound to the ideological rules of the Order. [...] The consequence is that Jesuit theatre is a cultural product that, notwithstanding the artistic peculiarity of individual works, hardly expresses positions accounted for by individual authors. This theatre is derived far more from a uniform spirit and serves collective spiritual and, at the same time, politico-religious requirements of the age.’²⁴ This makes their style more compact and defined as a whole, whereas the fact that the style of Protestant authors is more varied and less defined can be explained by various factors. One could point at the Reformation’s emphasis on individuality and critical thinking, which made Protestant authors more free in their choice of models, but we must also consider more material explanations. The institutional context between the two confessions was very different: the institutions behind Protestant authors (and thus the occasion for writing a play) were much more diverse than in the case of Catholic writers. The Protestants were thus more independent than the Jesuits, who had to follow a strict set of rules and guidelines, both in the writing of dramas and in the occasions on which plays were commissioned.

- The Everyman plays cluster, which remained separate throughout every analysis, has strongly defined characteristics that make it an outlier in the overall network. These mostly lesser known works from Germany and the Low Countries, spanning a period of forty years, seem to show a similar historical and literary development, with heavy reuse between each other; though mostly by unknown writers, a high degree of reuse between each of these works suggests that their authors knew, read and imitated each other extensively.
- The transnational aspect of drama is strongly evident: interreligious dialogue, works and authors linked between different countries and even ages are present at every level of our corpus.
- Finally, our initial aim is demonstrated: stylistic similarities are given new interpretations in the light of their external factors working in the background, through layers of metadata, revealing peculiar phenomena and tendencies.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the value of combining stylometric analysis with metadata overlays to uncover nuanced stylistic patterns within early modern drama. By considering both internal textual features and external factors such as religious background, geographical location, and thematic content, we provide a more comprehensive understanding of how these dramas circulated and influenced each other across national and confessional boundaries. The integration of digital tools and historical context not only reveals stylistic connections, but also highlights the importance of transnational literary exchange in shaping the early modern literary landscape. This multifaceted approach offers new insights into the complexity of early modern drama and lays the groundwork for future

²³Andrea Peverelli, Marieke van Erp and Jan Bloemendal, ‘Tracing Themes and Topics in Neo-Latin Drama through Topic Modelling and Word Embeddings’ (submitted), and id. ‘When a Catholic Comedy looks like a Protestant Tragedy: Predicting Religious and Genre Features in Neo-Latin Drama’ (submitted).

²⁴Rädle, ‘Jesuit Theatre in Germany, Austria and Switzerland’, p. 187.

research on stylistic evolution and cross-cultural literary interactions. In terms of future research, there is still a great deal of work to be done to gain a full understanding of early modern drama production. The process of digitising early modern texts is still ongoing, and only a fraction of what we know is currently available in machine-readable form. These analyses and their results can capture trends and patterns that confirm earlier, even smaller, studies, but these will need to be definitively confirmed by later research that can draw on a more complete corpus. With the exciting prospect of a much larger, multilingual corpus of early modern drama comes new methodological perspectives. Algorithms designed to handle larger datasets, such as deep learning models, could improve accuracy and reveal previously unseen patterns. For example, neural network models could help to automatically extract semantic features such as word usage and stylistic preferences across clusters of authors, providing a richer understanding of the linguistic and thematic development of early modern drama.

6

CONCLUSION

Summary. In the Introduction I formulated two research questions concerning the mapping and quantification of networks of textual similarities, and the quantification of internal and external stylistic elements respectively. These questions framed not only the specific analyses undertaken in each chapter but also the broader aims of this dissertation: to challenge and refine our understanding of early modern drama through computational approaches. By combining quantitative and qualitative perspectives, this thesis bridges methodological innovation and literary history, offering new tools to uncover stylistic patterns, thematic trends, and transnational connections that traditional methods have overlooked. The first research question is addressed in Chapters 1 and 2 of the dissertation, in which I analyse the style of early modern playwrights from an "internal" point of view, that is the raw similarities between textual segments both within early modern dramas and between them and their classical models. The second question is answered in Chapters 3 and 4, where I deal with style as a product of "external" elements such as background, time and place of publication, genre and religious affiliation. Chapter 5 serves as a summarising study that follows both lines of research: using a larger corpus, I produce an analysis of both raw overlaps and similarities between texts and the complex layers of metadata that make up the constellation of external elements in my collection. The availability of a larger dataset allowed me to replicate results from the initial experiments, confirming the generalisability and efficacy of my approach.

6.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS REVISITED

In what follows, I will re-propose the research questions and analyse in depth how they have been answered in the chapters of this thesis.

My first research question was: *How can the extensive network of stylistic textual similarities within early modern drama be mapped and quantified through computational means?* The answer, as demonstrated in Chapters 1 and 2, is that computational methods can efficiently map these stylistic networks by identifying clusters of influence around key authors and their classical models. These methods reveal consistent patterns of similarity that map both internal connections among early modern dramas and their links to classical texts, and offer insights into how early modern dramatists adapted and reinterpreted classical and contemporary sources. By quantifying these dynamics, my research contributes a data-driven perspective on the stylistic evolution of early modern drama. Through these chapters,

I illustrate how early modern dramatists transitioned from reliance on temporally closer, time-bound models to broader stylistic experimentation. This computational approach thus maps and quantifies evolving stylistic preferences, providing a framework for examining how early modern dramatists reinterpreted each other's works and classical influences.

Chapter 1, "Tracking Textual Similarities", in particular, addresses the issue of emerging clusters of influential authors and their evolution over time. It proposes an analysis on a limited corpus of Neo-Latin texts and their classical models, highlighting patterns of similarities within the corpus. Using cosine similarity and stylometric techniques, I discovered that Neo-Latin drama follows the same pattern of evolution and similarity as real-world datasets of stories (Karsdorp and van den Bosch (2016)). Specifically, I observed a similar "S-TA/MA" model, with early authors favouring models close in time and space (*spatial-temporal attractiveness*), but later embrace a wider range of stylistic influences (*modal attractiveness*). Furthermore, I found that this evolutionary pattern in early modern Neo-Latin drama is modelled around "hubs of re-use", particularly important authors or clusters of authors around whom the others in the corpus are strongly connected. In particular, these hubs of re-use have been identified in authors belonging to the so-called "second generation" of early modern writers (Foxe, Diether, Schonaeus), between the mid and the late 16th century and already identified by traditional literary studies (Bloemendal and Norland (2013) as a crucial turning point in the development of Neo-Latin drama. Finally, another important aspect stood out in regards to imitation and re-use between early modern drama and their classical models: although regularly cited by many early modern authors, my analysis showed the complete stylistic extraneity of Plautus from the Neo-Latin corpus, while also highlighting a clear-cut preference for Terence in the 16th century and for Seneca in the 17th century. This shows clear preferences for the imitation of certain classical models over others with clear, data-driven evidence that is also supported by the current state of qualitative research.

Chapter 2, "The Process of Imitatio through Stylometric Analysis: the Case of Terence's *Eunuchus*", shows that computational methods can reveal points of influence within texts, providing a nuanced answer to the question of how textual similarities can be mapped within literary tradition, particularly in regards to classical imitation. Prompted by the results of the first experiment, I delved deeper into the relationship between Neo-Latin writers and their models, found in the classics. One particular text stood out as major source of reception for Neo-Latin authors: the *Eunuchus* by Terence. This prompted a stylometric analysis of this work across four corpora — Neo-Latin (the basis for the experiment), Italian, French, and English (the corpus to be used as a confirmation or refutation of the findings). On the one hand, I used translations of the *Eunuchus* into non-Latin languages and produced clustering visualisations for each corpus to determine the importance of Terence for each. On the other hand, I generated a custom analysis and visualisation to precisely pinpoint the *loci* of re-use of the *Eunuchus* in Neo-Latin dramas, highlighting the exact points in the Terentian text where early modern authors either performed imitation or diverged stylistically from their classical model. This experiment achieved two goals. From a methodological point of view, I devised an approach to multi-language stylistic analysis of historical texts through translations, with potential applications to any other genre and period. Conversely, regarding the imitation of classics, I provided data-driven evidence that confirmed or contradicted assumptions of previous traditional literary studies for Italian, French and English drama production (for example demonstrating the complete extraneity of Terentian style from

Shakespeare, despite his texts being rife with Terentian characters). Finally, my analysis revealed the systematic nature of classical imitation in early modern drama. I have been able to identify on an act-scene basis the *loci* of re-use by Neo-Latin authors, demonstrating a clear pattern of imitation and a preference for certain parts of the *Eunuchus*. By quantifying the frequency and distribution of these reuses, I established an approach to identify the degree of imitation of early modern authors with classical sources. The detailed mapping I produced shows that these re-uses are not random but part of quantifiable patterns that vary significantly between authors, offering new insights into how early modern authors re-interpret specific scenes from classical sources to align with their stylistic or thematic priorities. This approach reinforces a dynamic notion of literary tradition instead of a static one, where imitation of the classics was not passive but a key driver of an author's style.

My initial proposition on the analysis of style prompted a series of considerations on how it is conceived and how it can be studied, while also proposing a sub-division: style as the sum of similarities and overlaps between textual segments (internal structure), and style as the constellation of contextual features that influence an author (external structure). While the previous two chapters of dissertation dealt mainly with the first aspect of internal structure by performing analyses on raw textual similarities and not involving any metadata, it was also important to analyse the complex constellation of metadata on external and contextual elements, especially genre and religious background, that shaped early modern drama. Hence, the second research question: *To what degree do internal and external factors of style interact, and how much do external elements influence style?*. The answer is that not only external factors, such as genre and religious background, indeed shape an author's style, but that this external influence can be quantified with great precision. My analysis not only allows for a deeper understanding of how external factors shape style, but also reveals the degree to which some of these features, such as religious affiliation and genre, influence specific linguistic choices and correlate to themes. Chapters 3 and 4 provide evidence for these interactions, illustrating how external factors guide key decisions in language choices.

In Chapter 3, "Tracing Themes and Topics through Topic Modelling and Word Embeddings", I apply a mixture of topic modelling and word embeddings to an extended early modern Neo-Latin corpus, with the aim of analysing two crucial external aspects: genre and religious background. The topic modelling sub-experiment was able to capture patterns of preferences for specific topics that were linked to the choice of genre, and that were also linked to the chronological development of the corpus. First, the experiment largely confirmed the nature of literary genres, with comedies showing preference for joy, love and feast topics, and tragedies for crime, guilt and historical themes. I was also able to find other patterns that further the discussion of drama sub-genres. For example, the constant mixing of religious and historical topics on kings, princes and rulers, that shows a specific world-view, or the curious phenomenon of the 1620s: first noted in the Neo-Latin corpus and then re-confirmed in another Italian drama corpus of the same era, around the 1620s we note a steep increase in topics relating to religion, crime and guilt and a complete stop of addressing the themes of joy, love, feast and family. This phenomenon could be a reflection in literature of the deterioration of relations between Catholics and Protestants or the outbreak of the Thirty Years War, and confirming the great importance of external features on the style of authors. This discovery highlights the potential of Digital Humanities approaches in

traditional literary studies. Computational approaches can not only confirm and quantify general intuitions but also reveal latent patterns that have escaped conventional close-reading methods. The second part of the experiment, which involved word embeddings, produced coherent and distinctive results on the aspect of religious background and its influence on early modern writers: I was able to pinpoint with a high precision (between 0.83 and 0.93 scores) clusters of embedded words that showed a clear connection with either Catholic or Protestant theology, demonstrating that religious affiliation does indeed show through even in dramas and shapes the writing preferences of authors. My analysis thus reveals that certain genres are consistently correlated with certain thematic choices and their associated word choices, while religious background introduces distinct theological language and viewpoints into drama. This therefore relates to the original research question by demonstrating that external factors are integrated into style, and that an author's genre and religious affiliation can be as influential as internal stylistic elements in defining their work.

Chapter 4, "Predicting Religious and Genre Features", complements the previous ones by designing an unsupervised approach through Machine Learning algorithms to automatically identify features of genre (comedy, tragedy and their sacred variants) and religious background (Protestant and Catholic) that contribute to the shaping of early modern texts. By first analysing the misclassifications of features, in the case of genre, I was able to draw a schematic pattern based on the hybridisation of sub-genres (how much a class was mistaken for another), with tragedy being the most stable and all other sub-genres tending very strongly towards it. This shows a higher stylistic coherence in tragedy, which is used as a model by authors even in other genres. In terms of religious background, I also found that some classes (the religious denominations I took into consideration) tend to be more unstable than others. Protestant authors had a much higher misclassification rate, often being identified as Catholic: this shows that Protestant authors have a less identifiable and stable style than their counterpart. Finally, I proposed a new method of feature classification based on the chosen best performing algorithm used in the experiment, Logistic Regression. The result of this method is a table that shows raw values and a positive/negative distinction based on how distinctive or non-distinctive a specific word is to either denomination (Protestant and Catholic in my case). In this way, I was again able to identify the most important religion-related word choices authors make in their texts and to show that they clearly reflect either Catholic or Protestant early modern theology, demonstrating the high impact of religious background on their writing.

Chapter 5, "A Stylometric and Network Analysis of a Multi-lingual Corpus", constitutes a follow-up to the previous chapters, completing the analysis and adding further evidence to answer my two research questions. More importantly, it reveals patterns of influence and stylistic imitation that transcend conventional categorisations of genre, religious background, and national traditions. These findings challenge existing narratives, highlighting transnational networks of exchange and stylistic hybridity that demand further historical and cultural exploration. This chapter synthesises the findings of Chapters 1 to 4 to demonstrate that both internal and external factors work in tandem to define early modern drama. By integrating stylistic clustering with metadata, this chapter addresses both research questions in a unified framework, by demonstrating that literary networks are shaped by external factors interacting with internal stylistic similarities, and that the influence of contextual

elements strongly correlates to an author's style. When designing this last experiment, a specific aspect of stylistic analysis still posed problems: while stylistic similarities between authors can reveal meaningful connections, their significance becomes much clearer when contextualised with external metadata. If we superimpose knowledge of external features on a link between two texts, for example by introducing their genre, religious background and year of publication, this leads to a much more informed interpretation of their connection. With this premise in mind, I collected a large corpus of early modern dramas in multiple languages, translated them into modern English using GPT's API, and analysed both their raw stylistic similarities and key metadata elements such as publication details, main themes, religious background, and genre. By adding the metadata layers to the stylistic clustering analysis, I was able to confirm conclusions previously drawn from much smaller corpora and to reveal a large number of similarity and dissimilarity patterns that were not previously apparent. I was able to identify the same findings of Chapter 1, with a T-SA evolutionary pattern and the central role of the "second generation" of early modern dramatists. I confirmed again, from a third methodological approach, that Catholic authors show a much more compact style, with very strong links only between themselves, whereas Protestant authors often show connections either with other Protestants or Catholics. The analysis also revealed the importance of a selection of Dutch and German playwrights, as well as a core of French Catholic dramatists, to playwrights from across Europe. This also revealed, with data-driven analyses, the transnational aspect of early modern drama, which transcended religious affiliation and national boundaries. More strikingly, a phenomenon was noticed: a single work, the *Mercator* by Naogeorgus, who initially was Protestant, was found to be the major model of a dense cluster of Catholic authors. Moreover, his *Mercator* belongs to the tradition of "Everyman plays": uniquely, all other Everyman dramas consistently formed a cluster on their own, with no connection to any other drama in the corpus. We can only guess at the reasons for this discrepancy between *Mercator* and the other plays in the Everyman cluster. This and other previous findings I have highlighted invite further investigation. However, it is crucial to reiterate that this thesis does not aim to provide such interpretative or historical explanations, as its primary focus lies in addressing methodological questions and demonstrating the capabilities of computational approaches. Chapter 5 presented findings on patterns of similarities, clusters interacting with each other, and the emergence of clear hubs of re-use: these give us a more complete overview of early modern drama production, furthering the discussion on the relations between authors of the *Respublica Literaria*.

As a final consideration, these findings illustrate the dual value of computational approaches to the study of literature: they confirm and refine existing knowledge while also uncovering unexpected patterns that challenge established assumptions. For example, drawing from the four cases I cited, the stylistic absence of Plautus from Neo-Latin drama, despite his frequent citation, complicates traditional views of his influence. Similarly, Shakespeare's stylistic disconnection from Terence, despite clear thematic borrowing, repositions our understanding of his classical inspirations. The 1620s thematic shift toward crime, guilt, and religious topics underscores the profound impact of historical events on literary production, revealing a phenomenon that had previously escaped scholarly attention. Moreover, patterns such as the stylistic fluidity of Protestant dramatists, or the centrality of Naogeorgus' *Mercator* as a trans-national hub of reuse reflect the dynamic interplay between literary traditions across national and denominational boundaries. These findings demonstrate that the compu-

tational tools I employed in my dissertation are not just supplementary methods; they are essential for rethinking the scope and complexity of literary networks, enabling scholars to engage with both familiar and overlooked texts in innovative ways. Ultimately, my approach not only refines literary history but also highlights how computational approaches function as a "macroscope," capable of uncovering patterns and connections that are invisible to traditional close reading.

6.2 FUTURE WORK

"We have work to do"

Saruman the White, The Lord of the Rings movies, The Fellowship of the Ring.

As demonstrated throughout this dissertation, Digital Humanities methods not only confirm received knowledge, but also refine it, offering precise measures of previously unknown granularity that allow for detailed comparisons across authors and texts. These methods challenge us to rethink the way literary history is written by moving beyond generalisations to reveal patterns of imitation, influence, and stylistic evolution with exceptional clarity. Additionally, Digital Humanities approaches have uncovered unexpected patterns and phenomena that had previously escaped the attention of historians and literary scholars. These findings, while methodologically robust, now call for culturally, politically, and religiously informed contextual analyses by future literary historians to fully interpret their implications.

The first natural development, as far as future work is concerned, is the expansion of the corpus. With the last chapter, I gathered a corpus of nearly 700,000 words carefully curated to represent the diversity of early modern drama. This corpus captures the main known strands of genres, geographical regions and religious affiliations, making it representative of the major trends and features of early modern drama production. However, early modern drama encompasses a vast body of works, many of which remain undigitised or inaccessible for computational analysis. Expanding the corpus to include these additional texts would enhance its representativeness and allow for a broader validation of current findings, but increasing the size of the dataset is not without challenges. A larger corpus introduces variability in style, language, and metadata, requiring careful adjustment of pre-processing pipelines, such as tokenisation, lemmatisation, and feature selection, to ensure compatibility with existing methods. Additionally, clustering algorithms would need to be re-calibrated to account for new dimensions, ensuring that patterns observed in a smaller dataset remain interpretable at scale. These adjustments may involve testing alternative similarity measures, optimising dimensionality reduction techniques, or retraining machine learning models to adapt to the increased heterogeneity of the data. This process, while time-consuming, can effectively provide new insights and new evidence that scholars of traditional humanities could not previously glean. Early modern drama production is known to be massive, with at least a thousand texts still lying untouched or un-digitised in libraries. Projects such as DraCor¹ and TransLatin² have made progress in the endeavour of collecting, digitising and publishing data on drama, but much still remains to be done.

Furthermore, we still need to fully exploit the power of AI and Large Language Models (LLM) in literary analysis. Although this project started before the widespread success

¹<https://dracor.org/>

²<https://translatin.nl/>

of LLMs, I briefly touched upon one of their possible uses. Nonetheless, the prospects remain vast. One promising direction is that of AI-trained LLM algorithms capable of handling large quantities of data and generative models specifically tuned to identify and interpret nuanced patterns of stylistic evolution and imitation within the corpus. These models can go beyond current methods by not only clustering and identifying similarities but also simulating the stylistic transitions that authors undergo over time, allowing researchers to track how influence, genre, and cultural shifts manifest themselves in evolving literary styles.

Another significant aspect of future work could be to develop a more interactive, visual analysis tool that allows scholars to dynamically engage with the data. Interactive clustering visualisations incorporating metadata would allow users to explore specific relationships between texts, authors, genres, and historical contexts. Such tools could broaden access to this complex data, and enable other researchers to use it in different academic contexts.

Finally, future work could integrate multi-modal data, including illustrations, stage directions, and performance-related documents, to enrich our understanding of early modern drama. While my dissertation has focused exclusively on textual analysis, early modern dramas were often accompanied by visual and performative elements that provide essential context. By expanding the corpus to include visual or material culture artefacts related to these texts, it may be possible to trace patterns not only in language and style but also in theatrical representation and iconography.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

- Andrea Peverelli, 2025. A Stylometric and Network Analysis of a Multi-lingual Early Modern Drama Corpus. To be published in: D. Wouters and J. Bloemendal (eds.), *The Transnational Impact of Latin Theatre: Qualitative and Computational Analyses* (Leiden: Brill, in preparation)
- Andrea Peverelli, Marieke van Erp, Jan Bloemendal, 2025 (Under review at *DHQ, Digital Humanities Quarterly Journal*). Tracing Themes and Topics in Neo-Latin Drama through Topic Modelling and Word Embeddings.
- Andrea Peverelli, Marieke van Erp, Jan Bloemendal, 2024. When a Catholic Comedy looks like a Protestant Tragedy: Predicting Religious and Genre Features in Neo-Latin Drama.
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APPENDIX

All texts used in this dissertation are available in a curated GitHub repository at: <https://github.com/AndrewPeverells/Translatin>.

SAMENVATTING

Dit proefschrift onderzoekt de stilistische en intertekstuele dynamiek van vroegmoderne Neolatijnse drama's door middel van computationele analyse. Neolatijnse toneelstukken, geschreven en opgevoerd in Europa van de 15e tot de 18e eeuw, speelden een cruciale rol in het humanistische onderwijs en de intellectuele uitwisseling. Geschreven in het Latijn – een taal die nationale en confessionele grenzen overstijgt – vormden deze stukken een internationaal literair netwerk dat diepgaand werd beïnvloed door klassieke imitatie, religieuze overtuiging en pedagogische functie. Ondanks hun historische belang blijven Neolatijnse drama's grotendeels onderbelicht in de literatuurwetenschap, mede door hun omvangrijke en verspreide corpus.

Deze studie hanteert een gemengde methodologie, waarbij traditionele literatuurtheorie wordt gecombineerd met computationele methoden zoals stylometrie, netwerkanalyse, Natural Language Processing (NLP) en machine learning. De onderzoeksvragen zijn: (1) het traceren van patronen van tekstuele gelijkenis en invloed tussen verschillende auteurs en periodes; (2) het onderzoeken van de impact van religieuze en culturele contexten op stilistische keuzes; en (3) het ontwikkelen van een schaalbaar, datagestuurd analysekader voor de studie van Neolatijnse literatuur.

Het proefschrift is opgebouwd rond een aantal casestudy's. Eerst worden stilistische ontlening en imitatie onderzocht, met name in de mate waarin vroegmoderne dramaturgen zich oriënteerden op klassieke auctoritates zoals Terentius, Plautus en Seneca. Een combinatie van stylometrische analyse en netwerkvisualisatie toont aan hoe bepaalde auteurs en stukken fungeerden als centrale knooppunten binnen een evoluerende compositietraditie. Vervolgens wordt de wisselwerking tussen genre en confessionele identiteit besproken, waarbij onder meer topic modelling, woordvectoren en voorspellende tekstclassificatie worden gebruikt om te laten zien hoe katholieke en protestantse toneelschrijvers elk hun eigen linguïstische en thematische conventies ontwikkelden. Tot slot plaatst dit onderzoek het Neolatijnse drama binnen een bredere Europese literaire context, en wordt aangetoond hoe Latijnstalige toneelstukken interactie vertoonden met de volkstalige tradities.

De bevindingen dragen bij aan meerdere vakgebieden, waaronder de receptiegeschiedenis van de klassieken, de vroegmoderne literatuurgeschiedenis en de Digital Humanities. De resultaten tonen aan dat stilistische gelijkenissen tussen stukken niet louter chronologisch of geografisch verklaard kunnen worden, maar eerder voortkomen uit confessionele en institutionele verbanden. Protestantse dramaturgen vertonen grotere stilistische variatie, terwijl jezuïetenauteurs zich houden aan een meer gestandaardiseerde taalregister. Ook blijken er discrepanties te bestaan tussen expliciete literaire theorie en het daadwerkelijke schrijfgebruik: hoewel veel auteurs Plautus als voorbeeld noemden, toont computationele analyse sterkere stilistische overeenkomsten met Terentius en Seneca. Bovendien brengt netwerkanalyse de transnationale aard van het Neolatijnse drama in kaart: stukken circuleerden wijdverspreid over Europa, en overstegen soms religieuze grenzen. Sommige auteurs en werken blijken invloedrijke knooppunten te zijn geweest, die stilistische trends

in uiteenlopende regio's bepaalden. Stylometrie toont aan dat confessionele identiteit terug te vinden is in linguïstische keuzes op een fijnmazig niveau, met subtiele maar consistente stilistische verschillen tussen katholieke en protestantse auteurs. Tenslotte onthult de analyse onverwachte intertekstuele relaties tussen auteurs met sterk verschillende achtergronden, maar opvallend verwante stijkenmerken.

Door digitale methoden te combineren met close reading biedt dit proefschrift een herhaalbaar model voor grootschalig literair onderzoek. Het daagt bestaande narratieven over vroegmodern toneel uit door de complexiteit van het Neolatijnse literaire netwerk te tonen, en laat zien hoe computationele technieken verborgen patronen aan het licht kunnen brengen. Uiteindelijk onderstreept dit onderzoek de noodzaak om Neolatijns drama opnieuw te beschouwen als een dynamisch en invloedrijk onderdeel van de vroegmoderne Europese literatuur.

SUMMARY

This dissertation investigates the stylistic and intertextual dynamics of early modern Neo-Latin drama through computational analysis. Neo-Latin plays, composed and performed across Europe from the 15th to the 18th century, played a crucial role in humanist education and intellectual exchange. Written in Latin - a language that transcended national and confessional boundaries -, these plays formed an international literary network shaped and deeply influenced by classical imitation, religious affiliation, and pedagogical function. Despite their historical significance, Neo-Latin dramas remain underexplored in literary studies, partly due to their vast and dispersed corpus.

This study applies a mixed-method approach, combining traditional literary theory with computational methodologies such as Stylometry, Network Analysis, Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Machine Learning. The research aims to: (1) trace patterns of textual similarity and influence across different playwrights and time periods; (2) examine the impact of religious and cultural contexts on stylistic choices; and (3) develop a scalable, data-driven framework for the analysis of Neo-Latin literature.

The dissertation is structured around key case studies. It first examines stylistic borrowing and imitation, assessing the extent to which early modern dramatists engaged with classical auctoritates like Terence, Plautus, and Seneca. A combination of stylometric analysis and network visualisation reveals how certain authors and plays functioned as central hubs within an evolving tradition of dramatic composition. The study then addresses the intersection of genre and confessional identity, using Topic Modelling, Word Embeddings and predictive text categorisation to demonstrate how Catholic and Protestant dramatists developed distinct linguistic and thematic conventions. Finally, the research situates Neo-Latin drama within a broader European literary ecosystem, showing how Latin-language plays interacted with vernacular traditions.

The findings contribute to several fields, including classical reception studies, early modern literary history, and Digital Humanities. The results indicate that stylistic similarities between plays do not simply follow chronological or geographical proximity but are influenced by confessional and institutional affiliations. Protestant dramatists exhibit greater stylistic variability, whereas Jesuit playwrights adhere to a more standardised linguistic register. The study also reveals discrepancies between explicit literary theory and actual writing practices: while many playwrights cited Plautus as a key model, computational analysis suggests a stronger alignment with Terentian and Senecan stylistic features. Additionally, network analysis uncovers how Neo-Latin drama functioned as a transnational literary phenomenon, with plays circulating widely across Europe, sometimes transcending religious divisions. Certain playwrights and works emerge as crucial “hubs” of influence, shaping stylistic trends across different regions and time periods. Stylometric analysis further demonstrates that confessional identity is embedded in linguistic choices at a granular level, revealing subtle but consistent stylistic distinctions between Catholic and Protestant dramatists. Finally, the study highlights the importance of hidden intertextual relation-

ships: computational analysis uncovers unexpected links between playwrights who, despite differing national and ideological contexts, exhibit striking stylistic affinities.

By integrating digital approaches with close reading, this dissertation offers a replicable model for the large-scale study of historical literary corpora. It challenges traditional narratives about early modern drama by demonstrating the complexity of Neo-Latin literary networks and the role of computational analysis in uncovering hidden patterns. Ultimately, this research highlights the need to re-evaluate Neo-Latin drama as a dynamic and influential component of early modern European literature.

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When I first applied for a PhD, I could hardly believe anyone would value my person so much as to accept me. I've always felt research and academia were my path, my calling, and what I would devote my life to. But five years ago, I was just starting out. I didn't feel knowledgeable enough; I was still looking for someone who could help me grow.

In a moment of lazy hopefulness, I applied for a postdoc position in Digital Humanities applied to the study of Latin, casually asking if there was any possibility to turn it into a PhD. I had no expectations. But then I was interviewed, and the unexpected happened: this possibility became reality. I was, quite simply, overjoyed.

Looking back, I now know how lucky I was. My two supervisors were the best I could have ever hoped for.

Prof. Dr. Jan Bloemendal, my first supervisor and Principal Investigator of the TransLatin project within which this dissertation was written. He is a true humanist like the great minds of old, a Renaissance intellectual like Erasmus, Reuchlin, Grotius, with whom he converses daily. A sharp intellect with vast curiosity, a scholar with a rare openness to innovation, a quality thanks to which I was able to pursue my PhD as a digital humanist in the first place. His guidance through the world of Neo-Latin drama, and our many conversations, helped me shape the direction of this research in new and meaningful ways, pushing me to greater heights.

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This dissertation is dedicated to her.

*apparirà con gli occhi verdi e ciglia nere e bocca rossa
anima luminosa come arcobaleno puro*

CURRICULUM VITAE

Andrea Peverelli was born on May 5, 1994, in Milan, Italy. He studied Modern Literature and Humanities at the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore in Milan, earning both his Bachelor's degree (2016) and Master's degree (2018) in Modern Philology, Literature, and Linguistics, both awarded cum laude. His studies focused on classical and modern literature, classical languages, philology, and historical linguistics, with additional courses in theology, semiotics, and corpus linguistics.

Following his Master's degree, Andrea worked on multiple research projects at various international institutions, collaborating with Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Milan), the University of Geneva and the University of Oslo. During this period, he contributed to projects in linguistic annotation, treebanking, and the digital processing of historical texts, working with large corpora of Latin literature, from classical to medieval texts (LiLa Project). His expertise in computational text analysis led him to develop tools for Latin text processing and participate in the creation of linguistic resources, including lexicons, word embeddings, and morphological analysers.

In 2020, Andrea began his doctoral research at the Huygens Institute (KNAW), as part of the TransLatin Project and under the supervision of prof. dr. Jan Bloemendal and dr. Marieke van Erp and, in a later stage, Dirk van Miert. His research focuses on tracing literary influence, modelling the circulation of texts across Europe, and analysing the role of religious and cultural factors in shaping stylistic trends. In addition, Andrea developed computational tools for processing historical texts, including a program for Latin text pre-processing tool.

Throughout his PhD, Andrea collaborated with multiple research groups, including the DHLab at KNAW, the Kennis en Kunstpraktijken research group, and the DraCor project (for the stylometric analysis of early modern drama). He has actively participated in international conferences and workshops, presenting his findings at venues such as Oxford University, Utrecht University, the University of Groningen, the University of Vienna, the University of Venice and the Computational Humanities Research Conference. His expertise has contributed to discussions in Digital Humanities, classical reception studies, and computational literary analysis, furthering the use of AI-driven methods for historical text analysis.

Beyond research, Andrea has been involved in teaching and academic service, supervising students, organising workshops, and reviewing for international journals. His expertise lies at the intersection of Digital Humanities, classical languages, and computational literary analysis, exploring how AI-driven methods can enhance the study of historical and literary texts.